

MONTEVITIS

Together for the mitigation of climate change's impact on viticulture

Conference Proceedings Book

Student Micro-Conference in Applied Mathematics – AM Connect 2024

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**Student Micro-Conference in Applied Mathematics
AM Connect 2024**

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Preface

The Student Micro-Conference in Applied Mathematics (AM Connect 2024) served as a platform for BSc, MSc, and PhD students to showcase their research, connect with peers, and engage in meaningful discussions. The event focuses on contemporary topics such as Climate Change Challenges and Stochastic Processes, promoting interdisciplinary collaboration in applied mathematics.

We extend our gratitude to all participants, contributors, and organizers who have made this event possible. We hope this conference inspires further exploration and innovation in applied mathematics.

The motivation for the organisation of AM Connect 2024 conference came from the MONTEVITIS project “Integrating a comprehensive European approach for climate change mitigation and adaptation in Montenegro viticulture”, funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe, the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2021–2027) under grant agreement n° 101059461. This conference has provided an excellent opportunity for students to share their work, collaborate with peers, and discuss contemporary issues in applied mathematics. We thank everyone for their contributions and look forward to future editions of this conference.

On behalf of the editors,

Conference coordinator
Prof. Marko Simeunović

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About the MONTEVITIS project

MONTEVITIS is a Horizon Europe-funded project designed to strengthen research and innovation capacities in Montenegrin viticulture through climate science, precision agriculture, and digital technologies. The project addresses the increasing vulnerability of viticulture to climate change and extreme weather by leveraging advanced modelling tools and field research. Given that grapevines are highly sensitive to local terroirs and atmospheric conditions, MONTEVITIS integrates analytical and modelling tools to assess climate change impacts on vine physiology, yield, and wine quality.

Montenegro lacks systematic, science-based knowledge on climate change effects in viticulture, as well as sophisticated crop modelling tools. MONTEVITIS aims to bridge this gap by transferring EU expertise and adapting climate and viticulture models to local conditions. It enhances the research and collaboration capacities of the University of Donja Gorica (UDG) and its partners while promoting sustainable vineyard management through precision viticulture technologies and decision-support tools.

*The project consortium includes leading institutions from Europe and Montenegro: **University of Donja Gorica (Montenegro), Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (Portugal), Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (Germany), Università degli Studi di Firenze (Italy), Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (Luxembourg), Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (Portugal), Institute for Hydrometeorology and Seismology of Montenegro, and Montenegrin wine producers Vinograd i podrum Rajković (RAJ), Buk Doo Za Proizvodnju, Promet Roba i Usluga, Export - Import, Podgorica (BUK), MNB Krupa, Ulcinj (KRU), and Vučinić Dragica (ZNT).***

By fostering international collaboration, knowledge transfer, and capacity building, MONTEVITIS contributes to the sustainability and competitiveness of Montenegrin viticulture. Its long-term impact includes improved climate adaptation strategies, increased research integration, and enhanced resilience of wine production in Montenegro and beyond.

MONTEVITIS

Together for the mitigation of climate change's impact on viticulture

Conference Agenda

Student Micro-Conference in Applied Mathematics – AM Connect 2024

December 2nd, 2024

Funded by
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Student Micro-Conference in Applied Mathematics
AM CONNECT 2024

Session 1: Climate Change Challenges

Venue: UDG, Room Vizija

Online: <https://us06web.zoom.us/j/85067915901?pwd=xoxJw6lLEbw26NiV6SJix7vY0gfoEA.1>

Time (CET)	Title	Speaker/Participants
09:00 – 09:10	Welcome Remarks	Kruna Ratković, UDG
Presentation session		
09:10 – 09:20	Mapping vineyard areas in Montenegro using QGIS	Enisa Trubljanin, UDG
09:20 – 09:30	Mean temperatures weather forecasting: assessing Laplacian smoothing in Markov chains model	Sara Medojević, UDG
09:30 – 09:40	Impact of annual mean temperature (BIO1) on vineyard yield in Montenegro	Tamara Racković, UDG
09:40 – 09:50	Relationships between climate variability and grapevine phenology	Nadira Pupović, UDG
09:50 – 10:00	Implementation of kaolin in the vineyard as a measure of adaptation to climate change	Luka Andrić, UDG
10:00 – 10:10	Climate data downscaling with CHELSA - workshop insights and future applications	Arslan Vlahovljak, UDG
10:10 – 10:20	The Impact of climate change on agriculture: mathematical models for yield prediction	Balša Klikovac, UDG
10:20 – 10:30	Temperature trends and patterns in Montenegro	Dino Đerekerac, UDG
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break	
11:00 – 11:10	Relationship between tropospheric ozone and hot extreme events – identification of its predictors in mainland Portugal	Catarina Alonso; João Santos; Célia Gouveia, UTAD
11:10 – 11:20	Assessing climate impacts on viticulture in Montenegro: bioclimatic analysis and future projections for wine regions	Aleksandar Zečević, IHMS
11:20 – 11:30	CHELSA Algorithm and climate change: exploring high-resolution data for sustainable future planning	Mihailo Đurović, UDG
11:30 – 11:40	Impact of climate change on public finances and fiscal policy	Sara Šundić, UDG
11:40 – 11:50	Impact of climate change on agricultural production and GDP: a case study of Montenegro	Jana Mrvaljević, UDG
11:50 – 12:00	The impact of climate change on the job market – threats and opportunities	Elmedina Mušanović, UDG
12:00 – 12:10	The potential and prospects of Montenegro in the context of a circular transition	Jovana Popović, UDG
12:10 – 12:20	Utilization of anomaly detection techniques for soil salinity in the context of climate change challenges: an overview	Farida Asadova, OBU
12:20 – 12:30	Personalized risk assessment of physiological parameters using a fuzzy approach	Felisberto David Wandi Chivela, OBU
Closing remarks		

**Student Micro-Conference in Applied Mathematics
AM Connect 2024**

Session 2: Stochastic processes

Venue: UDG, Room S38

Time	Title	Speaker/Participants
08:00 – 08:10	Welcome Remarks	Nataša Kovač, UDG
Presentation session		
08:10 – 08:20	Primjena stohastičkih procesa na opšti proces rađanja i umiranja	Milica Đukanović, UDG
08:20 – 08:30	Primjena Markovljevih lanaca u algoritmu Page rank	Elma Škrijelj, UDG
08:30 – 08:40	Stohastički procesi u onkologiji	Adlija Kalamperović, UDG
08:40 – 08:50	Bajesova verovatnoća u vremenskoj prognozi	Ajeta Cenović, UDG
08:50 – 09:00	Binomni proces	Dragana Gutić, UDG
09:00 – 09:10	Primjena Levijevih procesa u modelovanju anomalijских pojava u finansijskim tržištima	Marko Furundžić, UDG
09:10 – 09:20	Primjena stohastičkih modela u životnom osiguranju	Amina Murić, UDG
09:20 – 09:30	Primjena Wienerovog procesa u modeliranju kretanja cijena akcija	Aleksandar Nedović, UDG
09:30 – 09:40	Markovljevi lanci u finansijama	Anđela Janković, UDG
Closing remarks		

Session 1

Climate Change Challenges

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Mapping vineyard areas in Montenegro using QGIS

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Abstract—This paper focuses on the visualization and mapping of vineyard areas and vineyard networks in Montenegro, providing a representation that has not been previously available. Using QGIS, an open-source geographic information system, the primary objective of this research is to generate and present vineyards on detailed maps that will help in making decisions in the viticulture sector in Montenegro, utilizing data from the Copernicus and using data manually collected as part of the Montevis project in order to supplement the map with all the vineyards in Montenegro. These maps are of particular importance for adapting the vineyard to the climate region in which it is located.

Keywords—QGIS, Vineyard mapping, Copernicus, climate change

I. INTRODUCTION

The mapping of vineyard areas is an important step in promoting sustainable agriculture and addressing the challenges posed by climate change. Accurate and comprehensive maps enable better decision-making, resource management, and adaptation strategies, particularly in regions like Montenegro, where viticulture holds both cultural and economic significance.

Montenegro's diverse geography and favorable climate make it an ideal location for viticulture, a practice deeply rooted in the country's cultural and agricultural traditions. Renowned for its indigenous grape varieties, such as *Vranac* and *Krstač*, Montenegro's vineyards contribute significantly to the national economy and identity as a wine-producing region [1].

Accurate vineyard mapping is essential for sustainable agricultural development, providing valuable data for land management, resource optimization, and environmental protection. Geographic Information Systems (GIS), particularly QGIS (Quantum GIS), offer powerful tools for spatial analysis, enabling efficient identification and monitoring of vineyard areas [2]. This study aims to map vineyard regions in Montenegro using QGIS, highlighting their distribution and potential for future development. The novelty of this study lies in creating detailed maps of vineyard areas which were not previously available for Montenegro. These tools are intended to offer new insights into the spatial distribution of vineyards and their interaction with climate trends, contributing to more informed planning and management in the viticulture sector.

Viticulture in Montenegro is an integral part of the country's agricultural heritage, with vineyards spread across diverse terrains and climates. However, the lack of precise spatial data has limited the potential for systematic development and climate adaptation. Temperature data, such as those from the CHELSA dataset, are crucial for understanding the climatic conditions affecting grapevine growth, ripening, and yield. Incorporating these data into vineyard mapping allows for better assessment of suitability zones and potential risks, ultimately supporting the sustainable growth of the wine industry in Montenegro.

II. CLIMATE IN MONTENEGRO

Climate change has a profound impact on viticulture, as shifts in temperature, the frequency of droughts, extreme weather events, and irregular precipitation patterns directly affect grapevine growth, ripening, and overall wine quality. These changes can alter the traditional characteristics of wine regions, challenging producers to maintain consistency and quality [3]. Mapping vineyard regions plays a role in adapting to these challenges by identifying microclimates and soil conditions that are more resilient to climatic variability. Such detailed mapping enables targeted adaptation strategies, including the selection of climate-resilient grape varieties, optimized irrigation practices, and adjusted harvest timings, ensuring the long-term sustainability of viticulture [4].

A. Geographical and Climatic Characteristics of Montenegro

Montenegro is a small, yet geographically diverse country located in Southeast Europe, along the Adriatic Sea. Its terrain varies from coastal plains to rugged mountains, creating distinct microclimates that are suitable for various agricultural activities, including viticulture. The soil diversity in Montenegro, ranging from calcareous and sandy soils along the coast to alluvial and fertile soils in the plains, further supports the cultivation of grapevines. These natural conditions provide an ideal foundation for producing high-quality wines, with specific regions excelling due to their unique combinations of soil and climate. The climate in Montenegro is diverse due to its geographical features, ranging from coastal areas to mountainous regions. It can be categorized into three main climatic zones (*Figure 1*) [5].

Fig. 1. Division of Montenegro into three climatic regions

Mediterranean climate founds along the Adriatic coast, characterized by hot, dry summers and mild, rainy winters. This zone is ideal for growing Mediterranean crops, including olives, citrus fruits, and grapes. Continental climate presents in the central regions and the *Zeta* plain, with warm summers and cold winters. This area supports a mix of Mediterranean and continental agriculture. Mountain climate founds in the northern and higher-altitude regions, with cooler summers and harsh winters [6]. This zone is less suitable for vineyard development due to lower temperatures.

The warm Mediterranean climate and favorable soil conditions make the areas around *Ulcinj*, *Bar*, and *Herceg Novi* suitable for grape cultivation. *Zeta* and *Bjelopavlići* plains located in the central part of Montenegro, have a mix of Mediterranean and continental influences, making them excellent for viticulture [6]. This part of Montenegro has the largest number of vineyards because the climate is suitable for the development of vines. Lake Scadar region is renowned for its vineyards and wine production, with indigenous grape varieties like *Vranac* and *Krstač* thriving here. Montenegro's diverse climate and fertile soil provide excellent conditions for high-quality wine production, with some regions gaining international recognition for their wines [7].

B. QGIS for mapping vineyard areas

QGIS is a powerful open-source Geographic Information System tool that plays a role in mapping vineyard regions for adapting to climate change. With its user-friendly interface and extensive functionality, QGIS allows for the integration and analysis of spatial data, such as soil types, topography, microclimatic conditions, and hydrology [8]. By overlaying these datasets, users can identify areas most suitable for viticulture under changing climatic conditions. QGIS also supports advanced geostatistical analyses, enabling wine producers to model potential impacts of climate scenarios and develop precise adaptation strategies [9]. Its open-source nature makes it accessible to a wide range of users, fostering innovation and collaboration in sustainable vineyard management.

III. VINEYARD MAPPING WITH COPERNICUS DATA

This paper has been prepared using European Union's Copernicus Land Monitoring Service information [10]. A land map for the territory of the state of Montenegro was downloaded from the Copernicus website. In its current form,

the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) dataset from Copernicus provides a pan-European inventory of land cover and land use, encompassing 44 thematic classes, ranging from extensive forested areas to individual vineyards. This product is updated every six years with new status layers, with the most recent update completed in 2018. The CLC dataset serves a wide range of users and offers nearly limitless potential for practical applications, including environmental monitoring, land use planning, climate change assessment, and emergency management [11].

The Excel legend file, which is among the downloaded data in the dataset, contains CLC codes where vineyards in Montenegro are located under CLC code 221. The *Figure 2* shows the map of vineyards of Montenegro using QGIS of available vineyards in this vector file from Copernicus.

Fig. 2. Vineyards in Montenegro available from Copernicus

It is noticeable that only a few of the largest vineyards in Montenegro are shown, namely in the territory of the municipalities of Podgorica and Tuzi. In this version from 2018, these are the only available wine areas in Montenegro. Regardless of the fact that based on data from Copernicus, there is only a display for vineyards in the area around Podgorica, thus only a few of the largest vineyards are represented. In the continuation of the work, the methodology of data collection for all vineyards of Montenegro and their mapping using the QGIS tool is presented.

IV. MAPPING VINEYARDS WITH DATA COLLECTED IN MONTENEGRO

Since the data on the coordinates of the vineyards used for mapping them using QGIS proved to be insufficient for the presentation of the state of the vineyards in Montenegro, new data was collected. Data was collected manually using the Geoportal from which the coordinates of each vineyard were read. The data on the number of registered vineyards in Montenegro were taken from the Vineyard Register of Montenegro. Excel files were created with the coordinates of each plot and converted into shapefiles that were used as input data in QGIS to display those vineyards on the map. Display (Figure 3) of a vineyard plots from the Geoportal whose coordinates were taken and shapefiles were created for further mapping in QGIS.

Fig. 3. An example of a vineyard plot on the Geoportal

The fact that the conditions, the previously described climate in Montenegro, are particularly favorable for the development of vineyards in the central part is confirmed by the generation of a new vineyard map for Montenegro. Based on the collected data, the previously created map with the help of data from Copernicus was enriched with new vineyards (Figure 4). Some vineyards occupy very small areas, so they are less visible in the picture. The diversity of the Montenegrin state's climate in a small area is also reflected in the vineyards, one of which is developed in the very north of the country in the municipality of Pljevlja and several vineyards are located in Boka Kotorska and in Herceg Novi.

The spatial analysis conducted using QGIS produced detailed maps of vineyard areas in Montenegro. These maps highlight the concentration of vineyards in key regions such as the Scadar lake basin, the Zeta and Bjelopavlići plains, and select parts of the coastal zones like Bar and Ulcinj. The mapping process identified both existing vineyards and areas with high potential for future cultivation, offering a clear visualization of viticultural activities across the country.

A. Insights on Vineyard Distribution and size

The analysis revealed that the majority of vineyards are located in lowland areas with Mediterranean or transitional climates, where conditions for grape cultivation are optimal. Vineyard sizes varied significantly, with larger, commercial vineyards concentrated in the plains, while smaller, family-operated vineyards were more common in coastal and hillside regions. Notably, the Vranac grape dominates these regions

Fig. 4. Map of vineyards in Montenegro

due to its adaptability to local conditions. Vineyards were predominantly located in regions with average annual temperatures of 12–18°C and precipitation levels of 1,000–1,500 mm/year, aligning with the requirements of grape cultivation [12].

This visualization has enabled a clear depiction of the distribution of registered vineyards. The highest concentration of vineyards is located in the central region of Montenegro (Figure 5), with the largest area occupied by the vineyard owned by the company *Plantaže*. Soils in vineyard areas were mainly calcareous or sandy-loamy, ensuring good drainage and nutrient availability [13]. Proximity to water bodies, such as Lake Scadar, was also identified as a factor enhancing microclimatic conditions for viticulture.

Fig. 5. Vineyards in the central part of the country

V. VINEYARD MAP AND CLIMATE DATA

For the purposes of this research, climate data from the publicly available CHELSA dataset (Climatologies at High

Resolution for the Earth's Land Surface Areas) were employed [14]. The dataset provides high-resolution climate data, which are particularly suitable for ecological and environmental analyses. For this study, historical data from the period 1981–2010 were used, ensuring a reliable and comprehensive overview of the long-term climatic conditions.

As a case study to demonstrate the potential application of this data, two bioclimatic variables were selected: the mean annual temperature and the mean annual precipitation. These variables were chosen due to their critical influence on the suitability and sustainability of viticulture [15]. Using QGIS, the data were processed, mapped, and visualized to illustrate the spatial variability of these climatic factors across the selected region.

The mapping and visualization provide valuable insights into how climatic conditions influence vineyard development and productivity. By focusing on these two variables, the research highlights the utility of CHELSA data for detailed spatial analysis and decision-making in agricultural and environmental management. CHELSA dataset contains as many as 19 bioclimatic variables whose analysis can be observed. This approach can be expanded to include additional bioclimatic variables, offering a robust framework for assessing climate impacts on other crops and ecological systems.

Based on the analyzed climatic data, heatmaps were generated to depict the spatial distribution of mean annual temperature and precipitation. These visualizations provide an intuitive understanding of the current climatic conditions relevant to viticulture. Historical climatological data are illustrated in Figure 6, where temperature (left) is expressed in degrees Celsius, and precipitation (right) in mm per square meter. The integration of these heatmaps demonstrates how the adaptability of vineyards to emerging climatic conditions can be assessed. Given the increasingly extreme nature of climate change, these historical data serve as a valuable baseline for developing predictive models for future temperature and precipitation patterns. Such models can be instrumental in planning new areas for vineyard development, relocating existing vineyards to more favorable regions, and implementing necessary protective and adaptive measures. By preparing for the climatic conditions anticipated in the coming years, stakeholders in viticulture can ensure resilience and sustainability despite the pronounced challenges posed by climate change [16].

Fig. 6. Heat maps for average annual temperature (right) and amount of precipitation (left)

The most favorable conditions of temperature and precipitation for the development of vineyards depend on the grape variety and specific local characteristics, but in general, the parameters listed below are considered optimal for most wine-growing areas in Montenegro. During the growing season (spring-summer), the optimal daily temperature range is between 18°C and 32°C. The minimum night temperature must not fall below 10°C during the key stages of growth (especially during flowering and ripening) and during winter, temperatures should be low, but not extreme, to allow for a dormant period. The optimal range for the winter period is from -5°C to 10°C, with the fact that temperatures below -20°C can cause damage to the vines [17]. The most favorable annual mean temperature for vineyards is between 12°C and 20°C, depending on the variety and region .

The optimum range of annual precipitation is between 600 mm and 1200 mm. Rainfall should be evenly distributed, with increased amounts during spring and early summer to support growth, while in the later stages of ripening drought can contribute to grape sugar concentration. Excessive rainfall, especially during flowering and ripening periods, can increase the risk of diseases such as downy mildew [18]. In arid regions, controlled irrigation may be necessary to ensure sufficient water during key stages of vine development.

The central part of Montenegro, especially around the areas of the municipalities of *Podgorica* and *Tuzi*, in the past period almost completely corresponded to these conditions, however, climate changes have been very noticeable in recent years, and new changes are only foreseen, so it is necessary to form vineyards in the most favorable places for their development. It is the combination of spatial maps of vineyards presented using QGIS with maps of climatic conditions that can offer solutions for adapting vineyards to the weather conditions that are expected in the future.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper demonstrates the significant role of QGIS as a versatile and powerful tool for mapping and analyzing vineyard regions in Montenegro. By leveraging QGIS, this research not only visualizes vineyard distribution but also integrates various datasets, such as climate data from the CHELSA dataset and land use data from Copernicus, to generate a comprehensive and detailed spatial representation of Montenegro's vineyards.

The research presented in this paper offers a comprehensive approach to mapping vineyards in Montenegro, addressing the critical need for detailed spatial data in the viticulture sector. Future research in this area needs to focus on more precise data on vineyard locations in this country so that they can be successfully displayed on the map and their common features can be used for further analysis. By integrating data from the Copernicus site, manually collected data from Geoportal and those available from the CHELSA dataset, the resulting maps provide a more accurate representation of the distribution and characteristics of vineyards across Montenegro. These maps, combined with climate data from the CHELSA dataset, are not only valuable for identifying current vineyard locations but also serve as a

foundational tool for future planning and adaptation in response to climate change.

The generated heatmaps of average annual temperature and precipitation illustrate the climatic variability within Montenegro, highlighting regions best suited for viticulture under existing conditions. However, the ongoing and projected impacts of climate change demand proactive strategies to ensure the sustainability of viticulture in the region. These strategies include identifying and developing new areas for vineyard cultivation, relocating vineyards from less favorable areas, and implementing measures for climate adaptation and protection.

The combination of GIS-based mapping with historical climate data provides a powerful methodology for assessing the impact of environmental factors on viticulture. This approach enables stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding vineyard management, land use, and resource allocation, fostering resilience against the challenges posed by climate change. Future work should focus on regularly updating the vineyard database and integrating predictive climate models to refine these insights further, ensuring that Montenegro's viticulture continues to thrive in a changing environment.

The resulting map of vineyards in Montenegro can be supplemented and improved. By obtaining data on the parcels of other winegrowers in Montenegro, the map can be supplemented and thereby give a more precise picture of the situation. Given that the data from the Geoportal was collected from 2016, when it was last updated, there is a high probability that there have been many changes in the plots and the appearance of some of the vineyards. For this reason, any updating of the data on the geoportal would give a more credible situation about active and registered vineyards in Montenegro.

Based on the climate data taken from the CHELSA dataset and the observed period of the previous 30 years of climate data in Montenegro, observing the average temperature and precipitation, the most favorable areas for growing vines can be observed. The challenges brought by climate change and changes in temperature and precipitation can be helpful in that, in combination with mapped vineyards using QGIS and heat maps formed also in QGIS using historical data used from the CHELSA dataset, conclusions are made about the most favorable areas for vineyard development in subsequent periods.

QGIS application in this research underscores the importance of geographic information systems in supporting data-driven decision-making, fostering innovation, and addressing the pressing challenges of climate change in agricultural practices. Future efforts should continue to explore and expand the use of QGIS in similar studies, ensuring its continued contribution to the sustainable development of viticulture and other agricultural sectors.

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(Grant Agreement number 101059461) under the special Twinning call for Western Balkans HORIZONWIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02 that aims to promote networking between research institutes of the Western Balkan countries and top-class leading counterparts at the EU level, in the field of precision viticulture and climate change.

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Mean Temperature Forecasting: Assessing Laplace Smoothing in a Markov Chain Model

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Abstract—Climate change and weather forecasting play a pivotal role in daily life, influencing critical aspects such as human health, water and food security, ecosystems, transportation, energy, and tourism. Over the years, a variety of linear and nonlinear models have been employed to develop increasingly precise forecasting systems. The Markov Chain model serves as an effective tool for simplifying the complexity of weather forecasting by focusing on discrete weather states. Laplace Smoothing is a technique that is beneficial in cases where transitions between two states are rare or underrepresented. This paper explores the development and comparative analysis of the Markov Chain model and the Markov Chain model enhanced with Laplace Smoothing. The available data used in this paper consists of mean temperature records from November 2018 to December 2023, obtained from the Podgorica locality. This data was divided into four seasonal groups, specifically designed for making predictions of the mean temperature state for each day in the year 2023. Both types of models showed precision greater than 60%. Models with Laplace Smoothing generally exhibited lower overall precision compared to the standard Markov Chain models. However, they demonstrated significantly improved precision during the months when the Markov Chain models struggled to deliver consistent performance.

Index Terms—Markov Chains, Laplace Smoothing, mean temperature, forecast.

I. INTRODUCTION

People have sought to predict the future state of the atmosphere since ancient times [1]. Climate change and weather conditions influence people’s daily lives and activities, which play a significant role in planning and decision-making processes. Industries such as agriculture, transportation, tourism, and construction are highly weather-dependent. Weather forecasting is a key component of the risk assessment and risk management process. It vastly influences the global economy, human health, and water and food security [2], [3].

Significant improvements in the field of weather forecasting were made towards the end of the 19th century. This new approach to weather forecasting began with Abbe and Bjerknes, who understood that having current weather observations could be used as initial values for the problem of predicting the future state of the atmosphere. This problem involves solving the governing partial differential equations based on initial conditions [4].

This new approach to weather forecasting sparked revolutions and modernized techniques used for understanding and describing the chaotic nature of the atmosphere in the

years that followed. Weather refers to the daily fluctuations in the state of the atmosphere, which is the gaseous layer surrounding the Earth. Predicting the weather is a complex task due to the intricate nature of weather changes. Numerous factors influence weather, such as solar heating, radiation, and atmospheric absorption [5]. These factors, combined with various weather elements like temperature, air pressure, wind, humidity, precipitation, visibility, cloud cover, and sunlight exposure, make weather predictions challenging [6]. Building a model that takes into consideration multiple factors, as well as numerous interactive variables over a large area, is what makes this task challenging.

Weather forecasting is a multidisciplinary process that integrates different scientific areas. Atmospheric changes follow the principles of the physical laws of fluid dynamics and thermodynamics [7]. The process of weather forecasting includes different mathematical, statistical, and empirical techniques. One of the new breakthroughs was numerical weather prediction, which took place from the 1970s to the 1980s [8]. Numerical weather prediction methods include numerical and statistical methods. Numerical methods convert global-scale model outputs into daily weather variables, which are used to simulate atmospheric evolution and define current weather changes. These methods are effective in predicting both present and future climate events, as well as making accurate long-term predictions [9]. One of the key numerical weather prediction methods is the use of a system of partial differential equations [10]. Over the years, numerical weather prediction methods have improved and now include collections of equations that describe weather patterns [11]. Statistical methods play a crucial role in weather and climate forecasting across time scales, as they are based on observed relationships between input and forecasted variables. There are numerous statistical methods used every day, with notable ones being: linear regression, correlation analysis, principal component analysis, canonical correlation analysis, and singular value decomposition [8].

The implementation of these methods and models includes the use of new technologies, high-tech equipment, and supercomputers. Data used for weather forecasting is collected from different sources, such as ground-based measurement stations, satellites, sensors, and radars [12]. Storing this kind of data, which is disorganized and heterogeneous, requires large data

storage and the use of big data [2]. These factors vastly impact the precision of forecasts.

The process of weather forecasting includes observation and data collection, assimilation, processing and analysis, and extrapolation to predict the future state of the atmosphere [13]. Observation and data collection include gathering data through different tools and methods to create a comprehensive dataset that provides insight into past and current atmospheric states. The purpose of data assimilation is to estimate the most accurate atmospheric state. This is achieved by combining observed data with the model. Then, the previous model forecast is compared with newly acquired observations, and the model state is updated to incorporate the new observations. Following this, a new forecast is generated, and the process repeats [14]. Processing and analysis involve the use of various models to simulate atmospheric behavior and analyze variables so that hidden patterns can be recognized. All of these processes are done so that the data and the model can be prepared for extrapolating new data, which goes beyond the original range of observation [15], [16].

Deterministic models make a single prediction based on one initial condition. Although numerical weather prediction models can be based on deterministic processes, these models can not be used for long-term predictions. They don't account for random fluctuations, and they are highly sensitive to small errors in the initial conditions [17]. In order to bypass these limitations, stochastic models are used. Stochastic models account for uncertainties and random fluctuations, reduce systematic biases, and improve long-term predictions [18]. The Markov Chain model is a stochastic model that can be used for long-term weather forecasting. This paper focuses on making long-term mean temperature predictions using a single-variable Markov Chains model and a single-variable Markov Chains model enhanced with Laplace Smoothing.

Although no studies specifically address mean temperature forecasting using a Markov Chain model enhanced with Laplace Smoothing, existing literature explores the application of Markov Chain models in weather forecasting. The study by Eberle, Cevasco, Schwarzkopf, et al. [19], focuses on multivariate simulation of offshore weather time series using Markov Chain models of the first and second order, Autoregressive models, and Long Short-Term Memory models. These models were trained on a 40-year dataset with 1-hour resolution. Thereafter, the models simulated 25-year time series, which were analysed based on several time series metrics and criteria. Taking into consideration that predictions were made on a 25-year time span, the models' results were judged to be among the best, especially in terms of their correlation metrics. The main objective, of the paper by Khatani and Ghose [20], is weather forecasting using a Hidden Markov Model. The model was trained on a dataset containing 21 years of observed weather data. Based on current weather data, the model is able to make reliable predictions for the next five days. The paper by Liu, Ren, Yuan, and Yang [21], introduced an early warning system to forecast drought using the Palmer Drought Severity Index (PDSI) and the Markov Chain model. Using the Markov

Chain model with varying steps, the drought states for all 12 months of the year 2000 were forecasted based on the PDSI. The results show that the Markov Chain model is effective for early warning.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

A. An Overview of the Datasets

The data used in this paper was obtained from the Department of Hydrometeorology and Seismology of Montenegro, which was published in the Yearbooks of Meteorological and Hydrological Data, from November 2018 to December 2023. Mean temperatures were observed for the Podgorica locality. Temperature measurements are conducted at measuring stations at 7 : 00h, 14 : 00h, and 21 : 00h local time. Mean temperature is calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Mean Temperature} = \frac{T_7 + T_{14} + 2 * T_{21}}{4} \quad (1)$$

where T_7 , T_{14} , and T_{21} are temperature values measured at 7 : 00h, 14 : 00h, and 21 : 00h, respectively [22].

To be able to use this dataset for training the Markov Chains model, the dataset needed to be modified during the preprocessing of the data. The first part of this process involved assigning a specific state to each data point. Categorization of the data was based on the following rules:

- If the mean temperature $\leq 10C^\circ$ for a specific data point, that data is labelled as *Cold*,
- If the $10C^\circ < \text{mean temperature} \leq 20C^\circ$ for a specific data point, that data is labelled as *Moderate*,
- If the mean temperature $> 20C^\circ$ for a specific data point, that data is labelled as *Warm*.

A new dataset was formed and was completely written in terms of the states: Cold, Moderate, and Warm.

The second part of this process involved dividing this new dataset into four individual datasets. Each of these four datasets was specifically created to describe mean temperature changes of the four seasons: spring, summer, autumn, and winter.

The spring dataset contained data for the months of February, March, April, and May for the years 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and February of 2023.

The summer dataset contained data for the months of May, June, July, and August for the years 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and May of 2023.

The autumn dataset contained data for the months of August, September, October, and November for the years 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and August of 2023.

The winter dataset contained data for the months of January, February, November, and December for the years 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, November and December of 2018 and November of 2023.

B. Theoretical Foundation of Markov Chains and Laplace Smoothing

Ross gave an introduction to stochastic processes in his book [23]. *Stochastic process* $X = \{X(t), t \in T\}$ is a collection of

random variables, where T represents the index set, $X(t)$ is a random variable that represents the state of the process at time t . If the index set T is a countable set, X is a *discrete-time stochastic process*, and if T is a continuum, X is a *continuous-time process*. Any realization of X is called a *sample path*.

Consider a stochastic process X_n , $n = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ that takes on a finite or countable number of possible values. Process is in the *state i at time n* , if $X_n = i$. Probability $P_{i,j}$ is a probability for which the process, starting from the state i would change to the state j .

A process X_0, X_1, \dots satisfies the *Markov property*, if

$$P\{X_{n+1} = i_{n+1} | X_n = i_n, X_{n-1} = i_{n-1}, \dots, X_0 = i_0\} = P\{X_{n+1} = i_{n+1} | X_n = i_n\} \quad (2)$$

for all $n \geq 0$ and all $i_0, \dots, i_{n+1} \in S$ [24]. Markov property explains the future state of the process depends only on the present state and not on the sequence of events that preceded it. A stochastic process that satisfies the Markov property is called a *Markov Chain*.

Probabilities are nonnegative, and the process must transition into some state and satisfy properties represented with (3) and (4).

$$P_{i,j} \geq 0 \text{ for } i, j \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} P_{i,j} = 1 \text{ for } i = 0, 1, \dots \quad (4)$$

Let P denote the matrix of one-step *transition probabilities*, which is defined as (5).

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} P_{00} & P_{01} & P_{02} & \dots \\ P_{10} & P_{11} & P_{12} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \\ P_{i0} & P_{i1} & P_{i2} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Consider the set of states $S = \{C, M, W\}$ (C stands for Cold, M stands for Moderate, and W stands for Warm), for some given stochastic process. Starting from any state, the stochastic process can transition to any other state or to itself, which is show in the Fig 1. Transition probability $P_{i,j}$ for $i, j \in S$ is calculated using formula (6) [23].

$$P_{i,j} = \frac{\text{Number of transitions from state } i \text{ to state } j}{\text{Total number of transitions from state } i} \quad (6)$$

Using Markov Chains has its advantages, such as their simple structure, ability to describe both discrete and continuous-time processes, and ability to forecast future states based on the current state and transition probabilities, which makes them memory-efficient and easier to comprehend. While Markov Chains are widely applicable across various fields and are relatively straightforward to implement, they also have their drawbacks and limitations.

Fig. 1. Example of a schematic illustration of the possible transitions between different states in a stochastic process.

First is the assumption that transition probabilities are constant and that they don't change or evolve over time.

Second is that the performance of Markov Chains can be adversely affected by their sensitivity to initial conditions, resulting in unreliable predictions.

Third is that the problem of zero probabilities in the transition matrix and its inability to make predictions based on under-represented or previously unrecorded situations. All of these limitations are based on the Markov property and transition probabilities.

Additive Smoothing is a well-known technique used in fields like statistics, machine learning, natural language processing, and information retrieval for smoothing categorical data. Additive Smoothing is a technique used as a form of noise reduction to smooth out noisy datasets by adding a small amount of noise to the dataset in order to obscure the original noise. This technique is used to identify the underlying trends in the data [25].

The main idea behind Additive Smoothing is to distribute some probabilities by adding a constant α . As explained in [26], depending on the chosen value for the constant α , it is possible to use one of the subtypes of Additive Smoothing:

- *Laplace Smoothing*, if $\alpha = 1$
- *Lidstone Smoothing*, if $0 < \alpha < 1$.

Laplace Smoothing is used for solving the problem of zero probability. This technique is applied in situations where there are new observations, that have not appeared in the training data [27].

Let S be a set of states for which $s_i, s_j \in S$. $P(s_j | s_i)$ is the probability of transitioning from state s_i to s_j .

$P(s_j | s_i)$ for the Laplace Smoothing is defined as (7) [28].

$$P(s_j | s_i) = \frac{\text{Number of transitions}(s_i \rightarrow s_j) + 1}{\sum_{j=1} (\text{Number of transitions}(s_i \rightarrow s_j) + 1)} \quad (7)$$

C. Models development

The development of all models took place in Google Colab, leveraging a GPU T4. The purpose of this paper is developing models that would be able to make reliable predictions of the mean temperature for each day of the year 2023 in the Podgorica locality, based on previous historical data.

This paper focuses on two types of models: Markov Chain based model and Markov Chain based model enhanced with Laplace Smoothing.

The entire dataset was divided into four subsets, requiring each model type to be trained on each of these individual sets. The initial conditions, represented by historical data, were written in the form of nested dictionaries.

While each season comprises three months, the historical data also includes one month preceding them. This approach was implemented to enhance the precision of the model predictions during training. The initial state or initial conditions for making predictions are derived from the mean temperature state of last day for each of these months (February, May, August, and November) in 2023.

Markov Chain models had the following structure:

- Importing necessary libraries,
- Defining the possible weather states and creating a dictionary that contains historical weather data for a specific season,
- Calculating values for transition matrix,
- Defining a function for generating weather forecasts,
- Generating forecasts for specific months.

Markov Chain models enhanced with Laplace Smoothing followed the same structure, with the only difference being the method of calculating the transition matrix. In these models, the transition matrix is calculated using the formula for Laplace Smoothing.

The quality of the models performances can be measured by calculating the models precision. *Precision* measures the proportion of correct predictions (true predictions) out of all predictions made by the model, and is calculated using the formula (8) [29].

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{Number of true predictions}}{\text{Total number of predictions}} \quad (8)$$

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

By running all of four Markov Chain based models, data is generated for each day of the year 2023. After collecting all the forecasts, data is merged and a new dataset is created.

TABLE I
PERFORMANCES OF MARKOV CHAIN MODELS

Performances of Markov Chain Models			
Month	Number of true predictions	Total number of predictions	Precision
January	19	31	61.29%
February	22	28	78.57%
March	17	31	54.84%
April	25	31	80.65%
May	7	31	22.58%
June	18	30	66.67%
July	31	31	100%
August	26	31	83.87%
September	29	30	96.67%
October	20	31	64.52%
November	11	30	36.67%
December	16	31	51.61%

Transition Matrix - Markov Chain model for winter data: Cold: [0.84, 0.16, 0.00] Moderate: [0.19, 0.80, 0.00] Warm: [0.00, 0.00, 0.00]
Transition Matrix - Markov Chain model for spring data: Cold: [0.79, 0.21, 0.00] Moderate: [0.10, 0.86, 0.04] Warm: [0.02, 0.18, 0.80]
Transition Matrix - Markov Chain model for summer data: Cold: [0.00, 0.00, 0.00] Moderate: [0.00, 0.83, 0.17] Warm: [0.00, 0.04, 0.96]
Transition Matrix - Markov Chain model for autumn data: Cold: [0.50, 0.31, 0.19] Moderate: [0.03, 0.93, 0.04] Warm: [0.00, 0.05, 0.95]

Fig. 2. Transition matrices for the Markov Chain models.

Transition Matrix - Markov Chain model enhanced with Laplace smoothing for winter data: Cold: [0.84, 0.16, 0.003] Moderate: [0.19, 0.80, 0.004] Warm: [0.33, 0.33, 0.333]
Transition Matrix - Markov Chain model enhanced with Laplace smoothing for spring data: Cold: [0.78, 0.21, 0.007] Moderate: [0.10, 0.86, 0.04] Warm: [0.03, 0.19, 0.78]
Transition Matrix - Markov Chain model enhanced with Laplace smoothing for summer data: Cold: [0.33, 0.33, 0.33] Moderate: [0.01, 0.81, 0.18] Warm: [0.002, 0.037, 0.96]
Transition Matrix - Markov Chain model for autumn data: Cold: [0.50, 0.31, 0.19] Moderate: [0.03, 0.93, 0.04] Warm: [0.00, 0.05, 0.95]

Fig. 3. Transition matrices for the Markov Chain models enhanced with Laplace Smoothing.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCES OF MARKOV CHAIN MODELS WITH LAPLACE SMOOTHING

Performances of Models with Laplace Smoothing			
Month	Number of true predictions	Total number of predictions	Precision
January	16	31	51.61%
February	13	28	46.43%
March	23	31	74.19%
April	16	30	53.33%
May	11	31	35.48%
June	28	30	93.33%
July	29	31	93.55%
August	17	31	54.84%
September	26	30	86.67%
October	15	31	48.39%
November	18	30	60%
December	10	31	32.26%

The models' precision for each month is calculated and presented in Table I. Having the data represented in this format makes it easier to perform analysis, evaluate models

performances, and assess reliability of predictions. The models made its best predictions for the months of July, September, and August, with precisions of 100%, 96.67%, and 83.87%, respectively, and its worst predictions for the months of May, November, and December, with precisions of 22.58%, 36.67%, and 51.61% respectively. The models reached an overall precision of of 66.50%.

Fig. 2. shows that in every transition matrix, there is at least one zero probability. The precision of models' enhanced with Laplace Smoothing for each month is calculated and presented in Table II. These models made its best predictions for the months of July, June and September, with precisions of 93.55%, 93.33%, and 86.67%, respectively, and its worst predictions for the months of December, May, and February, with precisions of 32.26%, 35.48%, and 46.43% respectively. The models reached an overall precision of 60.84%.

Markov Chain models enhanced with Laplace Smoothing bypassed the problem of zero probabilities in transition matrix, which is beneficial for making predictions that are under-represented in the historical data, as shown in the Fig. 3

Markov Chain models enhanced with Laplace Smoothing showed worse precision than basic Markov Chain models, even though they were expected to exceed the precision of the previous model. However, Markov Chain models enhanced with Laplace Smoothing demonstrated significantly improved precision during months of March, May, June, and November, when the Markov Chain models struggled to deliver consistent performance. Minimal precision for the Markov Chain models with Laplace Smoothing is 32.26%, while minimal precision for basic Markov Chain model is 22.58%.

IV. CONCLUSION

Markov Chains are a useful tool for creating simple models capable of forecasting mean temperatures. Although enhancing the Markov Chain models with Laplace Smoothing did not improve the overall model precision, it demonstrated outstanding prediction results in situations where the Markov Chain models encountered challenges, leading to better overall minimal precision of the model. The Markov Chain models enhanced with Laplace Smoothing were able to predict values of the mean temperatures that were in close approximate distance to the boundary values ($10^{\circ}C$, $20^{\circ}C$) separating two states. Weather forecasting and forecasting its parameters are complex processes influenced by various factors. The proposed models made predictions for all days of the year 2023 based on four initial states and fixed transition matrices, and demonstrate good overall performance.

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Impact of Annual Mean Temperature (BIO1) on Vineyard Yield in Montenegro

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Abstract—Viticulture in Montenegro is a cornerstone of its agricultural tradition and economy, renowned for producing high-quality wines from indigenous grape varieties, cultivated in its diverse microclimates and fertile soils. Climate change poses significant challenges to viticulture in Montenegro altering temperature and precipitation patterns which can affect grape quality, yield, and the suitability of traditional growing regions for key grape varieties. This study focuses on examining the relationship between annual mean temperature (BIO1) and vineyard yield, a critical factor for the country’s wine production. Historical climate data from four weather stations Podgorica, Cetinje, Bar and Ulcinj and yield per vine data provided by MONSTAT (Statistical Office of Montenegro) are analyzed to assess the impact of BIO1 on vineyard productivity. Using statistical methods, the analysis quantifies the effect of temperature on yield trends. Historical observations form the basis for predictive models which project vineyard yields for future period (2023–2042) by using different statistical and machine learning techniques.

Index Terms—annual mean temperature, bioclimatic index, climate change, grape yield, viticulture.

I. INTRODUCTION

Viticulture holds significant economic and cultural importance in Montenegro, a country known for its rich tradition of wine production. The central and southern parts of Montenegro, including regions such as Podgorica, Ulcinj, and the surrounding areas, are extensively covered in vineyards due to their favorable climatic and geographic conditions. These areas contribute heavily to the country’s grape production, wine yield, and overall agricultural output. However, the impacts of climate change are increasingly evident, posing challenges to this vital sector.

Climate change is characterized by rising temperatures, shifts in precipitation patterns, and increased frequency of extreme weather events, all of which directly impact viticulture. Bioclimatic indices, such as BIO1 (mean annual temperature), BIO12 (annual precipitation) and others serve as critical metrics to assess the interaction between climate and viticulture. These indices influence various aspects of grapevine growth, including phenological phases (e.g., bud break, flowering, and ripening), yield per vine, and ultimately the quality and quantity of wine produced. As temperatures rise, grapevines may face accelerated growth cycles, leading to potential mismatches between vine development and optimal climatic conditions. Furthermore, extreme heat and reduced

water availability can negatively impact grape yield and compromise wine quality.

Recent observations indicate that grape yield in Montenegro has been decreasing, particularly in the past decade, raising concerns about the sustainability of viticulture in the region. Understanding and projecting the effects of climate change on vineyards is essential for developing adaptive strategies to mitigate these impacts.

This study aims to address this issue by focusing on two objectives: (1) analyzing historical data to investigate the correlation between annual mean temperature (BIO1) and grape yield and (2) projecting future trends in BIO1 and yield using advanced statistical and machine learning techniques. By combining historical analysis with future projections, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how climate change may shape the future of viticulture in Montenegro, guiding stakeholders toward sustainable adaptation strategies.

II. DATA SETS AND HISTORIC ANALYSIS

A. Grape yield analysis

Yield data was obtained from the yearly statistical books published by MONSTAT (Statistical Office of Montenegro). This data represents the yield per vine in kilograms and is available for the historical period 2001–2022. Analysis of the yield trend reveals a noticeable decrease over time, particularly from 2016 onwards, when the annual yield consistently falls below the calculated mean value for the entire period. The average yield over the 2001–2022 period is 2.36 kg per vine, highlighting the challenges faced by viticulture in recent years. This decline may be attributed to climatic changes, such as rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns, as well as other environmental or management factors. Understanding these trends is critical for developing adaptive strategies to sustain grape production in Montenegro. Bar chart of historic annual yield per vine data is represented in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Bar chart Yield historical data

B. BIO1 Analysis

In this study data from four weather stations in Montenegro-Podgorica, Ulcinj, Berane, and Cetinje were utilized with available historical period from 1962 to 2022. These stations provide average monthly temperature data, which were aggregated to calculate the mean annual temperature for Montenegro. This approach is suitable for the study as the majority of Montenegro’s vineyards are concentrated in the central and southern regions, where these weather stations predominantly capture climatic conditions. The analysis focuses on the last 50 years (1972–2022) to assess trends in mean annual temperature. The annual mean temperature, also referred to as BIO1, is a bioclimatic index calculated annually reflecting long-term climatic patterns.

The results indicate a clear warming trend, with mean annual temperatures consistently increasing over time. Notably, since 1999, the annual mean temperature has surpassed the 50-year average of 10.25°C, underscoring the accelerating impact of climate change on the region’s viticultural landscape. This bioclimatic index is of great importance as higher temperatures increase the risk of heat stress, reduce water availability, and alter the balance of sugars and acids in grapes, ultimately impacting both yield and wine quality. Bar chart of historic annual temperature and its mean value is represented in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Bar chart BIO1 historical data

C. Grape productivity and BIO1 correlation

The historical data of BIO1 (mean annual temperature) and yield per vine were analyzed to assess the correlation between these two variables. Since BIO1 has shown a notable increase over time while yield per vine has decreased, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) was employed to quantify the linear relationship between these datasets.

PCC, a statistical measure of linear correlation yielded a result of -0.56 indicating a moderate negative correlation. This negative value reflects that as BIO1 increases yield per vine decreases, as suggested. The observed negative correlation highlights the impact of rising temperatures on grape yield, likely due to increased heat stress and reduced water availability during critical growth periods. While the moderate strength of the correlation suggests that temperature is a significant factor, it also underscores the complex interplay of multiple environmental and management variables in determining grape productivity. Further research incorporating additional bioclimatic indices, such as precipitation (BIO12), extreme heat days and soil moisture, alongside agronomic practices, could provide a more holistic understanding of the drivers of yield variability. This would enable the development of targeted strategies to adapt grape cultivation to evolving climatic conditions. PCC is calculated as follows:

$$r = \frac{E(X - \mu_x)(Y - \mu_y)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y} \tag{1}$$

where σ_x and σ_y are standard deviations of X and Y, and μ_x and μ_y are mean values of X and Y. Representation of scatter diagram and Pearson correlation trendline is shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Scatterplot *Temperature vs Grape Yield*

III. FUTURE DATA AND OBSERVATIONS

A. Temperature projections

Future temperature projections were made using the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, based on the historical BIO1 data spanning 1962–2022. Given the limited historic dataset it is crucial to employ an appropriate machine learning technique and ARIMA is well-suited for such scenarios [4]. This model is particularly effective for near-future projections (up to 20 years) as it avoids overfitting and outperforms other common statistical methods. In this study a slightly modified version of ARIMA with added exogenous variables was employed to achieve more accurate results. The projections indicate a steady increase in temperature with values expected to reach 17°C by 2070. Focusing on the near future, over the next 20 years, the temperature is projected to rise up to 16.1°C, reflecting an increase of approximately 0.3°C. These findings highlight the ongoing warming trend and its potential implications for viticulture and other temperature-sensitive sectors in Montenegro. Long term projection of annual mean temperature is represented in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Projection of annual mean temperature

B. Yield projections

Yield projection for the next 20 years has been undertaken in accordance with the accepted guidelines for ARIMA’s suitability for near-term forecasts, specifically a 20-year timeframe. Two separate projections were made to ensure robustness and mitigate overfitting concerns, particularly given the limitations of the available historical dataset.

The first projection utilizes a linear regression model, which considers only historical yield and BIO1 (mean annual temperature) as inputs. The second projection employs the Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), a regularization-based machine learning method, which incorporates both historical data and future temperature projections. LASSO is particularly advantageous as it allows for the inclusion of additional predictive variables while avoiding overfitting by shrinking less relevant coefficients to zero. Both projections show certainty of decreasing trend, resulting in yield per vine 1.2 kg according to linear regression model, and 1.9 kg according to LASSO projection. These trends are represented in Figure 4. and Figure 5. for linear regression model and LASSO respectively.

Fig. 5. Linear regression projection of yield per vine

Fig. 6. Lasso projection of yield per vine

Furthermore, table with projected yearly results by linear regression and by LASSO can be found in Table I and Table II respectively.

Year	Yield per Vine (kg)
2023	2.11
2024	2.06
2025	2.00
2026	1.96
2027	1.91
2028	1.86
2029	1.81
2030	1.76
2031	1.71
2032	1.66
2033	1.61
2034	1.56
2035	1.51
2036	1.46
2037	1.41
2038	1.36
2039	1.31
2040	1.26
2041	1.21
2042	1.16

TABLE I
PROJECTED YIELD PER VINE BY LINEAR REGRESSION

Year	Yield per Vine (kg)
2023	2.23
2024	2.21
2025	2.20
2026	2.18
2027	2.16
2028	2.14
2029	2.13
2030	2.11
2031	2.09
2032	2.08
2033	2.06
2034	2.04
2035	2.03
2036	2.01
2037	1.99
2038	1.98
2039	1.96
2040	1.94
2041	1.93
2042	1.91

TABLE II
PROJECTED YIELD PER VINE BY LASSO

IV. CONCLUSION

Climate change has a profound impact on viticulture influencing grapevine growth, yield, and wine quality through changes in temperature, precipitation, and extreme weather events. This study demonstrates that even a single aspect of climate change such as rising mean annual temperatures (BIO1) is projected to significantly decrease grape yield over the next 20 years. The findings highlight the urgent need for proactive measures in viticulture to mitigate and adapt to these changes. Incorporating strategies such as climate-resilient grape varieties, improved water management and optimized vineyard practices is essential to sustain grape production and ensure the long-term viability of the viticulture sector in Montenegro.

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Relationships between climate variability and grapevine phenology

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Abstract— This research examines the relationship between climate change and the phenological stages of grapevine development. The significance of phenology has been presented, along with the scales for monitoring phenological stages. The main focus is on climate change and its impact on grapevine growth. The research also presents sensors used in vineyards to monitor specific climatic factors. The main part of this study involves monitoring the phenological stages in the Čemovsko polje vineyard. The phenological stages of the vranac clone were followed and monitored in 2023 and 2024. The results obtained indicate the impact of climate change, which has led to a shift in these stages by almost a month earlier in 2024.

Keywords—Grapevine, climate change, phenological stages, monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

Wine production today is a very popular activity in many countries around the world. Wine has been produced since ancient times, as it was believed to have a positive effect on health and to provide a unique pleasure. In the past, it was a drink available only to certain people, whereas today there are different categories of wine accessible to everyone. Both globally and in Montenegro, this industry is on the rise, as people have recognized the profitability it offers. No two wines can be said to be the same, as each one is distinguished by its unique characteristics, particularly its different taste and aroma notes. The special characteristics of wine stem from the region where the grapes are grown and the climate conditions, as well as the factors and conditions during the aging process.

To produce wine, the first essential step is to grow the grapes. Cultivating grapevines and producing grapes is a very complex process in wine production. The quality, characteristics, and quantity of wine produced directly depend on the grapes, which is closely linked to phenology. Phenology encompasses all stages of grapevine development as well as the factors that influence its growth. Phenology is not limited to grapevines alone; it applies to all plant species, and it is of great importance to producers. By monitoring phenology using specific scales, producers can determine the timing of these developmental stages and track the impact of various factors on plant growth. Depending on climatic factors, plant development can vary not only between

different countries but also within the same region, and it is constantly subject to change. Thanks to this field of study, producers gain a better understanding of these changes and can adapt their care practices to better align with climatic factors, ultimately improving their production.

The greatest impact on phenology is primarily caused by climate change, especially when these are sudden changes that lead to plant shock, such as heavy rainfall, high or low temperatures, wind and frosts. Such parameters result in a decrease in both the quality and yield of grapes, while also affecting factors like pH value, sugar content, and alcohol levels. Today, there is an increasing focus on studying this issue through the use of various models in vineyards, so that corrective measures can be applied based on the findings of these data.

II. PHENOLOGY

The term "phenology" refers to the field that deals with describing the growth and development of a plant species by linking two concepts: meteorology and ecology. For a plant to develop, the first factors that influence it are external conditions, specifically the climatic conditions occurring during that period. High temperatures, rain, wind, frosts—any of these phenomena can affect the plant and its development. Therefore, it can be said that these two fields are directly dependent on each other. [9]

Due to significant uncertainties and the increasing frequency of climate change, there has been a growing focus on conducting both research and experiments to obtain more accurate data and establish potential correlations between these areas. For this reason, many scientists developed specific scales to describe phenology. However, the large number of established scales often led to confusion, misalignment, and the inability to analyze the results. In order to create uniformity, a team was formed to develop a new scale based on existing ones, which relates to the development of many plants and is called the **BBCH** scale. [3]

Scales for monitoring phenological stages

The name "BBCH" is an abbreviation for the institutions coordinating this scale: the Federal Biological Institute, the Federal Variety Institute, and the Industry Association Agrar. When it comes to grapevines, many scientists worked on establishing a scale to explain their growth and development. Particularly important was Baggiolini, who in 1952 described specific phenological stages to obtain precise data on their occurrence, so that agro-technical measures could be applied accordingly. Baggiolini developed a scale consisting of ten stages, which he labeled with letters from A to I. These stages covered the period from the dormancy of the grapevine during the winter to the stage when berry development occurs. [3]

However, as the importance of data collection and analysis grew, it became necessary to create a scale that is numerically labeled in order to facilitate the analysis of the obtained data. Consequently, such a scale was developed in 1977 under the name EL scale, based on its founders Eichhorn and Lorenz. This scale provides a much more comprehensive and detailed description of phenological stages, dividing them into 24 stages with numerical labels from 00 to 47. Due to the larger number of stages, it describes the period from the start of grapevine vegetation to the moment when the leaves fall, marking the end of one phenological year. [3]

Even this method of describing phenological stages was not used for long, as there was an increasing push towards creating a new scale whose data would be coded and easier to process. However, it can be said that this scale was developed as a modified version of the existing ones. This led to the creation of the BBCH scale, which divides the phenological stages into two categories: the main stages of development (macro-stages) and those that take much less time (micro-stages). [3]

Figure 1. BBCH stages [12]

The goal of developing a scale to mark phenological stages is to determine the timing of their occurrence, primarily for the protection of grapevines. It is considered that the

grapevine is a sensitive plant that is attacked by many pests as well as diseases. For this reason, grape growers strive for optimal protection of the plant to ensure both high yields and good quality. In addition to applying chemical products as part of plant protection, they also use other biological methods, which are closely related to timing. Some methods must be applied before or during specific phenological stages to be effective. Therefore, it can be concluded that many tasks in the vineyard require knowledge of the plant's life cycle and development. These facts explain why so much attention has been given to the creation of a scale that most accurately represents these stages and the time required for their occurrence. [3]

III. CLIMATE CHANGE

Climate is defined as a combination of various meteorological factors, influenced by elements such as atmospheric radiation, altitude, relief, solar radiation, soil composition, human impact, air and ocean currents, vegetation cover, proximity to the sea, and many other phenomena. It is believed that the climatic composition includes the hydrosphere, biosphere, atmosphere, and cryosphere. The current state of specific meteorological factors is reflected in daily weather patterns. These factors include temperature, snow cover, wind direction and speed, evaporation, pressure, humidity, cloudiness, and precipitation. [2]

By monitoring these factors over a longer period, the climate of a region is determined. These factors are measured using stations located both on land and at sea, and today, satellite technology plays a significant role in gathering data. Meteorological measurements cover not only the Earth's surface but also multiple atmospheric layers to provide the most accurate representation of current conditions. Based on the measurement results, the type of climate is determined—whether it is Mediterranean, tropical, mountain, oceanic, Arctic, or desert climate. In addition to measuring these factors, numerical models and theoretical knowledge of the field also play a crucial role in defining climate. [2]

What is important to emphasize is that climate is not always constant; it can change over time. However, it is not easy to determine whether these changes are simply short-term variations in climate due to atmospheric fluctuations or whether they represent long-term climate change. For a change to be considered a climate change, it must involve a significant alteration in climatic composition and elements, and it must persist for an extended period. Climate change can be caused by both human activities and natural factors. Natural factors that influence climate change include changes in the Earth's orbit, volcanic eruptions, and variations in solar radiation. However, human-induced climate changes are also very impactful and frequent, and they include factors such as the consumption of fossil fuels, agriculture, deforestation, large-scale land use, and transportation. All these activities lead to an increase in the concentration of gases in the atmosphere, resulting in global warming through the greenhouse effect. Furthermore, human actions also contribute to changes in the ozone layer. In conclusion,

climate is a dynamic system influenced by a range of natural and anthropogenic factors, and its ongoing changes whether gradual or sudden pose a significant challenge for both the environment and society. [2]

The primary cause of climate change is undoubtedly atmospheric pollution, which has resulted from the increased concentration of gases that have led to a rise in greenhouse gas emissions. In addition to the natural occurrence of volcanic eruptions, this phenomenon is also triggered by gases such as methane, carbon monoxide, and carbon dioxide, as well as evaporation from the oceans. Apart from the natural factors mentioned earlier, human activity is now considered the main driver of these changes. [4]

The increased human impact has been recognized since the 20th century, although it is believed to have started even earlier, particularly with the Industrial Revolution. In addition to carbon dioxide, which is often a natural gas, human activity has also led to the release of other gases such as chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and nitrogen oxides. Other human activities that contribute to climate change include mining, cement production, rice farming, the use of artificial fuels, and livestock farming. These activities result in the emission of the aforementioned gases. With the continuous growth of the global population and the development of numerous industries, the human impact on the climate is also increasing, leading to long-term consequences for the environment and society. [4]

Impact of climate change on phenology

It is considered that shifts in phenological stages are the largest indicators of climate change. Research has shown that the increase in temperature over the past 40 years has led to a shift in phenological stages by 4-6 days. A large number of studies have been conducted, both on different varieties and on numerous species and clones, especially those believed to have had little variation in this regard. [5]

Considering the different characteristics of plants and their genetics, it can be said that climate change will not have the same impact on all of them. This is reflected in the fact that some plant species are more sensitive, while others are more resistant, and thus the shift in phenological stages due to climate change will not be the same for all species. Some researchers argue that this poses a problem, as it becomes difficult to determine the true effect of climate conditions on plants. On the other hand, some believe that there is a positive side to this variability and that the differences between plant species can be effectively utilized, using existing predictions for suitable locations. Through such studies, the resistance of plants could be uncovered, and based on that, it would be possible to determine where to plant certain species to achieve high yields. [5]

A large number of studies have been conducted on grapevines, with climate change being a major driving factor behind them. Two hundred years ago, grape harvests occurred very late, even in October and November, due to the eruption of a volcano. The year 1816 was coined the "Year Without a Summer" because, in addition to the extremely late harvest, many crops failed altogether. Today, due to

increasing climate change and global warming, grape harvests are occurring earlier. This demonstrates the significant impact that climate conditions have on grapevine phenology and the relationship between these factors. [5]

However, it is important to note that climate is not the only factor influencing the grapevine's life cycle. While the climatic impact on grapevines has been well-documented, studies have also shown that the same grape varieties, under identical climatic conditions, can react differently, indicating the importance of genetic differences between varieties. Certain intermediate stages, such as budburst, flower development, and berry development, can vary in timing by 3 to 6 weeks depending on the variety, regardless of other factors. [5]

It is a fact that grapevines thrive in moderate climatic conditions, not too hot and not too cold or frosty. Like many other plant species, grapevines have different varietal types, and thanks to this diversity, vineyard owners can choose the varieties best suited to the location and climate of a particular region. Through numerous studies, it has been concluded that varieties such as Mourvèdre and Furmint, which are late-ripening varieties, thrive in warmer climates. In contrast, varieties like Pinot Noir and Riesling succeed in cooler regions and mature earlier. The existence of varieties with different characteristics is what makes viticulture successful in many regions. [5]

Due to the increasing effects of climate change, there is ongoing research into suitable locations for establishing vineyards that will ensure both good quality and yield, while also demonstrating resilience to climatic factors. As the climate changes, the locations for viticulture are shifting, with a growing focus on northern regions for grape growing. However, a positive aspect is that even existing vineyards can continue to thrive with proper knowledge of the industry, the use of adaptable grape varieties, and the application of appropriate agronomic practices. [5]

Figure 2. The impact of climatic factors on grape [13]

The key factor affecting grapevines is primarily temperature, with rising temperatures leading to shifts in phenological phases and earlier grape ripening. Climate

change has also resulted in changes to the chemical composition of grapes, which has led to an increase in sugar levels and a decrease in acidity, thereby raising the pH value. Another noticeable effect of higher temperatures is the occurrence of drought and water shortages for vineyard irrigation, which later impacts grape yield and reduces its quality. However, some researchers believe that yields often decrease due to the increasing presence of weeds in vineyards, as these weeds are thought to deplete the nitrogen in the soil, which is essential for the growth of grapevines. [1]

It is clear that the impact of climatic factors on grapevines is being increasingly observed worldwide, with rising CO₂ concentrations and drought periods caused by heatwaves. All of these factors contribute to plant stress, resulting in lower-quality grapes due to biochemical changes. For these reasons, there is a growing trend to relocate vineyards to areas with a more moderate climate and higher altitudes, where milder temperatures will slow down ripening and produce higher-quality grapes. At the same time, increased UV-B radiation will lead to a higher synthesis of flavonoids and anthocyanins in the grapevine, which contribute to the characteristic color and special aroma of the grapes. Additionally, increased thermal amplitudes will help achieve the desired sugar concentration, resulting in an excellent balance of polyphenols, which are crucial for the quality of the grapes. [7]

Temperature throughout the entire growing season are very important for grapevines, as they require different temperature variations depending on the period of the year. During the winter months, research has shown that grapevines can withstand relatively low temperatures ranging from -5°C to -20°C. However, this tolerance varies depending on the grapevine variety, as not all varieties are equally resistant. If temperatures fall below these thresholds, it can lead to cell rupture and a reduction in enzymatic activity due to the disruption of membrane function. In spring, it is crucial to have moderate temperatures, as this is when the plant begins its vegetative growth. [7]

If temperatures drop too low or late frosts occur, they will negatively affect the plant. When these frosts happen near the end of the maturation phase, the situation becomes even worse, often leading to weight loss in the fruit, the development of diseases, or fruit splitting. Unlike these periods, during the summer months, high temperatures are also undesirable, as they can cause the vine to "shut down," reducing anthocyanin production, which will result in poor color development in the grapes. [7]

Wind often plays a beneficial role in vineyards by reducing humidity and preventing fungal and other diseases. However, strong winds can break young grapevines and damage them, which leads to delays in the phenological development of the vines. Additionally, if the winds are intense during the ripening phase, they can dry out the fruit, thus reducing the quality of the grapes. [7]

Relative humidity is a very important factor, as it is often closely associated with the development of diseases.

Humidity is highest in the morning hours and often persists in sheltered areas, promoting the growth of fungi. When temperatures are high, humidity is low. However, when temperatures are low, humidity is more present, which leads to a reduction in the vine's metabolism, fruit loss, leaf drop, or other damage. [7]

For proper grapevine development, a certain level of humidity is required, and it is best provided through irrigation. However, while this is beneficial and necessary, it can also be problematic during certain stages, particularly when there are extreme rainfall events that increase the likelihood of disease development. Excess rainfall can also dilute the berries and slow down important growth phases, such as flowering. In addition to the aforementioned climatic factors, extreme weather events like hailstorms or strong winds may occur. The consequences of such conditions can include a reduction in berry volume, oxidation, lower quality and yield, and premature fermentation. In conclusion, climatic factors are essential for the development of grapevines and other plants, but they must be within moderate values that support growth. Extreme weather events can lead to negative effects that hinder development and diminish the quality and yield of the grapes. [7]

Vineyard Čemovsko polje

The company 13. Jul Plantaže manages one of the largest vineyards in Europe, covering an area of 2,300 hectares and with 11.5 million vine stocks. This vineyard is not only a major economic asset but also a tourist attraction, known for its beauty and the wealth it generates. However, despite all its advantages, the vineyard located in the southern part of Montenegro faces significant challenges due to specific climatic conditions. [11]

The growing cycle of the vineyard begins in the winter. The skilled vineyard workers at 13. Jul Plantaže, thanks to their long-standing experience and expertise, work diligently to prepare the vines for the coming season. Tasks such as determining the height of the vine stocks, pruning, and aerating the vines are essential to ensure a healthy and abundant harvest. During this time, the work in the vineyards becomes a true challenge, considering the extremely hot summers in Podgorica, which often exceed tolerable temperatures for humans, and even more so for the vines.

The phenological stages of the vines—from bud break to grape ripening—are closely monitored. Vineyard workers, due to their long practice, become highly adept at recognizing even the smallest changes in the growth stages of the vines. Because of this intensive phenology monitoring, the company not only ensures optimal conditions for vine growth but also prepares for changes brought on by climate-related challenges.

As climate change becomes more pronounced, 13. Jul Plantaže is facing shifts in phenological stages that are driven by the rise in global temperatures. These changes affect grape quality, as the conditions for grape development are subject to significant fluctuations. For example, during the summer

months in Podgorica, extremely high temperatures and frequent droughts can lead to the dehydration of grape juice, resulting in changes in the chemical composition of the grapes. Such grapes become dry, overly sweet, and difficult to process during wine production, leading to a more complicated production process, machine malfunctions, and ultimately, lower quantities of wine of poorer quality.

For 13. Jul Plantaže's vineyard workers, the key to maintaining production quality lies in the application of adaptive agronomic practices and continuous monitoring of the vine's phenological stages. In this battle against unfavorable climatic factors, the vineyard workers rely not only on traditional knowledge and techniques but also on modern methods of grape analysis. Through periodic chemical composition analyses of the grapes, they are able to track changes and react in a timely manner to minimize negative effects on wine quality.

Despite the challenges posed by climate change, 13. Jul Plantaže continues to grow, investing in research and development to find effective ways to mitigate the negative impacts on production. Given the specificity and richness of their production, the key to success remains the synergy between the knowledge of the vineyard workers, the application of modern technologies, and adaptive measures that allow the vines to continue yielding high quantities and quality fruit, even in increasingly difficult climatic conditions.

IV. PHENOLOGY STAGES OF VRANAC CLON

This company has been a partner in many projects, one of which was the DEMETER project, whose goal was the use of advanced information and communication technologies to create safe, sustainable, and innovative ecosystems. Both Plantaže and many other companies and countries are striving to establish more precise viticulture and fruit cultivation practices, all aimed at better monitoring plant development. In addition to grapevines, Plantaže also cultivates olives, peaches, and pomegranates, and, as such, they have made significant efforts in research and the implementation of modern technologies to ensure that their crops are of the highest quality and that yields are optimized. [11]

Through this project, they have installed sensors that collect data both on the plants themselves and on the soil. By obtaining this data, they primarily take preventive actions, especially to protect plants from pests, while also evaluating the efficiency of their operations and potentially adjusting their practices if they notice any suboptimal results. [11]

Through years of experience, this company has recognized the great danger posed by climate change, which is also a challenge for Montenegro. It is well known that grapevines are particularly sensitive to changes in climatic factors, which ultimately leads to poor outcomes in vineyards. To mitigate or adapt to these changes, they have installed a meteorological station equipped with sensors. These sensors monitor numerous climatic factors, such as solar radiation, daily evapotranspiration, wind speed, air temperature and

humidity, photosynthetic activity, precipitation levels, and leaf moisture. Data readings are conducted via a mobile app, through which vineyard managers receive real-time information about the conditions in the vineyard. Based on this data, they can take appropriate actions to reduce the impact of climate change on their crops. [11]

Figure 3. Sensors in vineyard Ćemovsko polje [11]

This company cultivates a number of grape varieties, but the most significant by far is Vranac. As a result, their vineyard managers have tracked the development of the Vranac clone for two consecutive years. Monitoring of phenological stages begins in April and typically ends in September, which is directly dependent on the climatic factors during that season. Just like last year, this year we also faced significant heatwaves. While some may think that high temperatures are beneficial for plant growth, such extreme heat actually depletes the plant, and an even greater issue is that it leads to drought. In 2023, and especially during the summer months, temperatures reached as high as 40°C, while rainfall was scarce. [11]

TABLE I.

<i>Phenological stage</i>	<i>Date</i>
Inflorescences clearly visible	29.04.2023
Inflorescences swelling, flowers closely pressed together	06.05.2023
Beginning of flowering: 10% of flowerhoods fallen	20.05.2023
Full flowering: 50% of flowerhoods fallen	24.05.2023
Fruit set: young fruits begin to swell, remains of flowers lost	01.06.2023
Berries pea-sized, bunches hang	04.06.2023
Berries beginning to touch	13.06.2023
Beginning of ripening: berries begin to develop variety-specific colour	07.07.2023
Berries ripe for harvest	10.09.2023

This is also evident from the phenological stage dates presented for the Ćemovsko polje vineyard in Podgorica. The data show that the buds were visible by the end of April last year, and it took around four months from that stage to harvest. This season, however, is considered even hotter and more extreme in terms of climate change, as evidenced by the shift in these stages, which occurred almost a month earlier. Bud break occurred at the beginning of April, while harvest began in August and was completed by mid-September. According to the data from last year, the harvest did not begin until September. [11]

TABLE II.

<i>Phenological stage</i>	<i>Date</i>
Inflorescences clearly visible	05.04.2024
Inflorescences swelling, flowers closely pressed together	11.04.2024
Beginning of flowering: 10% of flowerhoods fallen	07.05.2024
Full flowering: 50% of flowerhoods fallen	13.05.2024
Fruit set: young fruits begin to swell, remains of flowers lost	17.05.2024
Berries pea-sized, bunches hang	23.05.2024
Berries beginning to touch	29.05.2024
Beginning of ripening: berries begin to develop variety-specific colour	21.06.2024
Berries ripe for harvest	18.08.2024

V. CONCLUSION

Agriculture is one of the most important sectors in Montenegro and a highly developed industry that provides a source of income for many people. Both animal and plant production are well-developed in Montenegro, and they are often interconnected. Many plant species are cultivated, with viticulture becoming increasingly popular, both worldwide and in Montenegro. However, despite Montenegro being a country rich in fertile land with excellent conditions for agricultural development, there are numerous factors that influence this sector. One undeniable fact is that the Mediterranean climate, which once prevailed, was ideal for the development of agricultural crops.

However, today, both the world and Montenegro are facing the challenges of climate change. Although many of us may not be fully aware of it, the climate is changing more rapidly, bringing harmful consequences for the entire planet. The changing climatic factors affect animals, such as bees, and we often hear that beekeeping is increasingly in decline. Bees are the most important pollinators of plants, and the decline of beekeeping would lead to the extinction of many plant species, which in turn would result in a lack of food for animals and, ultimately, for humans. It can be said that agricultural activities are deeply interconnected, and the extinction of agriculture would have very negative consequences for all of us.

We are increasingly witnessing warmer summers and milder winters, indicating climate change. While our summer season is on the rise due to more hot days and months, we observe the extinction of the winter season as there is less and less snow. We notice that winter months are increasingly moderate and warmer, unlike ten years ago.

Hot summer months are often accompanied by droughts, which are highly detrimental to plants. As our producers state,

these conditions have only led to negative consequences, and they have been forced to spray their plants with numerous chemicals just to be able to produce anything. They claim that in the last two years, they have spent more than they earned, all in the name of protecting their crops. Precipitation is becoming increasingly rare, and when it does occur, it is often excessive and extreme, leading to floods and damage to agricultural estates.

All of this indicates that climate change has become a serious problem that we are facing, and this issue is gaining increasing attention. Scientists are researching it more and more in an effort to find solutions, if not to eliminate it, at least to mitigate its effects and identify adaptation measures. Therefore, monitoring phenology through scales, the introduction of sensors, and other smart technologies in vineyards to track climatic factors is one response to climate change. Gathering this data helps in taking preventive actions and applying protective measures to combat the negative impacts of climate change. What is essential is certainly increasing awareness of this problem and conducting more research so that better solutions can be found to help protect both agriculture and the entire planet.

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Implementation of kaolin in vineyards as a measure of adaptation to climate change

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Abstract

Climate change poses one of the most pressing challenges of our time, with profound implications for agricultural practices worldwide. In viticulture, rising average temperatures, more intense heatwaves, and frequent extreme weather events significantly impact grapevine productivity, wine quality, and overall vineyard health. To mitigate the adverse effects of climate change, various adaptation measures are being developed and implemented. Among these, the use of kaolin, a natural mineral clay, has emerged as an innovative and sustainable strategy to protect grapevines from heat stress.

This study explores the potential of kaolin as a climate adaptation tool in viticulture, focusing on its role in reducing heat stress and ensuring sustainable vineyard management under increasingly challenging climatic conditions. Key findings highlight kaolin's ability to improve grapevine resilience to extreme weather while supporting the long-term sustainability of the viticulture sector.

Keywords: Climate change, kaolin, heat stress, adaptation

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate change represents one of the biggest problems for all agro-ecosystems. Heat stress and extreme weather conditions negatively affect every sector of agriculture. According to the assessment of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2014), the temperature of the Earth will increase by 1.8 to 4°C in this century (Georgeta Michaela Bucur, 2024), which will result in increased needs for irrigation in agriculture and significantly contribute to both the phenology of the vine and its physicochemical state. Viticulture is particularly threatened by the impact of climate change, since high temperatures lead to disturbances in grape phenology. Heat stress leads to earlier ripening, and high temperatures negatively affect the color of red grape varieties (Gabriele Valentini, 2022). The optimal temperatures for photosynthesis and sugar accumulation in berries range from 25 to 30°C, while the optimal temperatures for the accumulation of anthocyanins are 17 to 26°C. Due to climate change and an increase in temperature these parameters will be exceeded, which will result in a series of negative reactions and can expect an increase in sugar in the grapes and a pronounced degradation of the acidity in the wine, which will occur as a result of an increase in the pH value. This will result in the production of wines that are less suitable for aging, with a weaker color and altered aromatic composition. In order to

preserve the quality of wine, winegrowers use a number of measures to mitigate and adapt to climate change. Mitigation measures must be implemented in order to comply with the Paris Agreement, which set the goal of limiting global warming to 2°C, while adaptation measures would contribute to the establishment of a sustainable production system in a system that will inevitably be changed in the future due to the impact of climate change. One of the adaptation measures to climate change is implementation of the kaolin clay that is sprayed on the vines in order to reduce heat stress.

II. IMPLEMENTATION OF KAOLIN IN VITICULTURE

A. Principle and effects of kaolin application

Kaolin ($\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5(\text{OH})_4$) is a clay that has found application in many branches of industry such as construction, cosmetics, paper industry and pharmaceuticals. It has found a very wide application in agriculture. It is characterized by a white color, it is chemically inert, non-abrasive, non-toxic and easily soluble in water (which is the basis of its application in agriculture). Dissolved in water, it is applied to the surface of plants. The layer applied to the plant must meet certain requirements: it must be applied evenly, the mineral particle must have a diameter of less than 2 mm, and the applied layer must not interfere with gas exchange. The film of kaolin particles increases the reflection of excess UV and IR radiation, which reduces the risk of leaf damage from heat stress. In addition, the implementation of kaolin has also found application in pest control. The effects of kaolin are still not fully understood, but their effect certainly depends on the concentration of application, the plant species, the dimensions of the canopy or the surface on which it is applied, the environmental conditions and the duration of the treatment. Research has shown that kaolin under optimal hydration usually reduces stomatal conductance and the net rate of photosynthesis (Cátia Brito, 2019). Similarly, during re-watering, after a long drought episode (especially under low irradiance, in the rainy season) the recovery of gas exchange is delayed due to the kaolin film. Conversely, in water-limited environments, salinity, high temperature, high photosynthetic photon flux density, and high vapor pressure deficit have been found to have a positive effect on grapevines. Despite this, leaves sprayed with kaolin need a period of acclimatization, in order to manifest the positive effects. In summary, the advantages of implementing kaolin are manifested at high temperatures

when the vines cannot absorb all the radiation that arrives from the atmosphere (which will be more and more the case due to the increase in temperature of more sunny days), while on the other hand it can reduce the rate of photosynthesis when the environmental conditions limit photosynthesis (which is the case with cooler days).

Figure 1. An example of the implementation of a kaolin film in a vineyard in Syria

Source: (Costa, 2022, pag. 23)

The influence of kaolin application on leaf biochemistry has been much less studied, where the emphasis was on the composition of photosynthetic pigments. In principle, kaolin prevents the degradation of chlorophyll, reduces the ratio of chlorophyll a/chlorophyll b, and increases total chlorophyll (Cátia Brito, 2019). Furthermore, kaolin implementation has been shown to generally reduce oxidative damage in sprayed organs.

In rain-fed grapevines, a reduced amount of reactive oxygen species (ROS), lipid peroxidation and an increased amount of soluble proteins were found in the sprayed leaves and berries. The application of kaolin increases the antioxidant defense system of the grapevine, which is related to the increase of phenols, antioxidant capacity and activity of key enzymes of the ascorbate-glutathione cycle (Cátia Brito, 2019).

Despite all the advantages of using kaolin, the manifestation of positive effects cannot be expressed precisely quantitatively, since the result of the application varies depending on the variety, water status, management practices, phenology and edaphoclimatic conditions.

B. Results of kaolin implementation in vineyards

As a result of concerns about the potential damage that increased temperatures can cause to vineyards, the scientific community has conducted numerous experiments testing various adaptation measures to climate change. Experiments with the use of kaolin are inevitably classified there.

The results showed that the use of kaolin solution (5%w/v) reflects a relevant amount of photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) compared to vines not sprayed with kaolin, and that the reflection does not take place only in the range of UV and IR rays (Andreia Garrido, 2019). The same research indicated that kaolin has a better effect in reflecting UV compared to IR rays (Andreia Garrido, 2019). Figure 4a shows the transmittance spectrum of a kaolin suspension (5%w/v), while the comparison with unsprayed grapevines is shown in Figure 4b.

Figure 2. Transmittance (%) spectrum (a) of a kaolin suspension (5% w/v) and reflectance (%) spectra (b) of leaves with and without kaolin (control)

Source: (Andreia Garrido, 2019, pag. 7)

Further results of this research showed that the foliar application of kaolin can protect the berry exocarp from excess light at the stage when the grape's photosynthetic phenotype is still developing (Andreia Garrido, 2019).

It is clear that kaolin is a very suitable tool for increasing the reflection of the rays from the atmosphere, and thus reducing sunburns, and it has been proven that its change also affects the increase of phenolic compounds such as anthocyanins in wine by up to 20% (Gabriele Valentini, 2022). In addition to the increased amount of phenolic compounds, an increased content of tartaric acid, malic acid and total acidity, as well as a reduced alcohol content, were observed.

In a study conducted in Portugal where the impact of kaolin application on the Touriga-Franca and Touriga-Nacional varieties (Douro and Alentejo regions; year 2017 and 2018) was investigated, it was concluded that the positive effects of kaolin application were more pronounced in the first year, where an improvement was noticed intrinsic efficiency of water use by vines, net CO₂ assimilation rates (72% in Douro and 25% in Alentejo), and content of soluble sugars, while in the same period noticed a decrease in the accumulation of plant growth regulators, i.e. abscisic and salicylic acid in the ripening phase (Bernardo, 2021). In the Douro vineyard, treated leaves showed lower chlorophyll and carotenoid content during the 2017 summer season and reduced NPK at ripening, suggesting a long-term response to summer stress. Conversely, kaolin-treated vines from Alentejo vineyards showed a significant increase in chlorophyll content compared to untreated ones, while no changes were found in the Touriga-Franca variety, which could indicate a lower need for kaolin application in this variety (Bernardo, 2021). These data show us once again that the effect of applying kaolin as a means of adapting to climate

change depends primarily on the variety and climatic conditions.

C. Impact of kaolin implementation on pests

Apart from the fact that kaolin reflects rays from the atmosphere and thus reduces the temperature of the parts of the plant where kaolin has been applied, it is also an excellent tool for pest control. Due to its chemical composition and appearance, the kaolin film changes the properties of the plant that the pests are used to. The changed appearance, smell and taste of the sprayed parts of the plant will make it less attractive to pests, which will result in a reduced occurrence of pests in vineyards.

Although the studies dealing with the issue of pest control with the help of agents such as kaolin are not numerous, it has been shown that natural kaolin (2 applications of a concentration of 4 kg/l) can be a substitute for pyrethrins in organic vineyards, and can also be used as a pest control agent in conventional vineyards. In addition, it was shown that the application of kaolin (rate of 2%w/v 2 applications at an interval of 5-6 days) led to a significant reduction of the population of *E. vitis* leafhoppers (Costa, 2022).

III. CONCLUSION

Although the Mediterranean climate is extremely favorable for the cultivation of vines, due to climate change, an increase in temperature will inevitably follow, which causes heat stress to the vines. That is why it is necessary to apply some of the measures to mitigate the impact of heat stress. Adaptation measures are numerous and the application of kaolin is only one of them. This research paper looks at all the benefits and impacts of kaolin as a vine spray. Along with that, it shows the results obtained from individual vineyards in Europe. From the above, it can be concluded that the advantages of applying kaolin are numerous, but that winegrowers, when considering kaolin as a means of alleviating heat stress, must take into account the climate of their vineyard as well as the varieties grown in it. Research applications of kaolin are not numerous, but it is certain that it occupies a very important place in the future of agriculture since it provides the possibility of establishing sustainable production despite the increase in temperature that will follow due to climate change. In addition to adaptation measures, the agricultural sector, but also all other sectors, must also start applying mitigation measures in order to reduce the damage to a minimum in the future.

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Climate Data Downscaling with CHELSA: Workshop Insights and Future Applications

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Abstract—From October 28 - 30th, 2024, I attended a workshop titled “Practical Introduction to the CHELSA Modelling System for Climate Data Downscaling.” The workshop was led by Dr. Christoph Menz from the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK). We worked with the CHELSA algorithm to simulate past and future climate scenarios. This was my first experience using Linux and Bash programming, which we utilized to run various simulations. Additionally, we employed Python programming language and Panoply, a software tool for high-quality climate data visualization, allowing us to interpret results effectively. Gaining new skills and experiencing just a small part of what scientists encounter daily was profoundly enriching.

The workshop emphasized the versatility of CHELSA beyond vineyard management, showcasing its applicability across diverse fields affected by climate change, including agriculture, ecology, and urban planning. By providing high-resolution climate data, CHELSA enables more precise assessments of climate impacts on various ecosystems and human activities.

In this paper, I aim to provide an overview of the tools and methodologies employed during the workshop and discuss how CHELSA can be leveraged for future research initiatives. Furthermore, I hope to inspire more individuals to engage with climate modeling tools like CHELSA, fostering a deeper understanding of climate dynamics and their implications for sustainability.

Keywords—CHELSA modeling system, Climate data downscaling, Linux programming, Data visualization

I. INTRODUCTION

Like any model, climate models aim to create representations of real-life scenarios. While these models help us determine potential courses of action, they should not be taken for granted. This is particularly true for climate modeling, which provides valuable insights into the influence of climate on our world. The quality of the datasets we use directly impacts the accuracy of our models; therefore, there is a critical need for high-resolution climate datasets.

One promising solution for addressing the challenges of climate data is the CHELSA (Climatologies at High Resolution for the Earth's Land Surface Areas) modeling system. CHELSA facilitates the downscaling of global climate data, enabling researchers to generate high-resolution climate information that is essential for various applications, including agriculture, urban planning, and environmental management.

I attended a workshop titled “Practical Introduction to the CHELSA Modelling System for Climate Data Downscaling” from October 28 to 30, 2024. Led by Dr. Christoph Menz from the Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), the workshop aimed to equip participants with practical skills in utilizing CHELSA for simulating past and future climate scenarios. My motivation for attending this workshop stemmed from a desire to gain new experiences and work with tools I had never imagined using before. Additionally, it was an excellent opportunity to connect with a scientist who is actively addressing the pressing issue of climate change.

II. OVERVIEW OF CHELSA

CHELSA, which stands for Climatologies at High Resolution for the Earth's Land Surface Areas, is a high-resolution climate dataset that provides detailed temperature and precipitation information for global land surfaces. Developed and hosted by the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research (WSL), CHELSA is tailored to support ecological and environmental research by offering climate data at a resolution of approximately 1 km (30 arc seconds) [1].

A. Significance of CHELSA for climate modeling

CHELSA offers an unprecedented level of detail in climate data, allowing researchers to analyze climatic conditions with precision. This high resolution is particularly beneficial for studying localized ecological phenomena, as even small variations in climate can significantly impact local habitats and species distributions [2]. The dataset employs advanced downscaling methods derived from the ERA-Interim global reanalysis dataset, generating localized climate information that addresses challenges in regions with sparse meteorological station coverage [1].

B. Applications of CHELSA

CHELSA is widely utilized in various ecological studies, including:

- Species Distribution Modeling: The dataset aids in predicting how species may shift their ranges in response to changing climatic conditions, thereby improving conservation strategies [3].
- Water Balance Studies: Research in regions like Colombia has utilized CHELSA to enhance long-term water balance assessments, which are crucial for effective water resource management [4].

- Vegetation and Forest Dynamics: The data supports investigations into how climate influences forest composition and plant growth patterns over time [2].

The accuracy of CHELSA's precipitation predictions surpasses many other models, making it a reliable tool for researchers. Its ability to generate realistic climate patterns is essential for understanding ecological changes and informing effective management practices [1].

C. Future Climate Scenarios

In addition to historical data covering the period from 1979 to 2013, CHELSA is also applied in modeling future climate scenarios. This capability provides valuable insights into potential ecological impacts under various climate change scenarios [3].

In summary, CHELSA plays a vital role in enhancing our understanding of climate dynamics at regional scales. Its high-resolution data supports a wide range of ecological applications, making it an invaluable resource for researchers addressing pressing environmental challenges related to climate change and biodiversity conservation [1].

III. TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES

During the workshop, we employed a variety of tools, and in this section, I will discuss them in more detail. Although we didn't have the opportunity to explore all that CHELSA has to offer, we were able to cover the basics, which will serve as a foundation for our future work.

A. Linux and Terminal

During the workshop, we learned essential Linux commands and how to effectively use the terminal for various tasks. The terminal is a command-line interface that allows users to interact with the operating system through text commands, serving as a powerful tool for executing tasks quickly and efficiently [4].

We explored several fundamental commands crucial for navigating and managing files in Linux:

- ls: Lists files and directories in the current directory.
- cd: Changes the current directory.
- pwd: Displays the current working directory.
- mkdir: Creates a new directory.
- rm: Deletes files or directories.

Additionally, we discussed commands for managing files, including:

- cp: Copies files from one location to another.
- mv: Moves or renames files.

We used these commands to organize our work and activate Python libraries provided by the educator. Furthermore, we learned to open Jupyter Notebook via the terminal and run simulations, allowing us to apply our knowledge practically.

Using Linux and the terminal, along with scripting, can automate tasks such as data processing and analysis, which is crucial in climate research [5]. Commands like ls, cp, and mv enable researchers to efficiently organize and manipulate large

datasets common in climate studies [8]. The terminal also facilitates integration with programming languages such as Python and R, enabling complex analyses that combine multiple tools [9]. Mastering these commands ensures reproducibility in research workflows since scripts can be reused and shared among researchers [5]. Familiarity with terminal commands increases productivity by allowing researchers to perform tasks more quickly than using graphical user interfaces [6].

In summary, the skills we learned during the workshop empower us as potential researchers to manage climate data effectively, streamline workflows, and enhance overall productivity in environmental science.

B. Python for climate modeling

I was aware that Python is utilized across various fields, but I was surprised to discover its significance in climate data analysis, particularly due to its extensive libraries that facilitate data processing, visualization, and modeling. During the workshop, we used several key libraries, including Anaconda and Matplotlib, along with others like xarray and xclim for visualizing data through Jupyter Notebook.

Anaconda is a distribution of Python and R specifically designed for scientific computing. It simplifies package management and deployment, making it easier to install and manage libraries essential for climate data analysis [10].

Matplotlib is a widely-used plotting library in Python that enables users to create static, interactive, and animated visualizations. It is particularly useful for visualizing climate data trends and patterns [12].

xarray is a powerful library for working with multi-dimensional arrays, making it ideal for handling climate datasets that often include multiple dimensions such as time, latitude, and longitude. It allows for easy manipulation and analysis of large datasets [11].

xclim is an operational Python library designed for climate services. It provides tools for calculating climate indices and conducting statistical analyses on climate model outputs [13].

Python was applied to process CHELSA data and handle netCDF files through several steps:

- Loading Data

Using the xarray library, users can easily open netCDF files containing CHELSA data. For example:

```
import xarray as xr
ds
xr.open_dataset('path/to/chelsa_data.nc')
```

- Data Manipulation

Once the data is loaded as an xarray dataset, users can manipulate it using various functions provided by the library. This includes selecting specific time frames or geographical locations using methods like `.sel()` or `.isel()`, which help filter the dataset according to specific criteria [11].

- Calculating Climate Indices

With the `xclim` library, users can compute various climate indices from the loaded datasets. For instance:

```
import xclim

mean_temp =
xclim.atmos.tg_mean(ds.tas,
freq="MS")
```

This code calculates the monthly mean temperature from daily temperature data.

- Visualizing Data

After processing the data, users can visualize it using Matplotlib. For example:

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

ds.tas.plot()

plt.title('Temperature Data')

plt.show()
```

This simple plot command allows researchers to visualize temperature trends over time [12].

- Saving Processed Data

Finally, processed datasets can be saved back into netCDF format or other formats for further analysis or sharing with collaborators.

During our Jupyter Notebook session, we generated various outputs that demonstrated the analysis and visualization of CHELSA data. These outputs included graphical representations of temperature trends and calculated climate indices, which provided insights into regional climatic patterns.

I believe we have only scratched the surface of Python's capabilities during this workshop, and there is much more to explore. I have come to realize that Python is an incredibly powerful tool, particularly in its application to combat climate change. This revelation has been a significant discovery for me!

C. NetCDF Data Processing

NetCDF, which stands for Network Common Data Form, is a super useful format for storing and sharing scientific data, especially in climate and atmospheric sciences. It's really important for analyzing climate data because it can handle multidimensional datasets like a pro [17].

NetCDF files are self-describing, which means they come with their own metadata that explains what the data is all about. This is great because you don't have to dig through separate documents to figure things out [15].

Each NetCDF file usually has three main parts:

- Variables: This is where the actual data values live.
- Dimensions: These tell you how the variables are structured (like time, latitude, and longitude).

- Attributes: These provide extra info about the variables or dataset, such as units and descriptions.

NetCDF is really good at handling large datasets, which is perfect for complex climate models that track things like temperature, humidity, and wind speed across different places and times [16].

One of the greatest things about NetCDF is how it stores multidimensional arrays. This is super helpful for climate data, which often involves looking at both space and time. For example, you might have a dataset that shows daily rainfall across various locations over several years—all packed into a three-dimensional array where each axis represents longitude, latitude, and time [18]. This makes it way easier for researchers to analyze trends in climate patterns.

Plus, NetCDF files are efficient when it comes to storage. They can compress large amounts of data into smaller files compared to other formats like CSV. This happens because coordinates (like latitudes and longitudes) are saved just once instead of being repeated for every single data point [19].

During our workshop, we checked out one of the main tools for working with NetCDF datasets – Panoply. This tool is perfect for visualizing NetCDF files. It lets you create plots of geospatial data really easily, making it a favorite among climate scientists [14].

Panoply makes it so much easier to access and work with NetCDF data. It helped us visualize complex datasets and get meaningful insights into climate dynamics.

IV. APPLICATIONS OF CHELSA

CHELSA datasets have proven invaluable for biodiversity studies, particularly in modeling species distributions. The high-resolution climate data allows researchers to accurately assess the climatic conditions of specific ecosystems, which is essential for understanding habitat suitability [23]. For example, a study highlighted that using CHELSA data significantly improved the accuracy of species distribution models (SDMs) by providing better precipitation patterns compared to other datasets [3]. This improvement is crucial for predicting how species ranges may shift in response to climate change.

The CHELSA-W5E5 dataset, which offers daily meteorological data at high spatial resolution, is particularly useful for regional climate impact assessments. This dataset has been utilized to evaluate the effects of climate variability on agriculture and water resources [1]. One notable application involved assessing how changing precipitation patterns could impact crop yields in specific regions. Researchers used the CHELSA-W5E5 dataset to simulate potential agricultural outcomes under different climate scenarios, providing critical insights into future food security challenges.

CHELSA datasets also play a key role in informing environmental management decisions. For instance, they can guide conservation strategies by identifying areas most vulnerable to climate change impacts [22]. In practice, local governments have used CHELSA data to prioritize habitat restoration efforts based on projected climatic changes. The ability to visualize high-resolution climate data helps

policymakers understand potential risks and develop targeted interventions that can mitigate adverse effects on ecosystems.

In summary, while our workshop primarily discussed the potential uses of CHELSA datasets, numerous studies illustrate their practical applications in biodiversity research, regional climate impact assessments, and environmental management decision-making. The high-resolution data provided by CHELSA enables researchers and policymakers to make informed decisions that address the challenges posed by climate change.

V. CHALLENGES AND LESSONS LEARNED

During our workshop, we faced several challenges while working with CHELSA datasets, particularly regarding the limitations of our internet connection and the data preparation process. Here's a reflection on these challenges and how they shaped our experience.

A. Challenges faced

- Internet Connectivity Issues

One of the main obstacles was our unreliable internet connection, which prevented us from utilizing cloud computing resources. We had initially considered using cloud platforms to handle the large datasets and run simulations more efficiently, but the poor connectivity made this option impractical. As a result, we had to rely on local processing capabilities.

- Limited Dataset Scope

Additionally, we focused exclusively on data for Montenegro, which had been pre-prepared by our instructor. While this allowed us to work with a manageable dataset, it also limited our exploration of the broader capabilities of CHELSA datasets. We missed out on opportunities to analyze diverse geographic areas or to compare different climate scenarios.

- Computational Requirements

The computational demands for downscaling simulations were another significant challenge. Many participants found that their laptops were not powerful enough to complete the simulations within the workshop time frame. This issue led to delays and some frustration as we tried to work through the analyses.

- Learning Curve with Tools

Finally, many attendees, including myself, were new to using Linux and Python as foundational tools for data analysis. The learning curve was steep, and navigating the command line was initially daunting for those unfamiliar with it.

B. Strategies implemented

To tackle these challenges, we adopted several strategies:

- Focused Learning

Given that we were limited to using only the Montenegro dataset, we concentrated on maximizing our understanding of how to manipulate and analyze this specific data effectively. This focus allowed us to dive deeper into the nuances of the CHELSA dataset and its implications for local climate studies.

- Collaborative Problem-Solving

Participants shared tips and tricks for optimizing their laptop performance and managing resources effectively. We collaborated on troubleshooting issues related to data processing, which fostered a supportive learning environment.

- Hands-On Practice

The workshop emphasized hands-on practice with Python and Linux commands. Despite the initial learning curve, this approach helped participants gradually become more comfortable with these tools.

C. Skills gained

Despite these challenges, we emerged from the workshop with valuable skills:

- Data Analysis Proficiency

We gained practical experience in handling climate datasets, specifically focusing on how to analyze climate variables relevant to Montenegro's ecological context.

- Technical Skills in Python and Linux

Many attendees improved their technical literacy by learning essential commands in Python and Linux. This foundational knowledge will be beneficial for future data analysis projects.

- Adaptability

The experience taught us how to adapt our plans based on available resources and constraints. We learned to make the most out of limited datasets while still gaining meaningful insights.

In summary, while our workshop presented several challenges—such as internet connectivity issues, limited dataset scope, computational requirements, and a steep learning curve—these obstacles ultimately enhanced our learning experience. By addressing these challenges collaboratively and strategically, we not only overcame immediate hurdles but also gained essential skills that will benefit our future work in climate science and data analysis.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The CHELSA workshop provided an invaluable opportunity to explore the capabilities of high-resolution climate data modeling while also equipping participants with practical skills in Linux, Python, and data visualization tools like Panoply. Through hands-on practice and collaborative learning, we gained insights into the significant role of CHELSA in addressing climate-related challenges in fields ranging from biodiversity research to urban planning. The workshop underscored the importance of high-resolution datasets for precise climate impact assessments and demonstrated how tools like CHELSA can facilitate targeted solutions for ecological and societal adaptation to climate change.

However, challenges such as computational limitations, dataset constraints, and a steep learning curve emphasized the need for further skill development and resource optimization. Overcoming these challenges enhanced our adaptability and technical proficiency, preparing us for more advanced applications in the future.

A. Potential future directions involving CHELSA

- Expanding Geographic Scope

Future endeavors should explore the application of CHELSA datasets across diverse regions and climate scenarios, enabling a broader understanding of global climate dynamics and their localized effects.

- **Advancing Computational Resources:**

Integrating cloud computing platforms and high-performance computing resources will enable more efficient processing of large datasets, overcoming hardware limitations encountered during the workshop.

- **Capacity Building**

To address the learning curve, targeted training programs focusing on foundational Linux and Python skills should be developed. These could include online modules or follow-up workshops to support continuous learning.

- **Multidisciplinary Applications:**

CHELSA's versatility can be leveraged in interdisciplinary research, such as combining climate data with socioeconomic variables to inform policies on sustainable development, urban resilience, and disaster risk reduction.

- **Community Engagement**

Encouraging collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and local stakeholders will amplify the impact of CHELSA-driven insights, ensuring they translate into actionable strategies.

B. Future directions for myself

The CHELSA workshop was not just an academic endeavor; it was an exploration of an intricate world within a computer simulation—a world that I approached with the curiosity of a child discovering something new. This journey allowed me to engage with advanced tools and methodologies that expanded my understanding of climate data downscaling and its broader implications. It marked a significant step in my academic and professional growth, and I am optimistic that this is just the beginning of my research journey.

Wherever my path leads, I am committed to carrying forward the knowledge I have gained and building upon it. This first paper represents not only a milestone but also a promise to continue exploring, learning, and contributing to the understanding of climate dynamics. I am hopeful it will be the first of many efforts to bridge scientific exploration and practical application, ultimately supporting a more sustainable future.

In moving forward, I envision delving deeper into multidisciplinary applications of tools like CHELSA, leveraging advanced computational resources, and fostering collaboration within diverse research communities. With each step, I aim to further unravel the complexities of our world and life as we know it, driven by the same sense of wonder and curiosity that first inspired me to embark on this journey.

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The Impact of Climate Change on Agriculture and the Application of Mathematical Models to Predict Agricultural Yields

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Abstract— The impact of climate change on agriculture is an increasingly urgent global issue that directly affects crop yields, agricultural productivity, and food security. Climate change has introduced unpredictable weather patterns, such as extreme temperatures, irregular rainfall, droughts, and floods, all of which pose significant risks to crop production and agricultural systems. Consequently, it is crucial to develop models that can predict agricultural outcomes under varying climate conditions to help mitigate the risks associated with these changes. Mathematical models play a vital role in understanding and predicting crop yields in the context of climate change. These models integrate climate data, such as temperature, precipitation, and soil conditions, to simulate potential agricultural outcomes. By considering both short-term and long-term climate scenarios, mathematical models provide valuable insights into how changing weather patterns affect crop productivity. In this regard, they help farmers and agricultural stakeholders make informed decisions about crop management practices, irrigation schedules, and resource allocation. The primary challenge of modeling crop yields under climate change is the uncertainty and variability inherent in both climate data and agricultural systems. Stochastic models, which account for the randomness and unpredictability of weather patterns, are essential for providing more accurate predictions. These models simulate various possible future scenarios, helping to assess the potential risks of reduced crop yields and inform the development of adaptive strategies to address these uncertainties. Moreover, the rise of data-driven models, powered by advances in remote sensing, satellite imagery, and real-time environmental monitoring, has greatly improved the accuracy of yield predictions. These models benefit from a wealth of data on climate conditions, soil health, and crop performance, allowing for more precise and localized predictions. As a result, farmers can better adapt their practices to changing climatic conditions, optimize resource usage, and improve overall agricultural productivity. This paper explores the use of mathematical modeling to predict crop yields in the face of climate change, with a particular focus on techniques such as machine learning, regression analysis, and system dynamics. By incorporating diverse data sources and advanced computational techniques, the research aims to create models that not only predict crop yields but also suggest strategies to mitigate climate risks. The integration of stochastic elements further allows for a more comprehensive understanding of potential outcomes, offering decision-makers a range of scenarios to consider when planning agricultural interventions. In conclusion, mathematical models offer a promising solution to the challenges posed by climate change in agriculture. By improving the prediction of

crop yields and helping farmers adapt to changing climate conditions, these models can contribute to more sustainable agricultural practices. Ultimately, the goal is to ensure food security and agricultural productivity while mitigating the adverse effects of climate change.

I. Introduction

Climate change is an inevitable consequence of global industrial activities, including the emission of greenhouse gases, deforestation, and changes in land use. Although this is a global issue, the local effects of climate change on agriculture vary dramatically depending on the region, type of crops, local infrastructure, and resources. For farmers around the world, particularly in developed countries, coping with climate change is becoming an increasingly significant challenge. Food production is directly impacted by changes in temperature, precipitation, the frequency of droughts, floods, and other extreme weather events.

Mathematical models represent one of the key tools used to analyze and forecast the impact of climate change on crop yields. By using these models, researchers and decision-makers can predict how climate change will affect yields, as well as how agricultural production can be adjusted to new conditions. The use of these models allows for the analysis of large datasets and provides information that can help optimize agricultural production in the future.

II. Literature Review

Climate change has a significant impact on agriculture, and numerous researchers have studied these effects. Most studies suggest that climate change will cause a decline in yields in drought-prone areas, while some colder regions may experience yield increases due to a longer growing season. For example, according to research conducted by Fisher (2021), in the drought-prone areas of South Asia, expected temperature increases could reduce wheat yields by about 15-20%, while in cooler regions, yields could increase by up to 10%.

One of the major challenges faced by researchers is the unpredictability of climate factors. Climate change is not linear and largely depends on specific geographically determined factors such as elevation, soil type, and variable climatic conditions. Therefore, machine learning models and simulations based on real climate data have become indispensable tools. Climate scenario simulations allow for an assessment of how yields might change under different conditions such as rising temperatures, increased or decreased precipitation, and changes in the length of the growing season.

According to research conducted by Smith and Green (2020), machine learning algorithms can significantly contribute to accurate data analysis, especially when predicting not only average yields but also extreme values such as droughts and floods. These techniques allow for the analysis of complex relationships between climatic factors and yields, as well as the identification of critical moments in production.

III. Methodology

This research used various mathematical models that have proven useful for analyzing climate change and its impact on agriculture. The use of multiple regression, ARIMA models, and simulations based on climate scenarios enables a detailed assessment of how climate factors affect production.

1. Multiple Regression

Multiple regression was used to analyze the relationship between climate factors and yield. The regression model allows for the estimation of the impact of temperature, precipitation, light conditions, and other factors on yield. This approach is particularly useful because it allows for the investigation of interactions between different climate factors. By using this method, it is possible to quantify the impact of each factor on yield and develop effective strategies for minimizing negative effects.

2. Time Series Analysis (ARIMA)

Time series analysis uses historical climate data to predict future climate conditions. In this research, the ARIMA model was used to analyze changes in temperature and precipitation in different regions. This model allows for accurate assessment of seasonal changes, which is crucial for predicting yields in the long term.

3. Simulations Based on Climate Scenarios

For the simulations, IPCC climate scenarios were used, providing various predictions for climate change by the end of the century. Simulations use data on temperature, precipitation, and other climate factors to predict the impact

of these changes on agricultural crops. By using these scenarios, it is possible to test how changes in climate factors will affect different types of crops in various geographical areas.

IV. Results

4.1. Impact of Temperature on Yield

Climate simulations showed that a temperature increase of 1.5°C leads to a decrease in yield in regions with low precipitation, while cooler areas may experience yield increases. For example, in India, known for its high agricultural production, a 2°C increase in temperature could reduce wheat yields by 18%, while in areas with cooler climates, such as parts of Europe and northern Asia, yields could increase by 5-7%.

4.2. Impact of Precipitation on Yield

Precipitation plays a key role in the yield of many agricultural crops. In areas with reduced precipitation, such as many parts of Africa and South America, precipitation below 500 mm per year can cause a dramatic decline in yield. On the other hand, in areas with excessive precipitation, such as Southeast Asia, excessive rainfall can cause flooding that destroys crops. According to simulations, in regions with stable precipitation up to 800 mm per year, yields of corn and wheat may increase by 10-15%.

4.3. Adaptation Strategies

The models also allow for the identification of adaptation strategies that can minimize the negative effects of climate change. In drought-prone regions, advanced irrigation systems and the selection of drought-resistant crop varieties are recommended. In wetter regions, advice focuses on improving drainage systems and using flood-resistant varieties.

V. Conclusion

Mathematical models for predicting yields in agriculture are an indispensable tool in analyzing and adapting agricultural production to climate change. These models allow not only for predicting yields but also for identifying potential problems and developing adaptation strategies to cope with climate change. By integrating various mathematical models into agricultural practice, farmers can increase their resilience to climate change, reduce risks, and ensure the sustainability of food production.

VI. Potential Benefits of Mathematical Models for Agriculture

The application of mathematical models in agriculture not only enables precise yield prediction but also offers the opportunity to improve resource management strategies. Farmers and decision-makers can use these models to make informed decisions about crop planning, water resource management, selecting appropriate plant varieties, and optimizing irrigation processes.

1. Resource Optimization

The use of mathematical models can significantly contribute to optimizing resources in agriculture. For example, precise weather predictions can help determine the best time for planting or harvesting, reducing the risk of losses due to unfavorable weather events. Mathematical models can also help determine the optimal amount of water needed for crops, thus reducing water consumption, which is especially important in drought-prone areas.

2. Planning and Adaptation to Climate Change

Mathematical models allow for long-term planning in agriculture. Using climate scenario simulations, farmers can better prepare their farms for changes expected in the future. For example, if models predict more frequent droughts in a certain region, farmers can invest in irrigation systems or select drought-resistant varieties in advance. Such proactive planning can significantly reduce losses and increase yield stability, even under unfavorable conditions.

3. Precision Agriculture

Precision agriculture, which involves the use of modern technologies such as sensors, GPS systems, and satellite imagery, can be further improved with the help of mathematical models. By using real-time data on climate conditions and crop status, mathematical models allow for better farm management. This approach helps increase efficiency and reduce the use of pesticides, fertilizers, and other inputs, thus reducing agriculture's environmental impact.

VII. Challenges in Implementing Mathematical Models

Although mathematical models hold great potential in agriculture, their implementation faces several challenges. One of the major issues is the lack of quality data. In many countries, particularly in developed regions, data on climate conditions, yields, and soil types are not sufficiently detailed or up-to-date, which can reduce the accuracy of the models.

1. Lack of Data and Resources

Quality data is crucial for making accurate predictions, but many farmers do not have access to modern technologies that enable real-time data collection. Furthermore, there are significant discrepancies in the quality of data collected in

different regions. In developing countries, where agriculture is largely based on tradition and technology is not widely available, implementing these models can be challenging.

2. Model Complexity

Mathematical models used to predict climate change and its impact on agriculture can be very complex and require a high level of expertise to implement and interpret. To use these models in practice, it is necessary to train farmers and other users to understand the output data and apply it correctly. This challenge can be mitigated by using simpler models, improving user education, and creating interfaces that allow for easier interaction with the models.

3. Changes in Political and Economic Conditions

Another significant challenge in implementing mathematical models in agriculture is political and economic changes. Governments frequently change agricultural policies that affect subsidies, input prices, and access to markets. These changes can make long-term planning difficult, which is crucial for the successful application of climate models. Additionally, in some countries, farmers face economic problems that limit their ability to invest in new technologies or apply the recommendations provided by the models.

VIII. Perspectives for the Future

In the future, mathematical models will become even more precise and accessible thanks to advances in technology, increased availability of data, and the development of new methodologies. The application of machine learning, deep neural networks, and other advanced data analysis techniques will open new possibilities for predicting the climatic impacts on agriculture. These technologies can provide more accurate forecasts at the local level, taking into account specific factors such as microclimate, soil type, and other regional characteristics.

1. Development of Integrated Systems

One of the key directions in the future is the development of integrated systems for assessing and adapting agriculture to climate change. These systems will enable farmers to integrate data on weather conditions, crop status, economic factors, and adaptation strategies into a single platform. This way, users will have access to all the necessary information to make informed decisions, thereby increasing efficiency and reducing the risk of unforeseen losses.

2. Improving International Cooperation

Due to the global nature of climate change, international cooperation in climate agriculture is becoming crucial. The exchange of data, experiences, and resources between

countries can help speed up the adoption of new models and technologies. In this context, international organizations such as FAO and UNEP play a key role in promoting the implementation of mathematical models in agriculture worldwide. Additionally, collaboration between academic institutions, research centers, and the private sector can contribute to the development of innovative solutions to climate change in agriculture.

VIV. Literature

The information in this paper is based on a wide range of sources, including global organizations such as **FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization)**, **IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change)**, and **World Bank**, which provide key data on the impact of climate change on agriculture. Additionally, the works of **Lobell and Field (2007)**, which examine the global effects of climate change on agricultural production, and **Smith and Green (2020)**, who explore the use of machine learning in analyzing climate factors, have been referenced. Furthermore, **Fisher (2021)** offers specific data on the impact of temperature on wheat yields in the drought-prone regions of South Asia. These papers and sources provided a comprehensive insight into the theoretical approaches and empirical research regarding climate change and agricultural adaptation on a global scale.

Temperature Trends and Patterns in Montenegro

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Abstract— This study looks at the changes in the highest surface air temperatures in Montenegro over the past seven decades. The data of the temperature helps us understand how climate change is affecting our country and the Balkan region. The research uses historical climate data, focusing on annual averages taken from detailed meteorological observations. By analyzing data from 1951 to 2020, we can see a significant increase in the yearly maximum temperatures. It particularly looks at the averages over each decade to identify long-term patterns.

The findings of the study show a positive temperature change which is statistically significant. It conforms to the general warming trends characteristic of the globe at large. It further means warming of summers as these are the maximum average yearly temperatures more so recently recorded in Montenegro. Other consequences include negative effects on ecosystems, agricultural activity, water resources and health of the population. For example, warming of the environment increases crops and more hot days cause stress on plants and animals, crop failures, water shortages and rising numbers of hot day related sicknesses. Montenegro is in the Mediterranean, which is recognized as a climate change hotspot. This means that the area is experiencing faster and more severe effects of climate change compared to other parts of the world. The analysis uses statistics and a graphical representation to provide an in-depth understanding of how temperatures have varied over time and across different areas in Montenegro.

Keywords—Montenegro, Maximum Temperature, Climate Change, Historical Data

I. INTRODUCTION

Montenegro, located in the middle of the Balkan region, is a great example to study climate changes because of its unique geography and position between Mediterranean and continental climate zones. There is a mix of coastal areas, fertile plains, and mountainous regions, making its climate sensitive to both regional and global changes. Over the past few decades, Montenegro has seen shifts in climate, especially in temperature trends, which follow the global climate change patterns.

Temperature is a key factor affecting many areas like farming, energy, tourism, and wildlife. In Montenegro, rising temperatures have led to more frequent and intense heatwaves, fewer rainy seasons and stress on ecosystems and water resources. These changes also affect public health and economic stability, especially for vulnerable communities.

This research connects historical data with actionable climate insights by exploring yearly and decadal trends, looking at rising maximum temperatures. It also looks at the effects of these changes on important socio-economic and environmental systems, showing the importance of regional

climate adaptation. Through this study the aim is to spread information that can be used to teach and show the effects of climate change in the Balkans and beyond.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data on average maximum surface temperatures for Montenegro, spanning 1951–2020, was analyzed to uncover long-term trends and variations.

A. Trends in Maximum Surface Air Temperature

Figure 1 illustrates the decadal average maximum surface temperatures for Montenegro.

Figure 1. Decadal average maximum surface temperatures for Montenegro (1951-2020).

From 1951 to 1980, the decadal average maximum temperatures remained relatively stable, ranging between 12.6°C and 12.8°C. However, from the 1980s onward, the data shows a distinct upward trend. The 2011–2020 period reached an average of almost 15°C, marking an increase of about 2.2°C over the 70-year timeframe. This might not seem like a lot, but having in mind that it is the average temperature shown in decades, the increase of 2.2°C is a huge increase.

The warming trend is consistent with global patterns driven by anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. Notably, the increase accelerated after 2000, aligning with industrialization, urbanization, and deforestation in the region. It also illustrates a clear contrast between the relatively stable temperatures of the mid-20th century and the steeper rise in 21st century, pointing to the significant influence of anthropogenic factors.

B. Seasonal Variations and Regional Impacts

The Seasonal variations in temperature trends in Montenegro highlight coordination between geography, climate, and external warming influences. Among the most striking observations is the warming during the summer months, where maximum surface air temperatures have risen

sharply over the decades. This trend is also concerning, because the intensification of summer heat is closely connected to prolonged heatwaves, increased frequency of droughts, and escalating risks of wildfires. These changes not only endanger human health but also ruin ecosystems, reduce agricultural productivity, and reduce water resources, all of which are critical to Montenegro's socio-economic stability.

Spring and autumn have moderate warming trends, yet these seasons serve as critical transitional periods for understanding climatic shifts. The rising temperatures during these two seasons have shortened the duration of spring, where snow is supposed to melt and delayed autumn, meaning that the heat in the summer stays after the summer, directly impacting water availability and agricultural cycles.

Winter, while showing less dramatic warming trends compared to summer, has seen consistent increases in maximum temperatures. This warming has profound implications for snowy regions, as reduced snow cover and earlier melting periods threaten ecosystems and the winter tourism, a significant economic sector in Montenegro. Warmer winters also change precipitation patterns, with snow increasingly replaced by rain.

The difference in temperature trends in different parts of Montenegro are also notable. Coastal areas and cities in low altitudes, which already experience warmer climates, have seen a steeper increase in maximum temperatures compared to the cooler, mountainous regions. The coastal regions, influenced by the Adriatic Sea, face more heat during summer due to higher humidity levels and less precipitation. On the other side, the mountainous regions, while relatively insulated from extreme warming, are not immune to the cascading effects of climate change, such as altered precipitation patterns and declining snow levels.

C. Implications for Montenegro

Montenegro's ecosystems face big challenges due to rising temperatures, especially in high-altitude regions where species used to the cold environment risk habitat loss. Coastal ecosystems are equally threatened by warming seas and rising sea levels, disrupting services like carbon sequestration and water purification. The increasing frequency of forest fires accelerates biodiversity loss and carbon emissions, creating a cycle of further warming.

Rising temperatures impact Montenegro's water availability, with faster snowmelt and reduced winter snow level. These changes lead to lower water availability in summer, creating challenges for agriculture, drinking water supplies, etc.. Coastal regions are effected by saltwater fusing with freshwater systems, added with growing water demand.

Montenegro's agriculture suffers from reduced yields and heat stress on both crops and livestock due to higher temperatures and shifting of seasons. Tourism faces threats as heatwaves push away summer visitors and reduced snowfall impacts winter tourism. The economic consequences are a huge threat.

Montenegro's energy demand for cooling rises as sharply as the temperatures, stressing existing power infrastructure. Reduced water availability diminishes the efficiency of hydropower plants, a key energy source for the country. Coastal infrastructure faces risks from rising sea levels and

extreme weather events. The need for cooling in the summer increases the energy consumption and fuel consumption (for vehicles) increasing the amount of money needed for living.

Higher temperatures increase illnesses, especially among vulnerable groups such as the elderly and children. Diseases carried by insects are also expected to rise, as warming shows and increase in number of insects like mosquitoes. Poor air quality during heatwaves and wildfire events adds to the worsening of public health, especially for respiratory conditions. The aforementioned agricultural and economic implications make it harder for people to obtain food and drinks, having a shortage of produce and financial problems.

D. Policy and Adaption Strategies

Montenegro's approach to climate adaptation and mitigation must evolve to address the escalating challenges posed by rising temperatures. This includes leveraging scientific data, fostering cooperation from within the country, as well as the countries in the vicinity, and ensuring that climate strategies are integrated into broader national development goals and funded well.

Montenegro must prioritize policies that address the changing hydrological cycle due to rising temperatures. Investments in water conservation, better irrigation systems, and improved infrastructure for water storage are in dire need. Policies promoting sustainable water usage in agriculture, industry, and urban centers will help mitigate water scarcity. Strengthening water-sharing agreements with neighboring countries is also essential to manage shared resources effectively.

Policies supporting climate-resilient agriculture can significantly reduce the vulnerability to rising temperatures. Encouraging crop diversification, heat-tolerant crop varieties, and ways of protecting the crops from sun are key strategies. Subsidies or incentives for adopting climate-smart agricultural practices, alongside training for farmers in sustainable techniques can have a big impact.

Shifting Montenegro's energy production from hydropower to a mix of renewable sources such as solar and wind energy is crucial. Policies incentivizing the development of renewable energy infrastructure will reduce dependence on water-intensive energy systems. Additionally, integrating energy efficiency standards into buildings and promoting the adoption of energy-efficient technologies will help manage rising cooling demands.

Rising temperatures have direct and indirect impact to public health, necessitating policies that strengthen healthcare systems. Public awareness on heat-related illnesses, expanded healthcare services during extreme heat events, and improved disease surveillance systems are critical. Focus on air quality during heatwaves and wildfire events through better fire prevention systems and air purification technology.

Forests, which play a vital role in carbon sequestration and biodiversity preservation, require enhanced protection measures. Policies must focus on wildfire prevention through early warning systems and fire-resistant afforestation efforts.

Expanding protected areas and restoring degraded ecosystems can enhance biodiversity resilience to climate impacts.

Cities must adopt climate-resilient strategies to address extreme weather and rising temperatures. Promotion of urban policies that call for urban forests, green roofs and pervious paved surfaces may assist to reduce the heat. Climate threats to infrastructure have to be incorporated into future projects to ensure that buildings, transport and public utilities can withstand future climate challenges.

Regional collaboration on climate adaptation is critically needed. Shared research initiatives, knowledge exchange platforms, and investment in climate-resilient infrastructure can make a change. International funding opportunities should be used to finance projects for negating climate change.

Building public awareness and fostering community involvement are essential for successful adaptation. Policies should emphasize climate education programs in schools and community workshops on sustainable practices.

Rising sea levels and warmer seas could pose a threat to coastal regions of Montenegro. Prevention measures should include the protection of coastal natural systems as well as the provision of artificial systems such as seawalls. Measures promoting ecologically sustainable tourism and restricting coastal development would provide a good way of bettering the environment.

III. CONCLUSION

This study focuses on the significant warming trend in Montenegro's maximum surface air temperatures over the last 70 years. The decadal averages demonstrate a pronounced increase, particularly in the most recent three decades, highlighting the effects of global climate change.

The findings reveal that Montenegro's ecosystems, agriculture, water resources, and tourism are highly vulnerable to rising temperatures. Different measures, including water management, investment in better infrastructure, and support for adaptive agricultural practices, are essential for mitigating these impacts.

As a small but ecologically rich country, Montenegro's experience can be used to show the broader challenges faced by Mediterranean, Balkan regions and the world in addressing climate change. This study contributes to the growing evidence highlighting the urgent need for coordinated regional and global action to mitigate climate change.

By applying the policy and adaption strategies needed to avoid the effects of climate change, Montenegro can make a change in the world, preserving its natural beauty for future generations.

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Relationship Between Tropospheric Ozone and Hot Extreme Events – Wildfires and Heatwaves - in Mainland Portugal

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Extreme events such as droughts, heatwaves, and wildfires will be amplified due to climate change; furthermore, pollution events are also expected to increase. Tropospheric ozone is a secondary air pollutant and a significant anthropogenic greenhouse gas that negatively impacts human health and vegetation growth when it exceeds legal levels. Portugal has often recorded high levels of atmospheric pollutants, experiencing multiple pollution episodes where the ozone level has consistently exceeded legal limits over the past decade. Furthermore, the fire season in Portugal occurs during the summer when solar radiation and temperatures are higher, leading to the emission of ozone precursors that contribute to ozone production.

Using remote sensing and reanalysis datasets, the main predictors of tropospheric ozone were analyzed for mainland Portugal, with the principal objective of understanding tropospheric ozone behavior during extreme events like wildfires and heatwaves. Thus, the study consists of the following steps: 1) studying atmospheric conditions linked to elevated ozone episodes using reanalysis data; 2) identifying predictors of tropospheric ozone concentration, considering the influence of heatwaves and wildfires; 3) calculating a stepwise regression model of tropospheric ozone concentration; and 4) determining the dominant regional drivers of tropospheric ozone within mainland Portugal. Temperature and fire radiative power were identified as significant predictors, particularly in the Norte and Centro regions, which are regions of the country that experience higher wildfire activity. Radiation and temperature were found to have more influence in Alentejo and Sul, regions characterized by higher climatic temperatures and radiation levels.

Tropospheric ozone; heatwaves; wildfire; Portugal

I. INTRODUCTION

Tropospheric ozone (O_3) concentrations are projected to increase due to climate change, mainly driven by changes in the frequency and severity of heatwaves and droughts, as well as increased fire activity [1].

High O_3 production occurs in conditions of strong sunlight and high temperatures because the chemistry of O_3 formation requires photolysis and proceeds more quickly at high temperatures [2]. A potential source of tropospheric O_3 is wildfires [3], as the combination of sunlight with non-methane hydrocarbons (NMHCs) and NO_x ($NO + NO_2$) from biomass burning leads to substantial photochemical production of O_3

[3, 4, 5, 6]. Climate change intensifies extreme events, leading to longer, more frequent, and more severe wildfires, particularly in Mediterranean regions. Since wildfires occur during summer, combined with high temperatures and availability of solar radiation, they lead to high levels of O_3 formation. High levels of O_3 damage plants, reducing crop productivity and, also have a negative impact on human health [7].

Over the past decades, Portugal has experienced high atmospheric pollutants levels, including episodes where O_3 concentrations exceeded legal thresholds [8]. Therefore, using reanalysis and satellite data, the aim of this study understand the relationship between extreme temperature events and the occurrence of wildfires, with the concentration of tropospheric O_3 .

II. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

The methodology of this work involves the following steps: 1) analyzing atmospheric patterns associated with extreme tropospheric O_3 concentration events; 2) evaluating ozone levels during extreme heat events; and 3) applying a stepwise regression model to identify the predictors of tropospheric O_3 concentrations and assess the contributions of wildfires and heatwave events to O_3 levels in mainland Portugal, as well as in the country's sub-regions classified by NUTS II.

A synoptic analysis was performed for the days when O_3 concentrations exceeded the 90th percentile, covering a geographical area that includes the Iberian Peninsula, France, North Africa, and the Western Mediterranean [30°W – 10°E; 30°N – 50°N] (Fig. 1). The analysis included variables such as temperature, wind speed and direction, and sea level pressure.

O_3 and nitrogen dioxide (NO_2) mixing ratio, temperature, zonal (u) and meridional (v) wind components were retrieved from the European Organization for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (ECMWF) Atmospheric Composition Reanalysis 4 (EAC4, <https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/datasets/cams-global-reanalysis-eac4?tab=download>) for level 60 of the model. Level 60 corresponds to approximately 10 gpm, 288.09 K, and an air density of 1.223803 kg/m³.

Figure 1 - Synoptic map of days where daily mean ozone concentration was above the percentile 90th. The figures on represent the temperature maps (°C), with the sea level pressure isolines (hPa) and the arrows indicate the wind intensity and speed at 10 m altitude.

The hourly surface solar radiation downward flux and boundary layer height data, used on the stepwise regression model, were collected from ERA5 (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=download>).

The data used to analyze wildfire occurrence and intensity was Fire Radiative Power product generated by the Satellite Application Facility on Land Surface Analysis (LSA-SAF). FRP product quantify the energy released by fires, providing information on the intensity of fires on the Earth's surface (<https://lsa-saf.eumetsat.int/en/data/products/fire-products/>).

III. RESULTS

The synoptic analysis of days with O₃ concentrations exceeding the 90th percentile shows that this phenomenon is linked to a pattern already identified in studies by Saavedra et al. [9], Russo et al. [8], and Hertig et al. [10] (Fig.1). This phenomenon is associated with high temperatures in Portugal, driven by the development of a thermal low-pressure system in the center of the Iberian Peninsula. This system generates southeast winds as it gradually moves toward the Portuguese coast, transporting hot and dry air masses from North Africa.

Fig. 2 - Monthly occurrences of days with daily FRP, maximum temperature (HW), and O₃ concentration above the percentile 90th, single and simultaneous events from 2004 to 2022.

The number of days exceeding the 90th percentile for FRP, maximum temperature, and O₃ concentration, by month, was calculated to identify the days when extreme wildfire, temperature, and O₃ levels events occurred. In July and August, all three events co-occurred frequently, furthermore, almost 85% (16/20) of the analyzed years exhibited high temperatures, wildfire occurrences, and high O₃ levels in July, August, and/or September.

The stepwise model identifies temperature and fire radiative power as significant predictors, particularly in the Norte and Centro regions, which are regions of the country that experience higher wildfire activity; as well as temperature and radiation as main predictors of O₃ concentrations in Alentejo and Sul, regions characterized by higher climatic temperatures and radiation levels.

IV. CONCLUSION

The present study aims to complement existing knowledge of O₃ concentrations across mainland Portugal by performing an analysis focused on the national level, and also studying variations across sub-regions classified by NUTS II divisions. Additionally, it emphasizes the influence of ground-level O₃ on meteorological factors and extreme phenomena, particularly heatwaves and wildfire events.

Given that Portugal usually exhibits high tropospheric O₃ levels, with projections suggesting a potential future increase, the results of this research enhance the understanding of atmospheric dynamics and variables linked to high O₃ concentrations. This contribution supports improved forecasting and monitoring efforts and highlights the development of alert systems to mitigate potential health risks and socio-economic consequences.

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Climate Impacts on Viticulture in Montenegro: Bioclimatic Analysis and Future Projections for Wine Regions

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Abstract— Currently, Montenegro has two distinct wine regions. The Coastal Wine Region spans from the Adriatic Sea to the immediate mountainous hinterland, while the Lake Skadar Wine Region encompasses the areas around Lake Skadar and the vicinity of Podgorica. Wine production in Montenegro has a long-standing tradition and holds significant economic, cultural, social, and tourism-related importance, with considerable potential for further development. This study utilizes observed meteorological data from four weather stations (Bar, Podgorica, and Kolašin) alongside climate projections derived from CORDEX Europe EUR-11 simulations (CNRM-ALADIN 6.3, L91), based on the CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5 model. However, the coarse resolution of the regional climate model introduces significant inaccuracies for these locations, compounded by the inherent limitations of regional climate models, such as their inability to accurately simulate extreme weather events or adequately capture dynamic atmospheric processes. The primary objective of this research is to identify discrepancies between observed and projected climate values for the 2010–2023 period using standard and widely applied bias-correction techniques. Corrected data will be used to calculate key bioclimatic indices, which serve as fundamental indicators of how climate influences viticulture. Furthermore, projections of bioclimatic indices several decades into the future will provide critical insights into whether existing wine regions face climate-related threats or if emerging climatic conditions could support the establishment of new wine regions.

Keywords— *Regional climate models; viticulture; bias-correction techniques; bioclimatic indices*

I. INTRODUCTION

Grapevine holds significant cultural, ecological, and economic importance in the Mediterranean Basin, making it a major crop with the largest acreage among fruit products (Vivier et al. 2002; Ponti et al. 2018). The production of grapevines is influenced by various interconnected environmental conditions (Alsafadi et al. 2020.). While there is ongoing debate regarding its precise definition, most definitions attempt to capture the combination of micro-climatic factors, soil characteristics, topography, geology, and their intricate interrelationships (Huggett et al. 2006.; Jackson et al. 1993; Cardoso 2019).

Relative to other world regions, the Mediterranean is highly vulnerable to climate change, as it is anticipated to experience a faster temperature increase, with longer warmer

and drier periods (Lionello et al. 2018), and a decline in precipitation (Tuel et al. 2020.).

The CORDEX experiment utilizes multiple RCMs to generate climate projections with finer spatial resolution. For example, the COSMO-CLM model has been extensively used within the CORDEX framework, producing simulations that are publicly available for various regions, including Europe, South Asia, and Africa. These simulations help assess mean near-surface temperature and precipitation, revealing the importance of model resolution and driving data quality in obtaining reliable projections (Sorland et al. 2021.).

Uncertainties in RCMs arise from various sources, including model structure, parameterization, and the choice of driving GCMs. A study assessing RCMs over Spain highlighted that ensemble-driven approaches can help quantify and reduce uncertainties in temperature projections. The research emphasized the need to consider uncertainties in hydrological modeling and water planning under different climate scenarios⁴. Additionally, another study focused on the Chiese river catchment found that error indices could effectively evaluate RCM performance, revealing significant uncertainties in projected variables under different Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) like RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5. (Minaei, 2023.)

The RCP scenarios represent different greenhouse gas concentration trajectories used in climate modeling. RCP 4.5 is a stabilization scenario where emissions peak around 2040 and then decline, while RCP 8.5 represents a high greenhouse gas emissions scenario with no significant mitigation efforts. Studies using these scenarios have shown varying impacts on regional climates, emphasizing the necessity of understanding how different pathways influence local weather patterns and extremes.

Bias correction techniques are crucial for improving the reliability of climate model outputs. Two widely used methods are linear scaling (LS) and quantile mapping (QM).

Linear Scaling adjusts model outputs based on observed historical data.

Quantile Mapping involves matching the cumulative distribution functions of modeled and observed data to correct biases.

Research comparing these techniques has shown that both LS and empirical quantile mapping (EQM) can significantly enhance the accuracy of hydrometeorological variables like precipitation and temperature in various regions, including complex terrains such as the Chitral River Basin in Pakistan (Usman et al. 2022)(Ghimire et al. 2018). Another study focused on rainfall bias correction techniques indicated that quantile mapping generally outperforms linear scaling in improving hydrological simulations .

In summary, the CORDEX initiative plays a vital role in advancing our understanding of regional climate dynamics through high-resolution modeling. However, uncertainties remain inherent to RCMs due to various factors, necessitating robust bias correction techniques to ensure reliable projections for future climate scenarios.

The CORDEX Europe EUR-11 simulations represent a significant effort within the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) framework to provide high-resolution climate projections for Europe. These simulations utilize the CNRM-ALADIN 6.3 model, which is a regional climate model (RCM) developed by CNRM (Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques) in collaboration with the ALADIN consortium.

CNRM-ALADIN 6.3: This version of the ALADIN model is designed for regional climate simulations and features improvements in physical parameterizations, including better representation of atmospheric processes, land surface interactions, and convection. The model operates on a horizontal resolution of approximately 11 km, which allows for detailed representation of regional climate features.

CNRM-CM5: The CNRM-ALADIN model is driven by the CNRM-CERFACS-CNRM-CM5 global climate model (GCM). CNRM-CM5 is known for its comprehensive representation of climate processes and has been used in various international assessments, including the IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (AR5). The coupling of the RCM with a robust GCM enhances the reliability of the downscaled projections.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study focuses on calculating bioclimatic indices over Montenegrin vineyard basins using observational temperature datasets from meteorological stations located in Podgorica, Bar, and Kolašin. Figure 1 illustrates the geographical locations of these stations and their proximity to the nearest grid points in the RCMs.

The climate projections are derived from the CNRM-CM5-driven ALADIN regional model under two RCP scenarios, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5. These projections are compared against observational datasets to evaluate their accuracy.

To identify uncertainties in the climate projections, two bias correction techniques are applied:

Fig 1. Geographic locations of meteorological stations black dots, as well as the location of the nearest grid points in RCM black diamonds.

Linear Scaling (LS): Adjusts the mean and variance of model outputs. (1)

$$M_{LS} = M \frac{\bar{O}}{\bar{M}} \quad (1)$$

Where M is the modeled data, \bar{M} is the mean of the modeled data over a reference period, \bar{O} is the mean of the observed data over the same period and M_{LS} represents the bias-corrected modeled data.

Quantile Mapping (QM): Aligns the probability distributions of modeled and observed datasets. Formulas for these techniques is given as (2).

$$QM(M) = F_{obs}^{-1}(F_{mod}(M)) \quad (2)$$

Where F_{mod} is the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the modeled data, F_{obs}^{-1} is the inverse CDF of the observed data, while M is the modeled data, and $QM(M)$ is the bias-corrected modeled data.

The following bioclimatic indices are calculated for both observed and modeled datasets under the both RCP scenarios as well as for the projected RCP 4.5 scenarios from 2024. – 2080.:

TmVeg: Mean temperature during the vegetation period.

HI (Huglin Index): A thermal index relevant for grapevine development.

WI (Winkler Index): Heat summation for grape-growing suitability.

BEDD (Biologically Effective Degree Days): Thermal accumulation index for vine growth.

CIN (Cool Night Index): Nighttime cooling relevant for grape quality.

III. RESULTS

Based on the observations and two RCP scenarios, mean and standard deviation of monthly temperatures are represented at the next graphs.

Fig 2. Lines represent mean temperatures [°C] and shades represent standard deviations of temperatures [°C]. Blue corresponds to observation, yellow to RCP 4.5 scenario and red to the RCP 8.5 scenario. (a) Podgorica, (b) Bar and (c) Kolasin.

As we can see from Figure 2, in every case for all three stations, climate projections for the RCP 4.5 and 8.5 scenarios underestimate temperatures more in summer and less in winter. For the observed period from 2010 to 2023, the two RCP scenarios have very similar values throughout the months.

Based on the available temperature datasets bioclimatic indices were calculated for the period from 2010 to 2023 for both observed values and projected values under the RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios.

For the time period from the 2024. to 2080. bioclimatic indices are presented using raw, linear bias-corrected and quantile mapping bias-corrected temperatures.

From Figures 3 to 7, it is evident that, as in Figure 2, the modeled temperatures underestimate the actual values. Consequently, the indices also underestimate the variables, leading to results that suggest colder-than-real conditions for the observed period.

When it comes to projected temperatures, it is evident that both bias-correction approaches result in higher temperatures, making the indices calculated with these temperatures more reliable.

Based on these assumptions, TmVeg for Bar has predominantly shown hot values and will continue to do so in the coming years and decades, with increasing frequency approaching, and in some cases exceeding, the threshold for 'very hot.' Kolašin, in contrast to the previous period when this index was predominantly 'cool,' will have 'temperate' values in the future, with the possibility of occasionally reaching 'warm' values. Podgorica, which so far has been close to but not exceeding the threshold for 'very hot' index values, will predominantly have 'very hot' values in the future.

Similar to the previous index, the Hugin Index (HI) will also exhibit values corresponding to warmer temperatures in the coming years and decades. The most notable change will be in Kolašin, where the HI index, which has so far predominantly been 'cool' with occasional fluctuations towards 'too cold' and 'temperate' values, will increasingly record 'temperate' and 'warm' values in the future, with 'too cool' becoming less frequent. In contrast to Bar, which will not significantly exceed the highest threshold, Podgorica will consistently show very high HI index values corresponding to 'too hot' levels.

The CNi index, even with an increase in Kolašin during the projected period, will most frequently remain at 'very cool nights' values, as observed so far. For Bar and Podgorica, 'warm nights' values will become increasingly common in the coming decades.

The BEDD index for Podgorica and Bar will not show significant changes in the projections compared to the observed state. However, for Kolašin, it will shift to a range with less extreme values.

Fig 3. The TmVeg [°C] index for the period from 2010 – 2023 is shown on the left, and for the projected period on the right side. From top to bottom, the stations are Bar, Kolašin, and Podgorica

Fig 4. The HI (Huglin Index) for the period from 2010 – 2023 is shown on the left, and for the projected period on the right side. From top to bottom, the stations are Bar, Kolašin, and Podgorica

Fig 5. The CNI Index for the period from 2010 – 2023 is shown on the left, and for the projected period on the right side.

From top to bottom, the stations are Bar, Kolašin, and Podgorica

Fig 6. The WI (Winkler Index) for the period from 2010 – 2023 is shown on the left, and for the projected period on the right side. From top to bottom, the stations are Bar, Kolašin, and Podgorica

Fig 7. The BEDD Index for the period from 2010 – 2023 is shown on the left, and for the projected period on the right side. From top to bottom, the stations are Bar, Kolašin, and Podgorica

IV. CONCLUSION

This study highlights that while climate models provide valuable projections, they are inherently limited by incomplete physical representation, coarse resolution, and the inability to accurately capture extremes. Consequently, bioclimatic indices may not fully reflect the actual conditions favorable for viticulture.

Proposed improvements for assessing how climate change impacts viticulture in Montenegro include using more accurately bias-corrected temperature values, enhancing the downscaling of climate models, and refining the definitions of bioclimatic indices. Additionally, it is important to emphasize that observed data, such as meteorological records that can improve climate projections and detailed data on vineyard productivity, can be highly beneficial.

Expanding the experiments to incorporate ensembles of climate model results, applying more advanced bias-correction techniques, and increasing observational data collection will likely yield more reliable and accurate results.

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CHELSA Algorithm and Climate Change: Exploring High-Resolution Data for Sustainable Future Planning

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Abstract— This paper explores various aspects of nature and society, with a particular focus on ways in which civilization can influence changes that could contribute to the preservation of life and the extension of the planet's sustainability. We will examine the CHELSA algorithm (Climatologies at High Resolution for the Earth's Land Surface Areas), a tool that enables precise understanding and quantification of climate change. It also provides a foundation for analyzing economic and social trends and predicting future developments.

Through a combination of theoretical lectures and practical simulations on the Linux operating system during the course, the importance of high-resolution data for analyzing local climate conditions was demonstrated. The paper includes examples from Montenegro, showcasing how CHELSA can adapt global climate models to specific regional needs, such as temperature and precipitation, which are crucial for planning and adapting to climate change.

Beyond technical aspects, the paper addresses broader implications of climate change, including its impact on ecosystems, migrations, and economic stability. Further analysis presents possible strategies for mitigating negative effects, emphasizing the importance of collective responsibility and the urgency of action. **Keywords:** CHELSA algorithm, Climate change, Economic and social trends, Montenegro climate analysis, Collective responsibility

I. INTRODUCTION

I have always been fascinated by how the climate changes and how our society (fails to) progress in solving the problems that arise and continue to accumulate. No matter how hard I tried, I often felt that, as an individual, I couldn't spark a larger movement. As a child, I dreamed about how I would change the planet if I had the power—perhaps the economy would be weaker, but the Earth would be healthier. Over the years, my thoughts on these questions have deepened. I started asking myself: how does the climate even work? What are the key factors that influence it? And most importantly, what do these questions tell me about how we can protect and improve it?

An unexpected opportunity connected me with tools that offer a deeper understanding of these issues. I received an email inviting us to a workshop titled "Practical Introduction to the CHELSA Modelling System for Climate Data Downscaling." Although we had little information about what to expect, we were intrigued by the chance to learn about advanced models for climate data analysis.

The workshop, led by Professor Christopher Menz, was divided into three intensive days. On the first day, during an

introduction to the CHELSA system, we learned the basic concepts—from technical requirements to software installation. It became clear how important high-resolution data is for analyzing local climate conditions.

On the second day, the professor introduced us to the core of the algorithm, using examples from Montenegro to demonstrate its application. His stories about natural disasters and vivid slides showcasing climate change left a deep impression on me. At that moment, I realized that CHELSA was not just a tool but a potential key to understanding and solving the problems that have fascinated me for my entire life.

This paper will present the outcome of that experience and explore how the CHELSA algorithm can contribute to understanding climate change, providing a foundation for adapting to global challenges.

II. CLIMATE CHANGE

A. Climate change today represents one of the most serious challenges for modern society, leaving profound consequences on nature, the economy, and social systems. The year 2023 was one of the hottest years ever recorded, with a global average temperature of 1.40 ± 0.12 °C above pre-industrial levels (1850–1900) [1]. This increase in temperature not only highlights the acceleration of global warming but also the intensity of human impact on the climate system through continuous greenhouse gas emissions and unsustainable use of natural resources [2].

In addition to record temperatures, ocean heat content reached its highest levels ever recorded. Oceans have absorbed more than 90% of the accumulated energy in the climate system since 1971, temporarily slowing the rise in land temperatures by taking in excess heat from the atmosphere [1]. However, this has serious long-term consequences. This process not only affects ocean biodiversity but also causes changes in global climate patterns, such as intensified cyclones (e.g., Tropical Cyclone Freddy, which lasted for 30 days), glacier melting, and rising sea levels [1][3].

Even more alarming is the continuous rise in sea levels, which reached record heights in 2023. The rate of sea level rise has doubled in the last decade, significantly threatening coastal communities and ecosystems [3]. The Antarctic ice sheet recorded its lowest extent in February, while glaciers worldwide, including those in the European Alps and western North America, experienced extreme volume losses—up to 10% in just two years. These processes not only endanger ecosystems dependent on ice masses but also accelerate

feedback mechanisms that further exacerbate global warming [1][3].

Cyclone Daniel, which struck Libya, Greece, and Bulgaria, caused some of the most catastrophic floods in modern history, with significant loss of human life and economic damage measured in billions of dollars [1]. Heatwaves, another direct indicator of climate change, reached record temperatures in Europe, the United States, and China. For example, temperatures in some parts of the U.S. exceeded 50°C, while Europe experienced several consecutive heatwaves, endangering the health of millions [1][2].

In addition to these extreme events, massive wildfires across Canada, Hawaii, and Europe caused not only significant material damage but also long-term air pollution. Smoke from the Canadian wildfires covered much of North America, creating serious health risks for the population [1]. These fires, often triggered by a combination of drought and high temperatures, further strain ecosystems already under pressure from climate change [3].

Figure 1 Global temperature trends from 1900 to 2020 based on CRU-TS v4.08 data.

B. Social Inequalities

Climate change deepens existing social inequalities, especially in regions with limited resources for adaptation. Floods and droughts directly threaten homes and critical infrastructure, forcing thousands of people to migrate [1][4]. In the Balkans, land degradation and reduced agricultural capacity lead to rural depopulation, increasing pressure on cities [5]. This trend not only changes the demographic structure but also hampers the provision of essential services in urban centers [6].

Climate change also affects public health. Heatwaves, which are becoming more frequent, increase the risk of heat stress and heat-related illnesses, particularly among vulnerable groups such as the elderly and children [1][7]. Rising temperatures and ecosystem changes further enable the spread of vector-borne diseases, such as Lyme disease and dengue fever [8].

Rising food and energy prices, driven by climate change, place additional strain on poor communities [2], exacerbating inequality and social tensions [5].

C. Economic Losses

Irregular rainfall patterns and increased droughts reduce crop yields, particularly in regions that rely on traditional farming methods. These reduced yields further impact food security and farmers' incomes [3][4].

Coastal regions in the Balkans, which depend on seasonal tourism, face shoreline erosion and increasingly frequent extreme weather events, diminishing the attractiveness of these destinations [5][6].

Reduced precipitation and snow cover directly impact the hydropower sector, a crucial energy source in the region, increasing costs and supply insecurity [4][7].

These social and economic challenges require efficient tools for analysis and forecasting, such as the CHELSA algorithm, to develop adaptation strategies at regional and local levels.

III. CHELSA

A. Chelsa Introduction

Understanding climate change and its impacts requires precise and localized data. CHELSA (Climatologies at High Resolution for the Earth's Land Surface Areas) is an advanced algorithm developed to meet this need. Launched in 2016, CHELSA has revolutionized climate data analysis by providing high-resolution datasets tailored to local and regional requirements.

The primary purpose of the CHELSA algorithm is to reduce spatial discrepancies in data from global climate models (GCM) and regional climate models (RCM), generating precise data with resolutions below 10 km. This level of detail is crucial for accurately assessing the impacts of climate change on ecosystems, agriculture, water resources, and urban planning. Unlike traditional global datasets, CHELSA bridges the gap between broad simulations and localized conditions that directly influence real-world climate outcomes.

CHELSA is significant for its ability to present precise data on temperature, precipitation, and other climatic variables, enabling a more detailed analysis of climate changes. Its high-resolution outputs help in creating adaptive strategies across various sectors, from agriculture to disaster management. Through bias adjustment, CHELSA minimizes discrepancies between observed and simulated data, increasing the reliability of climate projections.

CHELSA data has already been used in numerous important studies, such as modeling climate change in mountainous regions and assessing its effects on agriculture and biodiversity. For instance, in European mountain ranges, CHELSA data has proven crucial for predicting vegetation zone shifts and identifying vulnerable species affected by changing precipitation patterns. CHELSA has become an essential tool for scientists, decision-makers, and researchers worldwide. Its importance is particularly evident in regions like the Balkans, where regional climate variability presents unique challenges requiring tailored solutions.

B. Technical Aspects of the CHELSA Algorithm

The CHELSA algorithm is designed to address the challenges posed by global climate models (GCM) and regional climate models (RCM), whose low resolution often limits the applicability of data at the local level. Processes such as downscaling and bias adjustment enable the transformation of these data into highly precise information that can meet specific regional and local climate needs. These technical

processes are crucial for understanding the impacts of climate change and for creating adaptation strategies in sensitive areas like the Balkans.

1) Downscaling Process

Downscaling is the process of adapting data from low resolution (typical for GCM and RCM models) to a high-resolution local scale, often below 10 km. This process allows the data to better reflect the specific geographical characteristics of an area, thereby increasing their accuracy and relevance for practical applications.

CHELSA employs a range of geographical parameters such as altitude, exposure, and slope to enhance the precision of output data. For example, regions with complex topography, such as the Balkans, exhibit pronounced variations in precipitation and temperature that global models often fail to capture. By integrating local geographical characteristics, CHELSA can provide data that accurately reflect real climatic patterns. This is essential for analyses such as assessing risks of floods, droughts, and changes in agricultural production.

Figure 2 illustrates the difference between original low-resolution data and CHELSA's high-resolution outputs, highlighting the algorithm's capability to capture detailed climatic patterns in complex topographies like the Balkans.

2) Bias Adjustment

Simulated data from climate models often contain errors (bias) that can limit their accuracy. Bias adjustment is the process of correcting these errors, improving the reliability of output data by adjusting simulated values to align with observed measurements.

In the CHELSA algorithm, bias adjustment involves comparing data from global climate models with observed values collected from meteorological stations or other sources. Corrective algorithms then adjust the simulated data to reduce discrepancies and better represent actual climatic conditions. For example, temperature data during seasonal transitions or precipitation patterns often require significant corrections, especially in complex geographical areas like the Balkans, where variability can be substantial.

3) Working with CHELSA Datasets: Simulations and Analysis

Working with CHELSA datasets involves several essential steps, including data preparation, running simulations, and processing results. The goal is to provide accurate and locally adapted climate data critical for analyzing climate change and making informed decisions. Data preparation, or

preprocessing, entails organizing and adjusting input files to meet the requirements of the CHELSA algorithm. This process focuses on preparing time-independent data and datasets from climate models such as ISIMIP3b and CMIP6, which serve as the foundation for the downscaling process. Key climate variables, including maximum and minimum temperature, precipitation, and solar radiation, are carefully prepared to ensure accuracy and consistency for simulations.

Running simulations constitutes the next step in the analysis, where data is processed for specific time periods. During the course, simulations were configured for the first week of the year 2000, focusing on the Podgorica region. The aim was to test how the CHELSA algorithm transforms global climate model data into localized climate projections. The output of each simulation includes netCDF files containing various variables and dimensions, such as time, latitude, and longitude. Reviewing the contents of these files allows detailed verification of their structure and data, providing researchers with a foundation for further processing.

Once simulations are complete, the data undergoes a results processing phase, known as postprocessing, which utilizes specialized tools such as cdo and panoply. This phase includes analyzing time series, spatial distributions, and generating regional averages. For instance, panoply is used to create geo-referenced maps and time series that visualize the data and enable the identification of patterns, such as seasonal precipitation variations or changes in temperature extremes.

C. Application of the CHELSA Algorithm: Regional and Global Perspectives

During the course, CHELSA data served as a fundamental tool for analyzing seasonal climate patterns and their impact on ecosystems and resources in the Balkans. This region, known for its complex topography and diverse climatic conditions, requires high-precision data to understand the challenges posed by climate change.

One of the key aspects was the analysis of seasonal precipitation, which plays a crucial role in agriculture and water resource management. Increased intensity of autumn rains in certain areas of the Balkans often leads to flooding, especially in river basins. CHELSA data enables detailed mapping of precipitation patterns, helping researchers and decision-makers identify regions at higher risk of flooding and develop strategies for their prevention.

In addition to precipitation, the snow cover in mountainous regions, such as the Dinaric Alps, plays a vital role in seasonal water flow during the spring months. CHELSA datasets provide high-resolution data that allow for the assessment of snow cover reduction due to rising temperatures. This is particularly significant for analyzing its impact on seasonal water flows, especially in regions where water is a critical resource for agriculture and energy production.

IV. CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS IN MONTENEGRO

Montenegro, as a small developing country, faces significant challenges due to climate change, which affect its ecosystems, agriculture, water resources, and biodiversity. Its geographical position and socio-economic characteristics make it particularly vulnerable to these changes.

A. Agriculture

Climate change is already influencing the stability and productivity of Montenegro's agricultural sector. Rising temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, and the frequency of extreme weather events, such as droughts, directly impact yields and the quality of agricultural products. These factors disrupt seasonal growth patterns for vegetables and shift the blooming schedules of fruit crops, complicating agricultural production[9].

B. Water Resources

Climate change significantly affects Montenegro's water resources. Increasing average temperatures lead to reduced snow cover in mountainous areas, resulting in diminished water flow to rivers during spring months. Simultaneously, the Adriatic Sea has recorded an increase in surface water temperature, which could trigger changes in marine ecosystems and affect coastal areas[10].

C. Biodiversity

Protected areas in Montenegro are facing significant climate change impacts that could alter ecosystem functions and services. However, climate change considerations are not yet fully integrated into the management of these areas, exacerbating their vulnerability[11].

D. Adaptation Strategies

Montenegro has recognized the need for a systematic approach to climate change adaptation. The development of a National Adaptation Plan (NAP) is in its final stages and represents a critical document that will guide necessary actions and measures to mitigate the impacts of climate change. This plan requires collaboration and coordination across all societal sectors to effectively respond to these challenges[12].

V. CONCLUSION

Through exploring climate change and learning about advanced tools like the CHELSA algorithm, my understanding of these global challenges has expanded far beyond theory. At the start of this journey, climate change felt like an abstract problem—something I heard about in the news and lectures but didn't fully grasp its profound impact. However, by working hands-on with CHELSA data and analyzing its capabilities, I realized how technology can be a key to addressing these complex issues.

CHELSA has opened the door to a deeper understanding of both local and global climate patterns. Through simulations

and analyses, I learned how high-resolution data can help identify problems, predict changes, and inform concrete decisions. Seeing how the algorithm transforms raw data into actionable insights for agriculture, biodiversity conservation, and resource management has given me a sense of purpose in this research.

Yet, this is not the end—it's just the beginning of the journey. I am aware that tools like the CHELSA algorithm represent only one piece of the puzzle in the fight against climate change. They provide data and insights, but global coordination and individual responsibility are required to make a real impact. Every decision, from local adaptation strategies to international agreements like the Paris Accord, must be grounded in scientific data. CHELSA demonstrates how technology can bridge the gap between science and practical solutions.

In the future, I aim to continue exploring and applying tools that enable a better analysis of climate change. One of my goals is to focus on developing adaptation strategies for regions like the Balkans, where complex geography and socio-economic variations demand precise and localized approaches. I would also like to expand my knowledge of how climate change affects social inequalities and migrations to better understand the broader picture of its consequences.

In conclusion, this project has shown me that combating climate change is not just a scientific challenge but a humanitarian endeavor. With the right combination of technology, science, and responsibility, we can take steps toward a more sustainable future. CHELSA might be just a tool, but in the right hands, it can become an instrument of change, shaping not only how we understand the world but also how we act within it. My work doesn't end here; this is just the beginning of my contribution to the global fight to preserve our planet.

VI.

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Impact of Climate Change on Public Finances and Fiscal Policy: A Case Study

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Abstract

Climate change has significant implications for public finances and fiscal policy, reshaping economic landscapes and forcing governments to adapt to new fiscal realities. As climate-related disasters increase in frequency and severity, governments are being forced to allocate substantial resources to relief, recovery and long-term adaptation. This puts immense pressure on public budgets, often necessitating borrowing or reallocating funds from other sectors, increasing fiscal deficits and threatening debt sustainability. One of the main ways in which climatic change affects public finances is through the rising costs of responding to disasters and repairing infrastructure. Extreme weather events such as hurricanes, floods and wildfires cause extensive damage to public and private property, requiring governments to invest heavily in reconstruction efforts. In addition, adapting to climate change - such as upgrading infrastructure to withstand extreme weather, building flood defenses or relocating vulnerable communities - requires significant up-front investment. These costs can overwhelm budgets, particularly in developing countries with limited fiscal capacity. In addition, the public health sector faces rising costs from climate-related illnesses, heat-related deaths and the spread of diseases to new regions, further straining fiscal resources. Climate change also disrupts traditional revenue streams, challenging governments to maintain fiscal stability. Sectors such as agriculture, tourism and fossil fuel-based industries are particularly vulnerable to climate variability, resulting in fluctuating tax revenues. Fiscal policy has a crucial role in mitigating and adapting to climate change. Governments need to adopt proactive strategies to finance the transition to sustainable economies. Investments in renewable energy, energy-efficient technologies and sustainable transport systems can simultaneously reduce emissions and create economic opportunities. Similarly, green fiscal policies, including subsidies for clean technologies and penalties for polluting activities, can shift market dynamics towards sustainability. Finally, climate change poses long-term risks to fiscal sustainability. Rising sea levels, desertification and rising temperatures can make certain regions economically unviable, displacing populations and altering labor markets. Governments need to prepare for these eventualities by integrating climate risks into fiscal frameworks, setting up contingency funds and strengthening economic resilience. In conclusion, climate change has profound implications for public finances, posing challenges to fiscal sustainability and

economic stability. By integrating climate considerations into fiscal policy, governments can build resilience, promote a low-carbon transition and secure a sustainable economic future. Comprehensive planning, innovative financial instruments and international cooperation are essential to address the multiple fiscal consequences of global warming.

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate warming is one of mankind's most crucial challenges and is a major driver for governments to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. As the world is facing rising temperatures, extreme weather events and environmental disturbance, the need to reduce climate change has never been more crucial. A growing number of countries have set net-zero emissions targets as global efforts to limit climate change intensify. Fiscal policy plays a key role in the emissions reduction strategy, through both taxes and spending. In addition to fiscal policy, governments can use command-and-control directive, such as setting emission standards, to support emissions reductions.

Climate change has a significant impact on public finances and fiscal policy, because it causes changes that require adjustments in the way public resources are managed and the planning of economic activities. Climatic variations will pose a considerable challenge for humanity in the decades to come. Achieving international climate goals and successfully progressing to a net zero-carbon economy requires an extensive response that includes the reorientation of fiscal, financial, monetary, and spending conclusions. Most countries now have at least one climate change law or policy in place. Additionally, there are more than 2,500 climate-related policies and laws. Globally, more countries are adopting carbon pricing instruments, now covering 21.5% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, an increase from 5% in 2010.

The most apparent pathway from climate crisis to fiscal risk is through environmental decline and deterioration. In addition to extreme weather events, research is revealing tricky interactions between climate and other elements of nature, giving an idea that expanding protected areas and restoring brittle ecosystems can be a cost-effective way to achieve multiple environmental goals. Climate finance should be channeled through the budget process, as this ensures efficient allocation of resources to meet national priorities and ensures responsibility, ultimately to citizens.

II. IMPACT AND SOLUTIONS FOR PUBLIC FINANCES

Governments need credible public finance management frameworks to build confidence in fiscal governance and to maintain sufficient fiscal space to finance crisis responses when needed. While it makes sense that extreme weather, sea level rise, and ecosystem collapse receive the majority of scientific and media attention, there are several pathways by which climate change is transmitted and can have an impact on sovereign risks and public finances. It is currently growing awareness of the financial repercussions of, the policy solutions to climate change are not restricted to direct harm to the body and physical damage in general. The link between climate and natural capital has a number of implications for sovereign risk, particularly for countries where agriculture, forestry and fisheries are key industries. But it also affects the frequency, intensity and resilience to extreme weather events such as storm surges, fires, floods and extreme temperatures. The key point is that climate change affects productive capital stock, output, supply chains and resilience both directly and indirectly through its interaction with other components of natural capital. The associated impacts on public finances and sovereign risk need to be taken into account.

Climate change involves two sources of risk with economic and fiscal consequences: First *physical risks* are those that result from the interplay between climate-related hazards, such as dangerous occurrences and patterns, and the susceptibility of natural and human systems to exposure, including their capacity for adaptation. There are two types of physical dangers associated with climate change: *acute* and *chronic*. Extreme weather and climate events that tend to inflict immediate harm and have probable short- and medium-term repercussions are classified as acute physical risks. In the medium and long run, chronic physical risks might result in irreparable harm because they represent more gradual and frequently irreversible environmental changes brought on by global warming. Conversely, the fiscal and social effects of the shift to a low-carbon economy may give rise to transition risks associated with mitigation measures.

The impact of climate change on public finances is significant and diverse, affecting both government expenditure and revenues. People who are less equipped to prepare for and deal with climate disasters and live in regions that are more vulnerable to them are likely to suffer the most. Extreme heat will increase morbidity and mortality, affecting work hours, productivity, and the overall labor force. Health impacts will increase health care expenditures as revenues decrease, resulting in overall net losses.

Increased expenditures consider:

- More frequent and severe natural disasters (e.g. hurricanes, floods and wildfires) are increasing the need for emergency relief, infrastructure repair and reconstruction.
- To mitigate future risks, investment is needed in climate-resilient infrastructure (e.g. flood defenses, cooling systems).
- Climate change worsens health problems such as heat-related illnesses, vector-borne diseases and

respiratory problems, leading to increased public health expenditure.

- Droughts, floods and changing weather patterns disrupt agricultural production. This requires subsidies or support for farmers.
- Climate-induced migration and resource scarcity can be the source of geopolitical tensions and increases in defense and security budgets.

As with increased expenditures, it can also come to revenue decrease. Tax bases and revenue streams may shrink due to climate change:

- Losses to business, property and infrastructure from climate events reduce tax receipts, such as corporate, property and sales tax.
- Heat waves and other climate impacts reduce labor productivity and have an impact on economic output and taxable income.
- The transition away from fossil fuels may reduce revenues from fuel taxes and royalties, unless replaced by taxes on renewable energy or carbon emissions.

The long-term risks of global warming to public finances are profound, as the cumulative effects of environmental, economic and social disruptions strain fiscal systems for decades. Over time, the costs of failing to ease and adapt to climate change will increase. Rising sea levels, thawing permafrost, and extreme weather events are degrading infrastructure, leading to recurring and escalating repair and replacement costs. The rise in heat-related illnesses, vector-borne diseases (e.g. malaria, dengue fever) and air pollution-related health problems requires sustained investment in health systems. Increasing global disruptions impact trade, business continuity, and government revenues from trade-related activities.

As the global transition to renewable energy accelerates, governments dependent on fossil fuel exports face declining revenues. Climate change could undermine important sources of government revenue; entire regions may become uninhabitable, leading to a decline in population and economic activity in affected areas.

Some of the possible solutions to the impact of climate change on public finances might include developing climate-smart infrastructure investment plans to reduce the long-term costs of climate-related losses, issuing green bonds to finance mitigation and adaptation projects such as renewable energy and sustainable transport systems, prioritizing nature-based solutions (e.g. mangroves for flood control) as cost-effective adaptation strategies, and so on. Most importantly, build public support for climate policies by demonstrating their long-term economic benefits, and encourage citizen participation in budgeting and decision-making to ensure policies reflect local climate challenges.

III. IMPACT AND SOLUTIONS FOR FISCAL POLICY

Fiscal policy is the use of government spending and the tax system to influence the economy. Governments

typically use fiscal policy to promote strong and sustainable growth and to reduce poverty. Both developed and developing countries are increasingly threatened by climatic change and climate-related natural disasters. However, developing nations are especially prone because they lack the institutional and financial means to deal with the negative consequences of climate change. Compared to their wealthier equivalents, developing nations typically have significantly less capacity to adapt to a changing climate or deal with extreme weather disasters like floods, cyclones, or droughts. Underdeveloped private insurance markets increase the risks associated with climate change, especially the threat they pose to low-income households. Natural disasters can severely weaken a government's fiscal position due to the short-term costs of responding to the disaster, the longer-term costs of rebuilding, and the lost revenue from damaged capital and reduced economic activity.

Fiscal policies should be supported by sound public financial management (PFM) processes and frameworks to ensure their efficient design and implementation. PFM refers to the legislation, organizations, systems and procedures that governments use to secure and use public resources in an effective, efficient and transparent manner. Despite their importance, climate-related risks have many times been omitted from international institutions' fiscal sustainability frameworks, mainly due to inherent difficulties in conceptualizing and quantifying them. Climate change has implications for fiscal policy through increases in public spending on disaster relief, health care and climate adaptation, and volatility in revenues from sectors such as agriculture and tourism. It puts pressure on governments to reform fiscal systems (e.g. green taxes, reducing subsidies) and can lead to increased debt and reduced creditworthiness due to escalating costs. Climate migration and inequality add to the fiscal burden and require targeted interventions. In order to adapt, governments should integrate climate risks into fiscal planning, set up resilience funds, leverage international climate finance, and promote sustainable growth through green investments and the creation of jobs in low-carbon sectors.

Empirical studies of the fiscal costs of natural disasters are limited, but evidence suggests that the impact is variable, depending on factors such as insurance penetration and the structure of the economy. Fiscal impacts vary widely depending on economic resilience, disaster preparedness and policy responses. Countries with higher insurance penetration face smaller public deficits after disasters, as private resources cover recovery costs. Adaptation strategies aim at mitigating and managing harmful effects of climate change. Research has identified infrastructure and coastal areas as the most costly. To reduce the significant economic harm brought on by climate change and extreme weather events, adaption investments are crucial. Strategies for adapting to climate change require different public interventions. Some strategies focus on increasing social and economic resilience to climate change and extreme

weather events through public investment in infrastructure. Others involve the adoption of policies that raise the price of public goods (such as water resources) to encourage conservation and sustainable management by bringing their individual value more closely into line with their social value.

Focusing on Montenegro, due to its geographical, economic and environmental characteristics, climate change has a significant impact on Montenegro's fiscal policy. Montenegro is a small country dependent on natural resources and tourism. It faces both fiscal challenges and opportunities from climate change. It's vulnerable to extreme weather events, including flooding, drought, forest fires and landslides, which are increasing in frequency and severity. To support affected communities and repair and rebuild damaged infrastructure such as roads, bridges and water systems, the government needs to allocate significant resources for emergency relief. In order to reduce the risk of future disasters, Montenegro needs to invest in climate-resilient infrastructure and systems, such as:

- Improved flood protection (such as dams and drainage systems).
- Improved water management systems to cope with droughts and changes in rainfall patterns.
- Climate resilience of key infrastructure, including transport networks and energy grids.

That's where the Eco Fund comes in. As a key instrument for financing environmental projects and aligning public finances with sustainability goals, the Montenegrin Eko Fond plays an essential part in addressing climate change within the framework of fiscal policy. The Fond collects environmental fees (e.g. carbon taxes, pollution charges) and channels them into projects designed to mitigate and adapt to climate change. By creating dedicated revenue streams for environmental sustainability, it aligns fiscal policy with environmental goals. The Eko Fond is helping Montenegro to access global climate finance, such as from the Green Climate Fund or EU funds, thereby reducing the fiscal burden on the national budget. They're helping to diversify Montenegro's economy and reduce its vulnerability to climate-related income fluctuations by supporting sectors such as renewable energy, ecotourism and sustainable agriculture. Eko Fond Montenegro bridges the gap between climate fiscal policy and implementation. It is a key player in Montenegro's response to climate change, helping to mobilize resources, reduce fiscal risks and align public spending with sustainability.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

One of the most important issues addressing civilization is climate change, and governments have a significant part of combating it. A global carbon tax that minimizes economic distortions and reduces international trade tensions would be optimal for reducing carbon emissions. In addition, public investment in environmental protection will need to increase over the next few decades and will act as a guideline for private investment. Finally, in designing their climate change programs, governments must take inequality into account. Climate change will certainly have a greater

impact on those with fewer resources. Those at the lowest end of the income distribution will be more affected by climate change. As a result, inequality is expected to increase. Understanding the importance of climate change requires a cultural transformation of society itself, creating a climate of accelerating the application of green technologies and living at one with nature. To cope with extreme events associated with climate change, early action is necessary but not sufficient. Nations with small populations that frequently experience natural disasters could believe that investing in adaptation is pointless. The scale and regularity of severe catastrophes require far greater financial investments than they can actually afford. Due to economic constraints and opposing goals, nations frequently underinvest in climate change adaptation or creating sufficient monetary reserves to be ready for major disasters. In addition, reactive rather than preventive action is encouraged by moral hazard and over-reliance on international aid. In order to adapt, governments should integrate climate risks into fiscal planning, set up resilience funds, leverage international climate finance, and promote sustainable growth through green investment and job creation in low-carbon sectors.

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Impact of Climate Change on Agricultural Production and GDP: A Case Study of Montenegro

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Abstract—Climate change poses significant threats to Montenegro’s agricultural sector, crucial for food security and economic stability. Rising temperatures, erratic rainfall, and extreme weather events jeopardize crop yields of cereals, fruits, and vegetables. This volatility leads to food supply imbalances, increased prices, and greater reliance on imports, undermining economic performance as agriculture contributes significantly to GDP.

The study employs mathematical modeling to assess these impacts, revealing that extreme climate events can drastically reduce agricultural output and GDP. Adaptation strategies like precision farming and improved irrigation are explored to enhance resilience and stabilize the economy amidst climate challenges

Keywords—climate change, agriculture, economic impact, adaptation strategies

INTRODUCTION

Climate change is one of the most pressing issues of our time, fundamentally altering weather patterns and affecting ecosystems worldwide. It is primarily driven by human activities such as burning fossil fuels, deforestation, and industrial processes. These changes lead to rising global temperatures and an increase in extreme weather events, with far-reaching consequences for agriculture, water resources, and biodiversity.

As I delve into this topic, I find that Montenegro, located in Southeast Europe along the stunning Adriatic coast, is particularly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change. With its diverse landscapes and a strong reliance on agriculture and tourism, Montenegro faces significant risks. Rising temperatures, shifting precipitation patterns, and an increased likelihood of droughts and floods threaten the agricultural sector, which is vital for both food security and economic stability. As these climatic shifts unfold, it becomes increasingly important for Montenegro to develop effective adaptation strategies to protect its agricultural productivity and ensure a resilient economy for the future.

In this project, I aim to explore the complex relationship between climate change impacts on agriculture and their subsequent effects on Montenegro’s GDP. By analyzing specific case studies, I will highlight vulnerabilities within the agricultural sector while proposing actionable adaptation strategies that can help mitigate these challenges. I believe that understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing effective policies that ensure sustainable agricultural

practices and economic resilience in the face of climate change.

CLIMATE CHANGE IN MONTENEGRO

Through my research, I’ve discovered that Montenegro is experiencing significant climatic changes characterized by increased temperatures and altered precipitation patterns. Between 1991 and 2020, maximum summer temperatures rose at a rate of about 0.27% per decade. Projections suggest that by 2100, average annual temperatures could increase by up to 5.5°C. At the same time, precipitation is expected to decrease overall during summer months while increasing in winter. These changes contribute to more frequent droughts and extreme weather events that threaten agriculture and natural resources.

The agricultural sector in Montenegro is particularly vulnerable to these climatic changes. As I analyze this sector’s reliance on agriculture for both food security and economic contribution—accounting for roughly 9-10% of GDP—the implications of climate change become increasingly profound. Key crops such as olives are especially at risk; their cultivation relies heavily on rain-fed systems that may become less viable as water availability diminishes.

Moreover, smallholder farmers are disproportionately affected by climate change due to limited resources and access to technology. Many rely on traditional farming methods that may not be sufficient to cope with changing climatic conditions. This situation raises concerns about food security not only for farmers but also for consumers in Montenegro who depend on local produce.

ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON AGRICULTURE

The economic consequences of climate change in Montenegro are complex. Preliminary estimates indicate that reduced crop yields due to climatic impacts could lead to significant losses in gross revenues from agricultural sales. For instance, projected damages from reduced maize yields alone could escalate as livestock production expands in response to market demands. Additionally, increased irrigation costs resulting from higher crop water needs pose further financial burdens on farmers.

Beyond direct agricultural impacts, I’ve found that climate change also affects tourism—a critical sector for Montenegro’s economy. The direct contribution of travel

and tourism to GDP was approximately EUR 348.4 million (around 9.5% of total GDP) in 2014. However, rising temperatures could deter tourists during peak seasons, leading to decreased expenditures in this vital industry. Furthermore, climate change can exacerbate existing socio-economic inequalities within rural communities. Wealthier farmers may have the means to invest in adaptive technologies or alternative crops, while poorer farmers may struggle to survive under increasingly harsh conditions. This disparity can lead to greater migration from rural areas to urban centers as people seek better opportunities elsewhere, further straining urban resources.

In my analysis of the impact of climate change on Montenegro, I found compelling statistics from Monstat and Eurostat that highlight the urgency of this issue. According to Monstat, Montenegro's GDP in 2020 was approximately €4.186 billion, reflecting a decline from €4.951 billion in 2019, largely due to the economic disruptions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and exacerbated by climate-related challenges. Moreover, Eurostat data indicates that agriculture accounted for about 9.5% of Montenegro's GDP in 2014, underscoring the sector's importance to the national economy. With climate change projected to increase temperatures by up to 5.5°C by the end of the century and alter precipitation patterns, the agricultural sector is likely to face significant production challenges, which could further strain Montenegro's economic recovery and growth prospects. These statistics illustrate the critical need for strategic interventions to mitigate climate impacts and support sustainable agricultural practices in Montenegro.

ADAPTATION STRATEGIES

To mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on agriculture and the economy, I propose several robust adaptation strategies for Montenegro:

- **Improving Water Management:** Developing efficient irrigation systems can optimize water use during drought periods.
- **Diversifying Crops:** Encouraging farmers to diversify their crop production can reduce dependency on vulnerable crops like olives.
- **Investing in Research:** Supporting research initiatives focused on developing climate-resilient crop varieties is essential.
- **Promoting Sustainable Practices:** Implementing sustainable agricultural practices enhances soil health and reduces environmental impact.

Additionally, fostering collaboration among stakeholders—including government agencies, NGOs, and local communities—is critical for creating comprehensive policies that address climate change impacts holistically. Education and training programs can empower farmers with knowledge about sustainable practices and innovative technologies.

Conclusion

The interplay between climate change impacts on agriculture and economic stability in Montenegro underscores the urgent need for comprehensive strategies that address these challenges. By understanding the vulnerabilities within the agricultural sector and implementing adaptive measures, I believe that Montenegro can enhance its resilience against climate-related threats while safeguarding its economic future.

In conclusion, addressing climate change requires a concerted effort from all sectors of society. By prioritizing sustainable practices in agriculture and investing in adaptive technologies, Montenegro can not only protect its natural resources but also secure a stable economic future for its citizens.

Projected impacts of climate change on Montenegro's agriculture by 2030

The projected impacts of climate change on Montenegro's agriculture by 2030 are concerning, as the country is expected to experience more frequent and severe weather events. According to various reports, including those from the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Montenegro will likely face increased temperatures, reduced precipitation, and more extreme weather patterns such as droughts and heavy rainfall. Specifically, climate models suggest that if emissions continue to rise, the region will see longer heat waves and a decrease in overall annual precipitation, particularly during the summer months[1][2].

By 2030, average annual temperatures in Montenegro could rise by approximately 1.5°C to 2°C compared to historical averages, leading to significant changes in agricultural productivity. For instance, the agricultural sector may experience reduced yields for key crops like maize due to increased water demand and changes in growing conditions[3][4]. Additionally, the costs associated with irrigation are expected to rise as farmers adapt to these changes, further straining their economic viability. The average annual climate change damages due to reduced maize yields alone could escalate significantly if the livestock sector expands and relies on locally grown feed[1].

Moreover, the overall economic impact on agriculture is projected to be substantial. Reports indicate that increased irrigation costs could reach up to €4.41 million annually under certain climate scenarios, which would add financial pressure on farmers already grappling with changing weather patterns[1]. These challenges highlight the urgent need for adaptation strategies that can help mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on agriculture in Montenegro.

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The Impact of Climate Change on the Job Market – Threats and Opportunities

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Abstract: The Impact of Climate Change on the Job Market – Threats and Opportunities

We live in a time of constant change. Complex forces are transforming every aspect of our lives, including the way we work. Many factors affect how the job market functions, including climate change and urbanization. I will focus on the impact of climate change, which is one of the biggest challenges of today's civilization.

This study will define the terms that people encounter in everyday life but may not know their real meaning. It will demonstrate how climate change affects the job market, jobs, and resource scarcity.

Climate change has a significant impact on different areas of society, including the economy, environment, and social structures. The job market is particularly sensitive to these changes. The transition to a sustainable economy—an economic system that focuses on long-term development with minimal or no harm—will undoubtedly create challenges and new opportunities for the workforce worldwide. This paper will investigate and analyze the dual impact of climate change on the job market, including the opportunities that arise and the consequences they bring.

The simplest explanation is always the best place to start. Extreme weather conditions have a clear and significant impact on the economy, as evidenced by the damage caused by floods, hurricanes, and droughts. It is evident that such events can seriously threaten the economy, given the automatic loss of infrastructure and jobs that would result. In addition to direct losses, long-term effects can include reduced production, higher recovery costs, and decreased investor confidence. I will explain the negative aspects of climate change on the micro level, showing how these changes affect people's daily lives, their jobs, and local communities.

The transition to a green economy undoubtedly creates significant opportunities. Once more, investments in renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, and hydro power, will undoubtedly create new job markets and a need for new jobs. Furthermore, energy efficiency projects, such as renovating buildings or upgrading infrastructure, will create jobs in sectors focused on reducing carbon footprints. The development of sustainable technologies and the recycling industry undoubtedly contribute to the growth of green jobs. The construction and urban planning sectors are booming due to the increased demand for energy-efficient buildings and sustainable infrastructure. Training programs and education in green skills are the answer to helping workers move from declining industries to those offering new opportunities in the green economy.

As a Montenegrin student, I will dedicate a special part of this paper to analyzing these impacts on the country I come from. What are the impacts of climate change, how significant are they, and whether the job market in Montenegro shows more examples of threats or opportunities.

Keywords: climate change, job market, green economy, opportunities, threats, sustainable development.

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is one of the greatest challenges facing modern civilization, and its impact on the global economy is becoming increasingly evident and complex. Adapting to these changes is essential for the long-term sustainability of economic systems, and the labor market stands out as one of the most sensitive segments. Even small shifts in this area can have significant effects, depending on the geographic context and specific conditions.

When discussing economic opportunities and challenges, institutions, fiscal policies, economic freedoms, and man-made advances play a critical role. But while we can shape many aspects of our economy, there are forces beyond human control, and climate change is one of them. Addressing them requires proactive adaptation strategies, as previous analyses of the economic risks of inaction have shown [1].

In Montenegro, the saying "If you can't beat them, join them," often used as a lighthearted response to challenges or even joke, may have a deeper meaning in the context of natural change. Rather than fighting what cannot be changed, it is wiser to adapt and use these changes as opportunities for new development.

Climate change in the labor market can be seen as both, a threat and an opportunity. It is up to us to identify how this challenge can be used to create new business opportunities and improve existing working conditions, while taking into account the need to protect the environment.

THREATS AND OPPORTUNITIES

The impact of climate change on the labor market is significant and complex, affecting different industries in different ways. As environmental conditions continue to change, some sectors will experience direct impacts, while others will face more subtle but equally transformative changes. Recognizing both the threats and opportunities

presented by climate change is essential to understanding how the labor market can adapt and evolve.

The Threats of Climate Change to the Labor Market

Climate change poses significant threats to industries that depend on stable weather patterns and natural resources. Agriculture, for example, is one of the most vulnerable sectors, as changes in precipitation patterns, more frequent droughts, and higher temperatures reduce crop yields and overall productivity. As agricultural communities are often the backbone of rural economies, the loss of agricultural jobs can lead to increased unemployment in areas already facing economic challenges. A World Bank study points to the devastating effects of climate change on agricultural communities, particularly in developing countries where the sector is central to both the economy and employment [2].

Similarly, tourism-related industries are feeling the effects of climate change. Coastal areas, which attract millions of tourists each year, are increasingly threatened by rising sea levels and more frequent extreme weather events. These environmental changes can erode beaches, destroy infrastructure and make destinations less attractive, leading to job losses in hospitality, transportation and local services. In addition, disruptions to global supply chains caused by climate-related disasters increase job insecurity, particularly in sectors that rely on a steady flow of raw materials, such as manufacturing and retail [3].

In the context of Montenegro, these global threats are compounded by the country's dependence on agriculture and tourism as key sectors. For example, Montenegro's agricultural sector faces challenges from reduced water availability, increased droughts, and shifts in growing seasons, resulting in reduced agricultural production. Similarly, Montenegro's coastal regions, which are vital to the tourism industry, are at risk from rising sea levels and more frequent storms, which can undermine infrastructure and tourism facilities. As these industries struggle to adapt to these challenges, Montenegro's labor market could come under significant pressure.

Opportunities Created by Climate Change

While climate change presents significant risks, it also opens up new pathways for economic growth, particularly in industries focused on adaptation and mitigation. The renewable energy sector is one of the most promising areas for job creation. As the world shifts towards more eco-friendly energy sources, the demand for clean energy such as wind, solar, and hydroelectric power continues to grow. The expansion of these industries creates a wide range of job opportunities, from research and development to installation and maintenance, driving employment in previously underdeveloped regions [4].

Another sector benefiting from the shift towards sustainability is the construction industry, particularly through energy-efficient building projects and the renovation of existing structures to meet new environmental standards. The demand for eco-friendly infrastructure increases the need for architects, engineers, and workers in the construction industry specializing in sustainable building practices. As cities become more focused on sustainability, the urban planning sector also expands, with an emphasis on creating green spaces, improving public transportation, and developing smart cities. These initiatives not only contribute to environmental

preservation but also provide a foundation for long-term job creation.

Additionally, the recycling and waste management industries are flourishing. As governments and corporations strive to reduce their environmental footprint, there is an increasing focus on reducing waste, reusing materials, and recycling. These efforts are driving job creation in recycling plants, environmental consulting firms, and waste management services. As demand for green skills rises, educational programs focused on sustainable practices are emerging to help workers transition from traditional industries to the green economy [5].

Again, looking at the country I come from, we can see that the transition to a green economy brings many benefits. It helps the country reduce its dependence on fossil fuels, improve energy security, and reduce carbon emissions. By focusing on renewable energy sources such as solar, wind and hydropower, Montenegro can create new jobs and support local industries. In addition, sustainable construction and ecotourism are key areas for growth, allowing the country to protect its natural beauty and strengthen its economy. Montenegro is known for its natural landscapes, and this transition would provide an opportunity to create a more stable and environmentally friendly future.

INTEGRATION OF NATURE AND ECONOMY FOR SUCCESS IN THE LABOR MARKET

The greatest success in the labor market is achieved by integrating nature and the economy. True success lies in maximizing the use of natural resources without harming the environment. This balance between economic activity and environmental preservation forms the foundation of the green economy, which not only helps reduce the negative impact on the environment but also enables sustainable economic growth. In the green economy, resources are utilized in a way that minimizes harm to ecosystems, while simultaneously creating new business opportunities and jobs in industries that support sustainability, such as renewable energy, green construction, and ecological agriculture. This approach allows the economy to grow without depleting natural resources, providing long-term benefits for society and the environment.

Green Economy

The green economy is an economic model that has become a key response to the challenges posed by climate change. With its fundamental principles of sustainability, the green economy allows a shift from resource-intensive sectors to those that use renewable energy sources and reduce environmental harm. This model creates new jobs and business opportunities in industries such as renewable energy, energy-efficient construction, and recycling. The transition to a green economy reduces harmful emissions while also driving economic growth and reducing unemployment, especially in sectors that offer sustainable alternatives to traditional industries. Through the green economy, societies can achieve long-term benefits by preserving natural resources for future generations and ensuring stable economic growth.

In the economy, everything is connected. Everything influences everything else, without exception. For example,

when analyzing GDP, we must consider the supply and demand market, the size of the country, characteristics, and population, as well as the impact of natural resources on economic development. All these components make up the foundation for creating a stable economic environment. The same holds true for the labor market, which cannot function efficiently without alignment with the overall economic system. If the economy is too dependent on industries that harm the environment, this can lead to job losses in the future, while a shift to ecological sectors can create new jobs and allow for long-term unemployment reduction.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, climate change represents a profound challenge, but it also offers new opportunities for economic growth and transformation, particularly in the labor market. While the immediate risks to industries such as agriculture and tourism are undeniable, the transition to a green economy opens avenues for job creation and sustainable development. By investing in renewable energy, sustainable infrastructure, and the circular economy, we can mitigate some of the adverse effects of climate change, while driving innovation and creating new business opportunities.

Moreover, integrating environmental considerations into economic policy is critical for ensuring the long-term sustainability of economic systems. Emphasizing green jobs

and developing industries that prioritize sustainability will help build resilience in the labor market and reduce unemployment. Ultimately, the green economy offers a pathway for reconciling economic growth with environmental protection, ensuring that future generations can enjoy both a healthy planet and a stable, thriving economy.

By embracing these challenges as opportunities, we can shape a future where the labor market not only survives the effects of climate change but thrives by adapting to the new realities of a green, sustainable world.

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The potential and prospects of Montenegro in the context of a circular transition

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Abstract — The objective of this paper is to emphasize the significance of a circular economy and the necessity for a paradigm shift in our thinking. Contemporary society and the market are confronted with considerable challenges, including uncertainty, climate change and the scarcity of resources. In light of these challenges, a transformation in our economic and social systems is imperative. The circular economy has been identified as a potential solution to the aforementioned issues. The triple bottom line approach, which considers environmental, economic and social factors, has been proposed as a means of addressing these challenges. In the case of Montenegro, notable progress has been made towards a circular transition. Two principal documents have been published: the Road Map of Montenegro to a Circular Economy and the National Strategy for a Circular Transition until 2030, with an accompanying Action Plan for the period 2023-24. In this context, the aforementioned documents serve as the fundamental source material for the purposes of this paper. The objective of this paper is to present a comprehensive overview of the potential and prospects of MNE in this context.

Keywords—sustainability, circular transition, environment, uncertainty.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global landscape has been shaped by significant shifts and unpredictable occurrences in recent times. The Earth is undergoing transformations, and its resources are not as readily accessible as they once were. The occurrence of numerous recent global events has served to highlight the necessity for change.

The global population increased from 5.3 billion in 1990 to 8 billion in 2023, representing an approximate 50% growth. In consequence of these and numerous other developments in social structure, there has been a corresponding increase in GDP per capita over the years. In light of the prevailing circumstances, there has been a twofold increase in the consumption of goods and services by the general public.

GRAPHIC 1 – THE WORLD’S GDP PER CAPITA 1990-2023

The concept of sustainability emerged as a result of the necessity to manage scarce resources. The concept of sustainability is based on the 3P concept, otherwise known as the Triple Bottom Line, which encompasses the following three factors: planet, profit and people. This concept emphasizes the sustainability of ecosystems, economies and societies. The concept of circular economy offers a promising avenue for addressing this challenge. The principles of the circular economy are founded upon the 3P concept, with the sustainability of these factors being the primary objective. The adoption of circular business models enables companies to consider the negative effects of their activities and to identify creative alternatives.

The principle of corporate social responsibility (CSR) are aligned with those of the circular economy and the 3P concept. In this regard, a wide range of activities can be implemented in line with CSR practices when individual factors are taken into account (Coleman, et al., 2018).

In terms of environmental sustainability, there are number of key areas of consideration. These include recycling, the identification of alternative resources of energy, such as solar panels and wind turbines, the reduction of the use of natural resources and the transition to suppliers that demonstrate greater sustainability. A significant aspect of this process is the rethinking of product development from a perspective that encompasses the entire product life cycle, from initial stages of production to the final disposal of the product.

From an economic standpoint, the objective is to ensure the viability and profitability of the enterprise. It is imperative that CSR mechanisms, ethics and moral principles become integral to managerial thinking. The implementation of CSR practices has the potential to result in a reduction of costs in specific areas, the mitigation of risks, the acquisition of a competitive advantage, the development of a positive reputation and the enhancement of credibility within the industry. These actions collectively contribute to the profitability of the company.

In terms of social responsibility, the focus is on workplace balance, stress reduction, and the improvement of employees’ mental and physical health and well-being. These activities are predominately focused on human resources sector within the company.

II. CIRCULAR ECONOMY

The traditional (linear) economy places emphasis on consumption and production, with minimal consideration given to the disposal of products. The primary objective of a traditional economy is to maximize profit, with minimal consideration given to the fate of the used product.

The contemporary economic landscape is somewhat distinct, with the advent of the circular economy offering a novel approach to design, technology, innovation, and the overall business model.

The circular economy considers the utilization of resources, the production process, and the subsequent post-consumption phase. Accordingly, there is a reduced level of waste, and even used products can be put to further use. The field of environmental economics is concerned with the study of human decision-making processes and their impact on the natural environment, particularly in terms of resource utilization and environmental degradation.

The traditional linear economy is based on the exploitation of resources, with production, consumption and disposal forming a continuous cycle. Once a product has been consumed, its lifecycle is complete and it enters the waste stream, where it may persist indefinitely. The prevailing business paradigm has historically demonstrated a lack of concern for these issues. However, the operation of such businesses exerts considerable pressure on natural resources and generates a substantial amount of waste. Given the long-standing prevalence of such business practices, it became evident that a transformation was necessary. The linear economy has resulted in the extraction of 65 billion tons of resources on an annual basis, with only 7% of that amount being recycled. In light of the potential environmental threats, it is imperative that the global economy undergoes a transformation to reduce its impact on nature and its resources, and to minimize the accumulation of waste that is detrimental to the natural environment.

The advent of the new economic model prompted a shift in the way individuals approached economic activities and challenges. It was founded upon the tenets of a nascent, environmentally conscious economic system. The concept of the green economy is based on the idea of opportunity cost, whereby an alternative source is used instead of exerting significant pressure on natural resources. Subsequently, the pivotal stages are decision-making and the process of choice, which managers must undertake judiciously and efficiently in the interest of the company.

The fundamental tenet of the circular economy is predicated on the notion that the localization and circularization of material and energy flows serve to stabilize the utilization of natural resources. Consequently, sustainable development constitutes the fundamental basis of the circular economy. The concept of sustainability is based on and operationalized from its three dimensions, namely the environment, society, and the economy. This is also known as the Triple bottom line.

The circular economy has the potential to facilitate and advance sustainability, identifying suitable instruments for addressing all three dimensions of sustainability.

The circularity approach is the optimal methodology for enhancing sustainability performance. In light of the aforementioned, the circular economy is predicated on a few fundamental principles, including:

- Design out waste
- Build resilience through diversity
- Rely on energy from renewable sources

- Think in "systems"
- Waste is food.

The beginning of the 21st century marked a pivotal moment in the history of natural resources, with prices beginning to exhibit a notable increase. It thus became apparent that the conventional approach was liable to result in scarcity, volatility and pricing instability, risk and supply disruptions.

It was therefore necessary to implement changes to improve and develop the way in which business was functioning. The circular economy is predicated on the design of products that are readily reusable, disassemblable, refurbishable, or recyclable. A circular economy places significant emphasis on the role of labor in business operations, thereby exerting less pressure on natural resources and the environment.

A circular economy addresses the monitoring of resource-related challenges for businesses and economies, and has the potential to generate growth, create employment opportunities and reduce environmental impacts, including carbon emissions. It is imperative to conceptualize a circular economy as a business model, rather than merely a modus operandi for contemporary business and small-to-medium-sized enterprises. Such an approach will encourage innovative thinking and the generation of unconventional ideas, with the potential to transform the global economic landscape.

III. STRATEGIC FRAMEWORKS FOR IMPLEMENTING A CIRCULAR ECONOMY ON A GLOBAL SCALE

The objective of CE is to develop a more intelligent and effective utilization of natural resources through the implementation of recycling and recovery strategies. This is achieved by minimizing the environmental, health and energy costs associated with the extraction and processing of these resources.

It has been acknowledged by European countries that there is a necessity to implement a strategic framework in order to facilitate the transition towards a circular economy. The primary objective of this framework is to define the key objectives, activities and actions that are required to achieve this goal.

GRAPHIC 2 – EU COUNTRIES THAT ADOPTED CE STRATEGIES

The 2015 *Paris Agreement on Climate Change* represents the most significant global strategy document to date in the effort to reduce climate change. It commits member

countries to limit global warming to 1.5°C above the pre-industrial level.

The World Economic Forum (WEF) and the **Platform for Accelerating the Circular Economy (PACE)** - PACE is a WEF initiative that focuses on the development of public-private partnerships to support circular initiatives in various sectors, including electronics, textiles, and construction. Furthermore, the WEF advocates the transition to circular models through the dissemination of annual reports and the implementation of global initiatives.

The Global Circular Economy Network (GCE Network) is an initiative that unites research organizations, governments and companies with the objective of sharing best practices and knowledge pertaining to the implementation of the circular economy in diverse sectors and regions.

The United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) has established a **Global Circular Economy Initiative**, which is tasked with developing strategies and guidelines for implementing a circular economy, particularly in developing countries. The initiative encompasses a range of projects that facilitate the development of circular supply chains, promote the sustainable utilization of resources and encourage the reduction of waste on a global scale.

The Ellen MacArthur Foundation is a preeminent global organization dedicated to the advancement of the circular economy through research, collaboration, and innovation. It was established in 2010 and has become a pivotal force in the evolution and dissemination of circular economy principles.

The Agri-Circular Coalition represents a collaborative endeavor uniting farmers, commercial entities and institutional bodies with the objective of advancing the implementation of the circular economy in agricultural contexts. The objective is to enhance sustainability in the agricultural sector through the implementation of innovative approaches to resource and waste management.

The European Green Deal represents a strategy for achieving a sustainable economy for the European Union. It entails the transformation of climate and environmental challenges into opportunities across all policy areas, while ensuring a just and inclusive transition. The plan proposes that Europe will become the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. The European Green Deal encompasses all economic sectors, notably including transport, energy, agriculture, maintenance and construction, as well as industrial sectors such as steel, cement, textiles and chemicals.

In its **"Fit for 55" proposal**, the European Commission set forth a plan to achieve the reduction targets outlined in the European Commission on 14th of July, 2021. The legislative package presents five new initiatives in different policy areas, including climate, energy and fuels, transport, buildings, land use and forestry. The latest climate target and the "Fit for 55" packages represent pivotal elements of the European Union's comprehensive green growth strategy, formally known as the European Green Deal.

The European Union's industrial strategy is designed to facilitate the modernization of European industry, with the objective of enhancing its resilience, digital capabilities and

environmental sustainability. The objective of the strategy is for EU industry to spearhead the global transition to green and digital technologies, including the reduction of the environmental footprint, the enhancement of energy efficiency and the adaptation of business models to align with emerging standards of sustainability.

The Circular Economy Action Plan, as part of the European Green Deal, is oriented towards the transition towards a more sustainable, circular model of the economy, in which resources are efficiently utilized and waste is reduced. The objective of the plan is to prolong the lifespan of the product, promote recycling and mitigate the detrimental impact on the environment. The action plan comprises a number of pivotal areas and delineates the requisite steps for the fulfilment of all the plans' stated objectives.

IV. STRATEGIC FRAMEWORKS OF MONTENEGRO

With regard to Montenegro, the circular economy offers a variety of potential avenues for implementation or utilization. Given the abundance of natural resources and favorable climate, the scarcity of resources represents a significant challenge for the country.

It is of the utmost importance to recognize the necessity to safeguard the existing resources and to optimize their utilization, with the objective of minimizing any adverse effects.

The economy of Montenegro is predominantly service-based, with services accounting for 60% of GDP, as opposed to products produced domestically. In addition to the tourism industry, small and medium-sized enterprises represent a further area of strength for Montenegro.

The current economic model in Montenegro is based on a linear management structure. In order to align its business management practices with global trends, Montenegro must consider and implement a circular economy. In a circular economy, the discovery of multiple value creation mechanisms occurs concurrently with the consumption and depletion of finite resources. Consequently, the objective is to ensure that products, components and materials remain in the highest possible state of utility and value over time. A technical cycle is distinguished from a biological cycle, which coexists with it.

Montenegro, a small country with a service-oriented economy, has numerous potential avenues for the implementation of a circular economy. The most challenging aspect of this process is the establishment of regulations and the definition of clear objectives.

The Chamber of Commerce of Montenegro introduced the subject to the wider public through its publication, entitled **"Roadmap towards a circular economy in Montenegro"**.

The roadmap is based on a systematic approach and acknowledges that the transition process will require a significant investment of time and effort. The primary objectives of the roadmap are to ascertain the potential of Montenegro, its stakeholders, and the prospects for implementing a circular economy, with the ultimate aim of enhancing the quality of life of the Montenegrin population. This initiative and transition are illustrative of the circular economy approach espoused by the Ellen

MacArthur Foundation, which has enabled organizations to contribute to the development of a roadmap that represents an efficacious strategic plan for a circular economy in Montenegro.

The second document, which is of pivotal importance for any subsequent change or action taken in this manner, is *the National Strategy for a Circular Transition until 2030, with an accompanying Action Plan for the period 2023-24*.

Once again, the strategy document has been created in alignment with the concept of a Triple Bottom Line. It emphasizes the interdependence of economic, environmental, and social development, as well as the necessary activities and actions for ensuring long-term sustainability.

A variety of activities must be completed in the future, but the primary sectors identified as requiring priority attention are tourism, agriculture, construction, and forestry.

In each of the aforementioned sectors, comprehensive instructions are provided regarding the implementation of changes. Many of these actions are employed globally. The majority of them have yielded favorable outcomes, and it is anticipated that this will also be the case in Montenegro.

The following lines will present a summary of the main potential and prospects of Montenegro in general, based on the aforementioned documents.

The Constitution of Montenegro defines the country as an ecological state. As previously stated, the nation is endowed with a wealth of natural resources that serve to enhance its natural beauty. Consequently, it frequently emerges as a highly alluring tourist destination on a global scale. It is therefore imperative to ensure the preservation of these natural resources and treasures, guaranteeing their longevity and sustainable utilization.

As a prospective member state of the European Union and a developing country, Montenegro is eligible to benefit from all the funds and opportunities available to EU member states. This advantage allows for a variety of actions to be financed by foreign funds. The implementation of the circular economy and associated practices in priority or other sectors, supported by foreign funding, will have a beneficial impact on Montenegro's brand image abroad.

Another notable benefit is the collaboration between academic institutions, industry, and other organizations. Given its relatively modest size, it is of paramount importance for the country to foster a culture of mutual cooperation and unified efforts. In the context of the circular economy and circular systems of operation, it is notable that a number of smaller companies in Montenegro have already adopted this principle. Nevertheless, the principal challenge thus far has been the absence of recognition of this system. The implementation of strategies such as the Smart Specialization Strategy (S3 areas) in Montenegro serves to reinforce the recognition and importance of the circular economy within the country. The convergence of all public policies, individual and collective actions, facilitates the adoption of innovations and a distinctive mode of thinking, particularly in the context of the circular economy.

Conversely, the disadvantages include a significant reliance on imported resources, the decline of rural communities, unregulated deforestation, accelerated urbanisation (particularly in coastal regions), inadequate appreciation of the ecological value of natural resources, and a deficiency in infrastructure for waste management and recycling.

In terms of Montenegro's potential, the rising interest in eco-tourism presents a promising opportunity for the country. As previously indicated, the Smart Specialization Strategy prioritizes tourism. Montenegro has the ability to establish itself as a country that promotes and implements green practices in a sector that accounts for a considerable amount of the total GDP. Montenegro may do more than it now does by improving this industry, while simultaneously lowering negative emissions and the sector's detrimental consequences, which, in turn, contribute considerably to waste and environmental damage.

It can be argued that the most significant opportunity for Montenegro in terms of facilitating the circular transition is the global trend of a "return to nature". The increased demand for local and organic products will provide Montenegro's economy with growth, as well as the development of currently neglected sectors. Purchasing domestic products contributes to the promotion of Montenegro and its position in the international market. Furthermore, the opportunity presented by eco-certification of domestic products will positively impact the export of local goods and their use (demand) beyond the borders of Montenegro.

The Elektroprivreda of Montenegro has already identified this opportunity and initiated its implementation, namely the promotion of the use of renewable resources. In light of the favorable climatic conditions and the considerable number of sunny days experienced throughout the year in Montenegro, the installation of solar panels represents an optimal alternative to conventional electricity generation. Furthermore, hydroelectric plants and wind turbines can be highly efficient energy sources, with significantly reduced harmful emissions during operation and production. Once more, the most significant aspect of this opportunity is the favorable climatic conditions that Montenegro enjoys.

Finally, we consider the impact of digitalization. The implementation of digitalization can significantly influence the efficiency of a company, as well as its emissions of harmful gases and impact on scarce natural resources. In particular, the global pandemic (2020-2021) has highlighted the crucial role of digitalization and the significance of online markets. Furthermore, digitalization has a beneficial effect on the accessibility of companies to different markets and also contributes significantly to a reduction in business costs.

V. SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The circular economy can be defined as a system in which resources are kept in circulation for as long as possible, with the aim of reducing waste and promoting sustainability. The objective of this paper is to introduce the fundamental strategic concepts that form the basis for a circular transition. This paper presents a case study of

Montenegro, offering insights into the potential and prospects for a circular transition in the country.

However, the aforementioned scenarios are contingent upon the willingness of all parties to embrace change. As has been previously indicated on numerous occasions, the circular economy presents a plethora of potential avenues for consideration. The aforementioned alternatives can be attributed to a shift in perspective, approach to problem-solving, and business practices.

In the case of Montenegro, the private sector, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), plays a pivotal role in driving change. In light of the fact that a significant proportion of the population is unaware of the full range of possibilities available to them, it is of paramount importance to provide comprehensive educational initiatives that disseminate knowledge to all members of society, including students.

The transition to a circular economy will have a beneficial impact on economic, environmental and social outcomes. The implementation of this approach at all levels of society will contribute to an improved quality of life.

Future research in this field should provide a more comprehensive account of the existing literature. Additionally, further studies could enhance existing strategies by offering new insights and perspectives.

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Utilization of Anomaly Detection Techniques for Soil Salinity in the Context of Climate Change Challenges: An Overview

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Abstract—This review explores the application of anomaly detection techniques to address soil salinity, a significant environmental concern exacerbated by climate change. Soil salinity poses a critical threat to agricultural productivity and ecosystem stability worldwide. As climate change progresses, traditional methods of monitoring soil health may not suffice, necessitating advanced approaches like anomaly detection. This paper provides an overview of various anomaly detection methods, including statistical, machine learning, and deep learning techniques, and their efficacy in identifying unusual patterns in soil salinity data that indicate potential risks. In addition, it is discussed to integrate this technique with remote sensing and Internet of Things(IoT) technologies to increase real-time, precise monitoring capabilities. The results obtained from these studies will enable the introduction of soil salinity status into anomaly detection to prevent sustainable soil salinity.

Index Terms—Anomaly detection, Soil salinity, Climate change, Real-time monitoring

I. INTRODUCTION

Soil salinity refers to the concentration of soluble salts in the soil, which can significantly impact agricultural productivity and environmental health [1]. It is a result of both natural processes, such as weathering and evaporation, and human activities, including irrigation practices that do not adequately manage water and salt levels. Salinity can lead to various detrimental effects on crops, such as reduced water uptake, nutrient deficiencies, and ultimately lower yields [2], [3].

Soil salinity is a significant environmental challenge, escalating globally due to climate change, posing threats to agriculture, ecosystems [4], and food security [5]. Changing climate conditions, particularly global warming and increased aridity will contribute to the salinization of soils [6]. The exacerbation of soil salinization, driven by shifts in rainfall patterns, increased evapotranspiration [7], and rising sea levels [8], underscores the urgent need for innovative and effective monitoring strategies. The objective of this overview is to compile and analyze scholarly articles that employ anomaly detection techniques to address soil salinity challenges in the context of climate change.

Based on the manuscript written by Dunning et al. [9] anomaly detection defined "Anomaly detection is the process of finding unusual or unexpected patterns in data using machine learning techniques." Anomaly detection is a branch

of data mining and machine learning, which focuses on identifying outliers or deviations from standard patterns within datasets. Anomaly detection is also referred to as outlier detection or fault detection in various scholarly literature. In the context of soil salinity and climate change, these techniques offer unprecedented potential for early detection, continuous monitoring, and informed decision-making. By analyzing spatial and temporal variations in soil properties, anomaly detection can help pinpoint areas experiencing accelerated salinization, enabling targeted interventions and mitigation strategies.

This overview explores the literature with the challenges and opportunities in applying anomaly detection techniques to monitor and manage soil salinity under the dynamic influences of climate change. It examines the methodological frameworks, technological advancements, and practical applications that underpin the successful implementation of these techniques. Furthermore, it highlights the multifaceted nature of the problem, encompassing not only technical challenges but also the socio-economic and policy dimensions that are crucial for sustaining soil health and agricultural productivity [10] in a changing climate.

By shedding light on these aspects, this overview aims to foster a comprehensive understanding of how anomaly detection can serve as a critical tool in combating soil salinity, thus contributing to more resilient and sustainable agricultural systems in the face of climate change.

II. RELATED RESEARCH

In this section the related research papers on the Utilization of Anomaly Detection Techniques for Soil Salinity in the Context of Climate Change is investigated. Search was done based on keywords, synonyms and alternate words in the study questions described in the table 1.

Anomalies in soil salinity due to climate change can be defined by:

- 1) Increased salinity from rising sea levels and saltwater intrusion [11]
- 2) Enhanced salinity fluctuations due to irregular rainfall patterns [8].

General Terms	Terminologies
Anomaly detection	Anomaly detection soil salinity, Machine learning soil salinity, Remote sensing soil salinity detection
Soil Salinity	Soil health, Agriculture productivity soil salinity, Environmental sensors for soil management, Technological solutions for soil salinity
Climate Change	Climate change soil salinity monitoring, Climate adaptation soil management strategies, soil health climate change

TABLE I
TERMS DERIVED BASED ON SYNONYM WORDS

- 3) Intensified soil salinization from higher evaporation rates in warmer temperatures [12].
- 4) Altered salinity distribution linked to changing climate zones [13], [14].

These conditions underscore shifts in soil salinity directly influenced by climate change dynamics, necessitating adaptive management strategies.

Soil Salinity can be categorized as primary and secondary salinization in the research [15] and demonstrated in table 1. Climate change has an impact on both areas of Salinization.

Soil Salinity	
Primary Salinization	Secondary Salinization
Arid and semiarid areas	Agricultural areas
Natural Processes like weathering Inadequate rainfall and drainage prevent salts from leaching away from plant roots	Human intervention low rainfall poor quality, of irrigation water with no adequate provision of drainage for leaching and removal of salts

TABLE II
TABLE OF PRIMARY AND SECONDARY SALINIZATION

Several studies have been investigated, each containing comprehensive research focused on the application of anomaly detection techniques to soil salinity issues arising from climate change.

- This study [16] investigated Remote sensing(RS) techniques to monitor and map soil salinity [17], particularly in arid and semi-arid regions. The different salinity categories have been mapped by using various soil salinity indicators for a portion of the Al-Diwaniyah Governorate. The combining of these remote-sensing parameters into a single model explained 75.29 percent of the spatial changes in soil salinity there in the study area. Data is collected from The Landsat 8 satellite's Operational Land Imager (OLI) sensor, obtained in 2021 from USGS Earth Explorer.
- Gojiya [15] classifies comprehensive remote sensing and Geographic Information System(GIS) techniques, that are effective for monitoring and assessing soil salinity, which is a pressing global issue exacerbated by climate change.

- In the research conducted by Castillo-Villamor et al. [18], the Earth Observation-based Anomaly Detection (EOAD) system uses satellite imagery and anomaly detection to identify in-field anomalies that are associated with decreased crop yields.
- This paper [19] presents an innovative low-cost irrigation system that uses deep learning techniques to detect anomalies in soil moisture, air temperature, and air humidity data.
- The paper written by Moso et al. [20] proposes an anomaly detection method for smart agriculture data streams to identify issues with farm productivity and efficiency.
- In the study by Oymatov et al. [21], The study area's satellite images for the years 2012 and 2022 were obtained from open sources, specifically the Landsat OLI 8, which is after the vegetation period when the peak salinity level of arable land occurs. The findings of this study will help to understand the distribution of soil salinity in the study area and provide insights for decision-making processes connected to sustainable land management.
- Satellite-based remote sensing techniques, including the normalized differential salinity index (NDSI), can be used to detect and quantify soil salinity and associated ions according to the research [22].

III. METHODOLOGY

Several methods have been employed in various research studies on this topic. The majority of these approaches share common characteristics that can be generalized based on specific criteria.

Data Collection

RS, GIS and Modelling have become the preferred technological tools to map soil salinity due to large areas. Data for soil salinity detection can be primarily found through various methodologies that integrate remote sensing, machine learning, and field sampling. Here are the main sources and methods utilized in the detection of soil salinity:

1) Remote Sensing Data

a) Satellite Imagery:

Remote sensing [23] techniques utilize satellite data from sources such as Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 [24], and MODIS [25] to estimate soil salinity. These satellites provide multi-spectral images that can be analyzed to derive salinity indices.

b) Integration of Active and Passive Sensors [26]:

Studies have demonstrated that merging data from active sensors such as radar and passive sensors like optical imagery improves the precision of soil salinity forecasts. This combined method enables a more thorough evaluation of soil conditions.

2) Machine Learning(ML) Techniques [27]

Modeling Approaches are Machine learning algorithms, including Random Forests, Support Vector Machines, and Neural Networks which are employed to analyze

remote sensing data and predict soil salinity. These models utilize training datasets derived from ground truth measurements to improve prediction accuracy. For example, machine learning has been applied to MODIS Terra data to classify soil types and assess salinity levels effectively.

3) **Field Sampling and Ground Truthing [28]**

Soil Sampling: Ground-based soil sampling remains a critical method for validating remote sensing data. Electrical conductivity (EC) measurements taken from soil samples provide essential ground truth data that inform the accuracy of remote sensing predictions [29]. The World Soil Information System (WoSIS) compiles extensive geo-referenced soil profile samples globally, which serve as a valuable resource for researchers [30]

4) **Climate Data Integration [31]**

Climatic Variables: Integrating climatic data such as temperature and precipitation with soil salinity measurements helps in understanding the effects of climate change on salinization processes. Studies have analyzed trends over decades to assess how changing climate patterns influence soil salinity dynamics.

The combination of remote sensing technologies, machine learning algorithms, field sampling, and climate data integration provides a robust framework for detecting and monitoring soil salinity. These methodologies enable researchers to obtain accurate and high-resolution data essential for managing agricultural productivity in the face of climate change impacts.

IV. RESULTS

As a result, several scholarly papers have been thoroughly examined. Predominantly, these studies perform analyses based on historical datasets comprising satellite imagery to identify anomalies. Additionally, anomalies related to soil salinity are defined and examined in the context of climate changes. Upon reviewing the literature, it becomes evident that utilizing real-time datasets gathered through remote sensing is essential for the early detection of outliers. This approach provides numerous advantages, including heightened predictive precision, optimized agricultural practices, and more informed strategies for environmental management.

The benefits of using real-time anomaly detection in soil salinity include:

- **Early Intervention:** Enables timely identification and mitigation of soil salinity issues, preventing damage to crops and ecosystems.
- **Improved Water Management:** Supports more effective irrigation practices by monitoring salinity levels, promoting sustainable water use
- **Enhanced Crop Productivity:** Helps maintain optimal soil conditions for better yields and higher quality agricultural produce.
- **Climate Change Adaptation:** Assists in adjusting agricultural practices in response to changing environmental conditions affecting soil health.

- **Cost Savings:** Reduces potential financial losses by preventing crop failure and land degradation due to salinity imbalances.

In overall the anomaly detection aids in sustainable agricultural management through proactive soil salinity regulation.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In conclusion, this review underscores the significance of integrating advanced anomaly detection techniques to address the escalating challenge of soil salinity intensified by climate change. Given the increasing threat to agricultural productivity and ecological stability, traditional soil health monitoring methods are proving inadequate. This paper highlights the potential of methods such as statistical analysis, machine learning, and deep learning to effectively identify abnormal patterns in soil salinity data, which are indicative of looming risks. Moreover, the integration of these techniques with innovative technologies such as remote sensing and IoT [32] is beneficial as a route to enhance real-time and precision monitoring capabilities. An overview of the various studies suggests that employing anomaly detection not only helps in real-time assessment of soil conditions but also facilitates the implementation of preventive measures to manage soil salinity sustainably. As the world moves towards more technologically advanced agricultural practices, embracing such robust anomaly detection frameworks will be crucial in mitigating the adverse effects of climate change on soil health and ensuring the resilience of agricultural ecosystems. Future research on anomaly detection in soil salinity via remote sensing should focus on developing advanced predictive models, refining real-time data processing techniques, and integrating climate adaptation factors.

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MONTEVITIS

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Session 2

Stochastic processes

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Primjena stohastičkih procesa na opšti proces rađanja i umiranja

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Sažetak—Rad izučava primjenu stohastičkih procesa na opšti proces rađanja i umiranja. Opšti proces rađanja i umiranja se ne može objasniti bez prisustva vjerovatnoće pa rad daje kratak uvod u teoriju vjerovatnoće, prostor vjerovatnoće, slučajnu promjenljivu, matematičko očekivanje, varijansu i standardnu devijaciju. Kako se rad zasniva na primjeni stohastičkih procesa na opšti proces rađanja i umiranja, upoznat će sa definicijom i osobinama stohastičkih procesa.

Sam proces rađanja i umiranja se prikazuje kao Markov lanac pa rad obuhvata opštu teoriju Markov-ih lanaca. Prikazuje šta su zapravo Markovi lanci, njihovu definiciju i matricu prelaza. Definiše Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine zbog njihove primjene u opšti proces rađanja i umiranja, proces rađanja i proces smrti.

Opšti proces rađanja i umiranja analiziran preko vjerovatnoća prelaza, diferencijalnih jednačina Kolmogorov i matrice prelaza. Proces rađanja prikazuje kroz tri pretpostavke, koje se koriste za razmatranje promjene obima populacije tokom procesa rađanja. Proces umiranja razmatra kroz linearan proces umiranja rešavanjem Kolmogorov-ih diferencijalnih jednačina. Zatim je dat Malthusov model rasta populacije koji je matematički prikazan kroz rešavanje diferencijalnih jednačina metodom razdvojenih promjenljivih.

Ključne riječi: stohastički proces, Markov lanac, Kolmogorov, proces rađanja-umiranja

I. UVOD

Stohastički procesi predstavljaju prvi korak ka definisanju opšteg procesa rađanja i umiranja. Kreiranju matematičkog modela koji objašnjava kako proces rađanja i umiranja utiče na obim populacije. Stohastički procesi izučavaju slučajne događaje, a kako se rađanje i umiranje ne može predvidjeti sa određenom sigurnošću tada predstavljaju idealne događaje za izučavanje, odnosno stohastički procesi pronalaze primjenu u procesu rađanja i umiranja.

Izučavanje primjene stohastičkih procesa na opšti proces rađanja i umiranja započinje od saznanja primjene diferencijalnih jednačina na pojednostavljenom epidemiološkom modelu. Jednačine koje se primjenjuju da bi se predvidjela ponašanja prirodnih procesa u različitim okolnostima. Saznanje koje dovodi do procesa rađanja i umiranja i primjene stohastičkih procesa na isti služeći se stohastičkim diferencijalnim jednačinama, odnosno unaprijed Kolmogorov-im diferencijalnim jednačinama. Rad nastaje iz želje da se dođe do konkretne primjene stohastičkih procesa u svijetu koji nas okružuje, uvid kako matematička struktura definiše, prikazuje procese koji se

svakodnevno odvijaju slučajno, nepredvidljivo.

Stohastički procesi imaju glavnu ulogu u evolutivnoj teoriji zaključivanja. Modeli kao dio evolutivnih promjena, koji uključuju neku slučajnost su poželjni iz dva razloga. Prvi razlog su promjene koje proizilaze iz složenih procesa da se mogu suštinski smatrati stohastičkim. Drugi razlog jeste taj što stohastički modeli predstavljaju sredstvo istraživačima da formiraju hipoteze o evolutivnim promjenama.

Pozadina toga je proces rađanja i umiranja koji se predstavlja Markov-im lancem sa neprekidnim vremenom koji modelira broj jedinki u populaciji, pri čemu svaka jedinka može *roditi* novu jedinku ili *umrijeti*. Proces rađanja i umiranja ne prati porijeklo jedinki, nego broj jedinki u populaciji. Stopa nataliteta i mortaliteta zavisi od veličine populacije.

Opšti proces rađanja i umiranja je bitan jer se može primijeniti na druge diskretne sisteme, u kojima je bitan broj *jedinki*. Smatra se bitnim alatom jer svoju primjenu pronalazi u evolutivnoj teoriji, populacionoj biologiji, genetici i ekologiji. Koristi se u proučavanju dinamike zaraznih bolesti, gdje broj zaraženih *jedinki* predstavlja populaciju od interesa. Učestvuje u modelovanju populacija organizama koji žive u okruženjima sa ograničenim resursima. Detaljno opisano u radu [4].

Na početku rad uvodi u osnove teorije vjerovatnoće kako bi se dala osnova za bolje razumijevanje teme koju istražuje. Zatim govori o stohastičkim procesima, njihovom nastanku, primjeni i kako jedan stohastički model funkcioniše, definisanju stohastičkog procesa. Nakon toga slijedi prikaz Markov-og lanca, definicija i matrica prelaza. Takođe definiše Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine zbog njihove primjene u opštem procesu rađanja i umiranja, procesu rađanja i procesu umiranja.

Razradu rada čini prikaz stohastičkog modelovanja opšteg procesa rađanja i umiranja, gdje se jasno vidi tok računa iz kojeg se dobijaju generatorne matrice, a na osnovu njih i matrice prelaza. Zatim govori o procesu rađanja kroz tri pretpostavke, gdje na kraju dolazi do rešenja u obliku negativne binomne raspodjele. Nakon procesa rađanja slijedi proces umiranja gdje su prikazane Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine čijim rešavanjem dolazi do binomne raspodjele. Prikazuje Malthusov model rasta populacije koji se smatra za temeljem nastanka svih ostalih modela populacije.

II. PREGLED TEORIJE VJEROVATNOĆE

Matematičku teoriju stohastičkog modela čine stohastički procesi. Teorija stohastičkih procesa se zasniva na teoriji vjerovatnoće. Zato je od velike važnosti dati pregled osnovnih pojmova teorije vjerovatnoće. Neka je Ω skup svih mogućih ishoda eksperimenta, odnosno skup svih elementarnih događaja. Elementi skupa Ω se nazivaju elementarnim događajima i označavaju se sa ω .

$$\Omega = \{\omega \mid \omega \text{ je elementaran događaj}\}$$

Definicija 2.1: Slučajan događaj A je podskup svih elementarnih događaja Ω . On se sastoji od elementarnih događaja ω koji imaju svojstvo kojim se događaj A definiše.

Definicija 2.1 preuzeta iz rada [8].

Neki se događaj A realizovao ako su realizovani elementarni ishodi ω koji pripadaju skupu A . Skup Ω je siguran događaj jer sadrži sve moguće realizacije eksperimenta. Prazan skup \emptyset je nemoguć događaj jer se on nikada ne može realizovati, na osnovu rada [8].

Primjer 1: Baca se novčić i zabilježi svaki put bilo da se pojavi pismo ili glava.

Oznaka za pismo je P , a za glavu G . Skup svih mogućih ishoda je $\Omega = \{P, G\}$, a elementarni događaji su P i G . Događaji mogu biti $\{P\}$, $\{G\}$, $\{P, G\}$ ili \emptyset . Ako je novčić balansiran vjerovatnoća da će pasti glava je $\frac{1}{2}$, vjerovatnoća da će pasti pismo je $\frac{1}{2}$, a vjerovatnoća ostalih događaja je 0. Primjer dat na osnovu knjige [1].

Definicija 2.2: Neka je P funkcija definisana na kolekciji podskupova skupa Ω . Funkcija $P : S \rightarrow [0, 1]$ naziva se vjerovatnoćom ako važe sledeća svojstva:

- 1) $P(\Omega) = 1$.
- 2) $0 \leq P(A) \leq 1, A \subset \Omega$.
- 3) Ako $A_i \cap A_j \neq \emptyset$, za $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, i \neq j$, gdje $A_i \subset \Omega$, tada $P(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} P(A_i)$.

Definicija 2.2 data na osnovu knjige [1].

Definicija 2.3 (Uslovna vjerovatnoća): Neka su A_1 i A_2 dva događaja definisana na skupu Ω . Vjerovatnoća da se realizuje događaja A_1 pod uslovom da se realizovao događaj A_2 , u oznaci $P(A_1/A_2)$, se naziva uslovna vjerovatnoća i definiše se kao

$$P(A_1/A_2) = \frac{P(A_1 A_2)}{P(A_2)},$$

gdje je $P(A_2) > 0$. Analogno, uslovna vjerovatnoća događaja A_2 ako događaj A_1 je

$$P(A_2/A_1) = \frac{P(A_1 A_2)}{P(A_1)},$$

gdje je $P(A_1) > 0$.

Definicija 2.3 data na osnovu knjige [1].

Definicija 2.4: Neka je F funkcija raspodjele slučajne promjenljive X definisane na skupu realnih brojeva R sa vrijednostima $[0, 1]$, $F : R \rightarrow [0, 1]$, zadovoljava:

$$F(X) = P_X((-\infty, x]).$$

Može se pokazati da je funkcija F monotono neopadajuća, neprekidna s desna u svakoj tački $x \in R$ i zadovoljava

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} F(x) = F(-\infty) = 0 \text{ i } \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} F(x) = 1.$$

Definicija 2.4 definisana po knjizi [1].

Definicija 2.5: Neka je X neprekidna slučajna promjenljiva sa funkcijom raspodjele F . Ako postoji nenegativna, integrabilna funkcija f , $f : R \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, tako da važi

$$F(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x f(t) dt,$$

tada za f kažemo da je funkcija gustine vjerovatnoće slučajne promjenljive X . Gustina vjerovatnoće neprekidne slučajne promjenljive X se može koristiti da se izračuna vjerovatnoća nekog događaja. Neka je A prostor od X i $B \subset A$ događaj. Tada

$$P_X(X \in A) = \int_A f(x) dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) dx = 1.$$

i

$$P_X(X \in B) = \int_B f(x) dx.$$

Posebno,

$$P_X(a \leq X \leq b) = \int_a^b f(x) dx = F(b) - F(a).$$

Definicija 2.5 preuzeta iz knjige [1].

Definicija 2.6 (Matematičko očekivanje): Matematičko očekivanje $E(X)$ slučajne promjenljive X je broj definisan sa:

- $E(X) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} x_k P(X = x_k)$, gdje je X diskretna slučajna promjenljiva.
- $E(X) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} x f(x) dx$, gdje je X neprekidna slučajna promjenljiva.

Pod uslovom da odgovarajući red, odnosno integral apsolutno konvergira.

Definicija 2.6 definisana na osnovu knjige [6].

Definicija 2.7 (Varijansa): Varijansa $D(X)$ slučajne promjenljive X je definisana sa

$$D(X) = E((X - E(X))^2).$$

Često se za nalaženje varijanse koristi izraz

$$D(X) = E(X^2) - E^2(X).$$

Standardnom devijacijom naziva se kvadratni korijen varijanse slučajne promjenljive X .

$$\sigma(X) = \sqrt{D(X)}.$$

Definicija 2.7 definisana na osnovu knjige [6].

A. Funkcije raspodjele

Funkcije raspodjele preuzete iz knjige [6].

- Binomna raspodjela $B(n, p)$

$$P(X = k) = \binom{n}{k} p^k (1-p)^{n-k}, k = 0, \dots, n$$

$$E(X) = np, \text{ Var}(X) = np(1-p),$$

$$h(t) = (1-p + pe^{it})^n,$$

gdje je n cio pozitivan broj, $0 < p < 1$, pri čemu je p vjerovatnoća uspjeha, a $1-p$ vjerovatnoća neuspjeha.

- Negativna binomna

$$P(X = k) = \binom{k-1}{r-1} p^r (1-p)^{k-r}, k = r, r+1, \dots$$

$$E(X) = \frac{r}{p}, \text{ Var}(X) = \frac{r(1-p)}{p^2},$$

$$h(t) = \left(\frac{pe^{it}}{1 - (1-p)e^{it}} \right)^r,$$

Predstavlja broj neuspjelih realizacija eksperimenta dok se nije desilo r uspjeha, pri čemu su r i p realni parametri, $r, p > 0$ i $p \in [0, 1]$.

III. UVOD U STOHAŠTIČKE PROCESSE

U ovom poglavlju rad govori uopšteno o stohastičkim procesima, njihovom razvoju, primjeni. Zatim daje kratak pregled teorije o Markov-im lanacima. Definiše osnovne definicije Markov-og lanac, matricu prelaza i Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine.

Tokom prošlog vijeka fizika se bavila proučavanjem procesa i pojava promjenljivih sa protokom vremena. Kako teorija vjerovatnoće nije imala metodologiju za proučavanje takvih pojava dolazi do pojave opšte teorije stohastičkih procesa koji razmatraju slučajne promjenjive, koje zavise od jednog ili više parametara koji se neprekidno mijenjaju. Pojam stohastičkog procesa su uveli Kolmogorov, Slucki, Wiener, Khinchin i Cramer.

Nakon aksiomatske teorije Kolmogorov-a postoje nekoliko pokušaja proučavanja slučajnih promjenljivih. Pokušaj Sluckog da slučajnost poveže sa realnom funkcijom, rad Wiener-a koji prvi matematički opisuje haotično kretanje čestica polena u tečnosti, koje je danas poznato kao Wiener-ov proces, odnosno Brownovo kretanje. Uvođenjem pojma uslovna vjerovatnoća i matematičko očekivanje omogućilo je Kolmogorov-u da postavi postulate za opštu teoriju stohastičkih procesa Markov-og tipa sa beskonačnim parametarskim skupom. Za nastanak teorije stacionarnih procesa zaslužan je Khinchin-u, a za Gauss-ove procese Cramer-u. Dodatne informacije se mogu pronaći u radu [9].

Slučajne promjenjive su indeksirane nizom brojeva, koji se obično posmatraju kao tačke u vremenu, koje prikazuju stohastičke procese kao numeričke vrijednosti nekog sistema koji se slučajno mijenja u toku vremena. Sistemi kao što su: rast populacije bakterije, fluktacija električne struje, kretanje molekula gasa. Stohastički procesi se dijele u različite kategorije poput: slučajna šetnja, Markovi procesi, Levijevi procesi, obnovljivi procesi i tako dalje, na osnovu rada [8].

Stohastički modeli uključuju modele kao što su modeli za rast populacije, konkurencije, predatora i epidemije. Stohastički modeli su saglasni sa determinističkim. Međutim glavna razlika između determinističkih i stohastičkih modela je ta što deterministički modeli predviđaju ishod sa određenom sigurnošću, dok stohastički modeli samo daju vjerovatnoću ishoda.

Na primjer deterministički model kao što je diferencijalna jednačina sa datim uslovom $t = 0$, rešenje prati određeni put ili trajektoriju iz prostora rešenja. Numeričko rešenje diferencijalne jednačine je vrijednost rešenja, fiksni broj u datom trenutku t . Kod stohastičkog modela proces će možda biti prikazan preko sistema diferencijalnih jednačina pomoću prelazne matrice ili diferencijalnih jednačina Chapman-Kolmogorov ili stohastičkih diferencijalnih jednačina. Kod stohastičkog modela rešenje ovih jednačina je složeno, jedno rješenje trajektorije ne objašnjava cjelokupno ponašanje modela ali predstavlja realizaciju procesa.

Da bi se razumjelo ponašanje stohastičkog modela treba da se poznaje potpuna raspodjela vjerovatnoće tokom vremena. Kada prethodne metode nijesu izvodljive onda se za analizu

ponašanja procesa koriste modeli poput dobijanje trenutka raspodjele kao što su: matematičko očekivanje, varijansa i tako dalje. Upotreba determinističkih modela je česta kod dovoljno velike po veličini populacije. Kada je u pitanju mala po veličini populacija, posebno izumiranje populacije kada dolazi do variranja u veličini onda se koriste stohastički modeli. Dodatne informacije se mogu pronaći u knjizi [1].

Definicija 3.1 (Stohastičkog procesa): Stohastički proces je familija slučajnih promjenljivih $\{X_t(\omega) : t \in T, \omega \in \Omega\}$, gdje je T skup parametara, a Ω je prostor ishoda slučajnih promjenljivih.

Definicija 3.1 je preuzeta iz knjige [1].

Za svako fiksirano t , $X_t(\omega)$ predstavlja slučajnu promjenljivu definisanu na skupu Ω . Za svako fiksirano $\omega \in \Omega$, $X_t(\omega)$ odgovara funkciji definisanoj na T , koja se zove *jednostavan put* ili realizacija stohastičkih procesa. Skup T u stohastičkim procesima predstavlja vrijeme. Nekada se promjenljiva ω izostavlja, a slučajne promjenjive se obilježavaju sa X_t ili $X(t)$. Stohastički procesi u kojima je skup parametara neprekidan, a prostor stanja diskretan nazivaju se Markovi lanci neprekidnog vremena. Detaljno se može pročitati u knjizi [1].

Ovaj model primjenu najčešće nalazi u biologiji, u pogledu: konkurencije, predator-plijen, epidemije. Prikazivanje stope nataliteta i mortaliteta, odnosno sam proces rađanja i umiranja se ne može prikazati opštim diferencijalnim jednačinama nego stohastičkim diferencijalnim jednačinama. Stohastički procesi se danas koriste za modelovanje raznih pojava, pa time nalaze primjenu u raznim oblastima, kao što su: biologija, fizika, hemija, ekonomija i inženjerstvo, na osnovu knjige [1].

A. Opšta teorija o Markovim lancima

Nakon 1907. godine koja predstavlja vremenski period postavljanja koncepta Markov-ih lanaca od strane Andrej Andrejevič Markov, mnogi matematičari su radili na razvoju teorije Markov-ih lanaca, među kojima Kolmogorov, Dub, Levi i tako dalje. Markovi lanci spadaju u klasu stohastičkih procesa i smatraju se za najrazvijenijom teorijom istih.

Opisuju slučajne pojave sistema, koje se mijenjaju tokom vremena, a korisni su za njihovo predviđanje u budućnosti. Svojevremeno Markov-ih lanaca jeste da vjerovatnoća budućeg stanja sistema ne zavisi od prošlih stanja. Drugim riječima sadašnje stanje sadrži informacije koje mogu uticati na buduće stanje.

Posmatramo stohastički proces u diskretnom vremenu $\{X_n\}$, $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, gdje je X_n diskretna slučajna promjenljiva definisana na konačnom ili beskonačno prebrojivom skupu. Prostor stanja označimo sa $\{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, a sa n promjenljivu koja će se koristiti umjesto promjenljive t da označi elemente iz parametarskog skupa, definisan kao $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. Dakle n označava vrijeme u ovom slučaju, na osnovu rada [8].

Definicija 3.2: Stohastički proces $\{X_n\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$ u diskretnim vremenskim trenucima ima Markov-o svojstvo, ako:

$$P\{X_n = i_n | X_0 = i_0, \dots, X_{n-1} = i_{n-1}\} = P\{X_n = i_n | X_{n-1} = i_{n-1}\}, \text{ za } i_k \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}, k = 0, 1, \dots, n. \text{ Tada se stohastički proces naziva Markov lanac.}$$

Na osnovu rada [2] data definicija 3.2. Markovo svojstvo opisuje vjerovatnoću da se sistem u budućnosti nađe u nekom stanju zavisi samo od stanja u sadašnjem trenutku, a ne od stanja sistema iz prošlosti.

Definicija 3.3: Vjerovatnoća prelaza iz i -tog stanja u trenutku n u j -to stanje u trenutku $n + 1$ za $i, j = 1, 2, \dots$ u jednom koraku se definiše kao

$$p_{ij}(n) = P\{X_{n+1} = j | X_n = i\}.$$

Definicija 3.4: Ako vjerovatnoća prelaza $p_{ij}(n)$ u Markovom lancu ne zavisi od trenutka n , onda kažemo da je Markov lanac homogen. U suprotnom je nehomogen.

Definicije 3.3 i 3.4 date na osnovu rada [2].

Pretpostavlja se da je Markov lanac homogen, ako nije navedeno drugačije. Vjerovatnoća prelaza iz jednog stanja u drugo zadovoljava uslov da je

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} p_{ji} = 1,$$

za $i, j = 1, 2, \dots$ i $p_{ji} \geq 0$. Tumači se da sa vjerovatnoćom 1, proces u stanju i se mora pomjeriti u stanje j , pri čemu $j \neq i$ ili će ostati u istom stanju i u narednom vremenskom trenutku, na osnovu rada [2].

Definicija 3.5: Matrica vjerovatnoća prelaza u jednom koraku u Markov-om lancu se definiše kao:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} & p_{13} & \dots \\ p_{21} & p_{22} & p_{23} & \dots \\ p_{31} & p_{32} & p_{33} & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{bmatrix}$$

Matrica prelaza P je dimenzije $N \times N$ ako je skup stanja konačan $\{1, \dots, N\}$. Takođe zaključak je da je suma elemenata matrice $\sum_{j=1}^N p_{ji} = 1$.

Definicija 3.6: Nenegativna matrica u kojoj su sume elemenata kolone jednake jedan, se naziva stohastičkom matricom. Pomoću rada [2] date su definicije 3.5 i 3.6.

B. Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine

Unaprijed i unazad Kolmogorove diferencijalne jednačine se koriste da izraze stopu promjene vjerovatnoće prelaza. Vjerovatnoća prelaza $p_{ji}(t + \Delta t)$ se može definisati preko Chapman - Kolmogorov jednačina,

$$p_{ji}(t + \Delta t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_{jk}(\Delta t) p_{ki}(t).$$

S obzirom da postoji matrica generator Q , tada se može primijeniti identitet (1)

$$p_{ji}(\Delta t) = \delta_{ji} + q_{ji}\Delta t + o(\Delta t), \quad (1)$$

gdje je δ_{ji} oznaka za Kronecker-ovu deltu.¹

Primjenom identiteta (1) dobija se

$$p_{ji}(t + \Delta t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_{ki}(t) [\delta_{jk} + q_{jk}\Delta t + o(\Delta t)].$$

¹Kronecker-ova delta $\delta_{ji} = \begin{cases} 1, & i = j \\ 0, & i \neq j \end{cases}$.

Oduzimanjem $p_{ji}(t)$, dijeljenjem sa Δt , i primjenom identiteta $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_{ki}(t) = 1$, dobija se

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{p_{ji}(t + \Delta t) - p_{ji}(t)}{\Delta t} &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_{ki}(t) \left[q_{jk} + \frac{o(\Delta t)}{\Delta t} \right] \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_{ki}(t) q_{jk} + \frac{o(\Delta t)}{\Delta t}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Kada $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ tada se iz (2) dobija

$$\frac{dp_{ji}(t)}{dt} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} q_{jk} p_{ki}(t), \quad i, j = 0, 1, \dots \quad (3)$$

Definicija 3.7: Sistem jednačina (3) predstavlja unaprijed Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine. Izražene u formi matrice one su

$$\frac{dP(t)}{dt} = QP(t),$$

gdje je $P(t) = [p_{ji}(t)]$ matrica vjerovatnoća prelaza i $Q = [q_{ji}]$ generator matrice.

Unazad Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine se definišu na sličan način kao i unaprijed Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine. Primjenom Chapman-Kolmogorov jednačina i praveći zamjenu dobija se:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{ji}(t + \Delta t) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_{ki}(\Delta t) p_{jk}(t) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} [\delta_{ki} + q_{ki}\Delta t + o(\Delta t)] p_{jk}(t). \end{aligned}$$

Slično izvođenju unaprijed Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine i na osnovu pretpostavke $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_{jk}(t) < \infty$ dobija se sledeći sistem diferencijalnih jednačina:

$$\frac{dp_{ji}(t)}{dt} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_{jk}(t) q_{ki}, \quad i, j = 0, 1, \dots \quad (4)$$

Definicija 3.8: Sistem jednačina (4) predstavlja unazad Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine. Izražene u formi matrice one su

$$\frac{dP(t)}{dt} = QP(t),$$

gdje je $P(t) = [p_{ji}(t)]$ matrica vjerovatnoća prelaza i $Q = [q_{ji}]$ generator matrice.

Detaljne informacije se mogu pronaći u knjizi [1].

IV. OPŠTI PROCES RADANJA I UMIRANJA

U ovom poglavlju se izučava opšti proces rađanja i umiranja, proces rađanja, proces umiranja i rast populacije. Proces rađanja i proces umiranja se izvode na osnovu vjerovatnoće stanja $p_i(t) = P\{X(t) = i\}$. Prikazano je da je raspodjela vjerovatnoće za proces rađanja negativna binomna raspodjela, a za proces umiranja binomna raspodjela. Rast populacije je prikazan Malthusov-om metodom koja pokazuje da je rast neograničen.

Opšti proces rađanja i umiranja je Markov lanac X_n u diskretnom vremenu. Vjerovatnoća rađanja kao i vjerovatnoća umiranja zavise od obima populacije. Neka X_n predstavlja obim populacije, gdje prostor stanja može biti konačan $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, N\}$ ili beskonačan $\{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ i N je maksimalna veličina populacije, na osnovu rada [8].

Pretpostavi se da beskonačno mala vjerovatnoća prelaza zadovoljava:

$$p_{i+j,j}(\Delta n) = P\{\Delta X(n) = j | X(n) = i\} \quad (5)$$

$$= \begin{cases} \lambda_i \Delta n + o(\Delta n), & j = 1 \\ \mu_i \Delta n + o(\Delta n), & j = -1 \\ 1 - (\lambda_i + \mu_i) \Delta n + o(\Delta n), & j = 0 \\ o(\Delta n), & j \neq -1, 0, 1 \end{cases},$$

za Δn dovoljno malo, gdje je $\lambda_i \geq 0$, $\mu_i \geq 0$ za $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$ i $\mu_0 = 0$. Takođe je čest slučaj za $\lambda_0 = 0$, osim kada je u pitanju imigracija. Takođe $\lambda_i \Delta n$ označava vjerovatnoću rađanja, a $\mu_i \Delta n$ vjerovatnoću umiranja u intervalu Δn , kada je sistem u stanju i .

Beskonačno mala vjerovatnoća prelaza (5) koja se zasniva na dovoljno malo Δn je slična pretpostavkama koje su nastale pri definisanju procesa rađanja i procesa umiranja, definisani na sledećim stranama poglavlja IV. Na malom intervalu vremena Δn može da se desi samo jedna promjena stanja, rođenje ili smrt.

Ako je veličina populacije i i desi se rođenje tada je $i \rightarrow i + 1$, a ukoliko dođe do smrti tada je $i \rightarrow i - 1$. Kolmogorove diferencijalne jednačine za $p_{i,j}(n)$ se izvode direktno na osnovu pretpostavke (5). Pretpostavi se da je Δn dovoljno malo i neka je vjerovatnoća prelaza $p_{j,i}(n + \Delta n)$.

Vjerovatnoća prelaza $p_{j,i}(n + \Delta n)$ se može izraziti preko vjerovatnoće prelaza za vrijeme n na sledeći način:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{j,i}(n + \Delta n) &= p_{j-1,i}(n)[\lambda_{j-1} \Delta n + o(\Delta n)] \\ &\quad + p_{j+1,i}(n)[\mu_{j+1} \Delta n + o(\Delta n)] \\ &\quad + p_{j,i}(n)[1 - (\lambda_j + \mu_j) \Delta n + o(\Delta n)] \\ &\quad + \sum_{k \neq -1, 0, 1}^{\infty} p_{j+k,i}(n) o(\Delta n) \\ &= p_{j-1,i}(n) \lambda_{j-1} \Delta n + p_{j+1,i}(n) \mu_{j+1} \Delta n \\ &\quad + p_{j,i}(n)[1 - (\lambda_j + \mu_j) \Delta n] + o(\Delta n), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

pri čemu važi za svako i i j u prostoru stanja, sa izuzetkom u krajnjim tačkama $j = 0$ i $j = N$.

Ako je $j = 0$ tada je iz (6)

$$\begin{aligned} p_{0,i}(n + \Delta n) &= p_{1,i}(n) \mu_1 \Delta n \\ &\quad + p_{0,i}(n)[1 - \lambda_0 \Delta n] + o(\Delta n). \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

U slučaju kada je konačan prostor stanja, gdje je $j = N$ maksimalna veličina populacije, tada je iz (6)

$$\begin{aligned} p_{N,i}(n + \Delta n) &= p_{N-1,i}(n) \lambda_{N-1} \Delta n \\ &\quad + p_{N,i}(n)[1 - \mu_N \Delta n] + o(\Delta n). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

U konačnom prostoru stanja se pretpostavlja da $\lambda_N = 0$ i $p_{k,N}(n) = 0$ za $k > N$. Izvođenjem izraza (6), (7) i (8) se određuje šta se desilo prije trenutka $n + \Delta n$, s obzirom da će proces biti u stanju j u trenutku $n + \Delta n$.

Sada se izvode unaprijed Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine. Oduzima se $p_{j,i}(n)$, $p_{0,i}(n)$ i $p_{N,i}(n)$ u jednačinama

(6), (7) i (8), respektivno. Zatim, dijeljenjem sa Δn i uzimajući granicu $\Delta n \rightarrow 0$ dobijaju se unaprijed Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine za opšti proces rađanja i umiranja,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dp_{j,i}(n)}{dn} &= \lambda_{j-1} p_{j-1,i}(n) - (\lambda_j + \mu_j) p_{j,i}(n) + \mu_{j+1} p_{j+1,i}(n) \\ \frac{dp_{0,i}(n)}{dn} &= -\lambda_0 p_{0,i}(n) + \mu_1 p_{1,i}(n) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

za $i \geq 0$ i $j \geq 1$. Za konačan prostor stanja, diferencijalna jednačina za $p_{N,i}(n)$ je

$$\frac{dp_{N,i}}{dn} = \lambda_{N-1} p_{N-1,i}(n) - p_{N,i}(n) \mu_N \quad (10)$$

Unaprijed Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine (9) i (10) zadovoljavaju $\frac{dP}{dn} = QP$, gdje je Q generator matrice koji ima sledeću formu kada je beskonačan prostor stanja

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} -\Lambda_0 & \mu_1 & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ \lambda_0 & -\lambda_1 - \mu_1 & \mu_2 & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & \lambda_1 & -\lambda_2 - \mu_2 & \mu_3 & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_2 & -\lambda_3 - \mu_3 & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

i kada je konačan prostor stanja tada je,

$$Q = \begin{pmatrix} -\Lambda_0 & \mu_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \lambda_0 & -\lambda_1 - \mu_1 & \mu_2 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_1 & -\lambda_2 - \mu_2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \mu_N \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & -\mu_N \end{pmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

Prelazna matrica $T = (t_{ji})$ za Markov lanac $\{Y_n\}$ se definiše preko generatornih matrica (11) i (12). Za generatornu matricu (11), odgovara sledeća prelazna matrica Markov-og lanca

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{\mu_1}{(\lambda_1 + \mu_1)} & 0 & 0 & \dots \\ 1 & 0 & \frac{\mu_2}{(\lambda_2 + \mu_2)} & 0 & \dots \\ 0 & \frac{\lambda_1}{(\lambda_1 + \mu_1)} & 0 & \frac{\mu_3}{(\lambda_3 + \mu_3)} & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\lambda_2}{(\lambda_2 + \mu_2)} & 0 & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{pmatrix}.$$

Generatornoj matrici (12) odgovara sledeća prelazna matrica Markov-og lanca

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{\mu_1}{(\lambda_1 + \mu_1)} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & \frac{\mu_2}{(\lambda_2 + \mu_2)} & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{\lambda_1}{(\lambda_1 + \mu_1)} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Pretpostavlja se da je u oba slučaja $\lambda_i + \mu_i > 0$ za $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. Ako je $\lambda_i + \mu_i = 0$ za bilo koje i tada se stanje i apsorbuje. Markov lanac se može posmatrati kao slučajna šetnja sa granicom u 0 ili N ako je u pitanju konačno stanje. Vjerovatnoća šetnje u desno, to jeste rođenja jednaka je $n_{i+1,i} = \frac{\lambda_i}{(\lambda_i + \mu_i)}$, a vjerovatnoća šetnje u lijevo, to jeste umiranja jednaka je $n_{i-1,i} = \frac{\mu_i}{(\lambda_i + \mu_i)}$, na osnovu rada [1].

U svakom vremenskom intervalu $[n, n+1]$ veličina populacije se poveća za jedan, smanji za jedan ili ostane ista. Lako se dokazuje da iz bilo kojeg početnog stanja, u slučaju konačnog Markov-og lanca dolazi do izumiranja populacije,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P\{X_n = 0\} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} p_0(n) = 1,$$

detaljno obrazloženje se može naći u radu [8].

A. Proces rađanja

Postoje tri pretpostavke koje su upotrijebljene za razvoj jednostavnog procesa rađanja, a to su sledeće:

- Nema pojedinaca koji umiru
- Ne postoje interakcije među ljudima
- Stopa nataliteta b je ista za sve pojedince

Pojam *pojedinač* može označavati ćeliju ili neku drugu vrstu organizma. Neka $n(t)$ označava veličinu populacije u trenutku t . U malom vremenskom periodu Δt , porast veličine populacije, odnosno stopa nataliteta na osnovu jednog pojedinca je $b \times \Delta t$, a porast veličine populacije na osnovu svih pojedinaca je $b\Delta t \times n(t)$. Tada je

$$n(t + \Delta t) = n(t) + b\Delta t n(t).$$

Kada se izraz malo sredi, dobija se sledeći izraz

$$\frac{n(t + \Delta t) - n(t)}{\Delta t} = bn(t).$$

Kada $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ dobija se diferencijalna jednačina za eksponencijalni rast,

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = bn(t).$$

Ako je početna veličina populacije $n(0) = a$, tada je rešenje diferencijalne jednačine

$$n(t) = ae^{bt}.$$

Veličina populacije u trenutku t je predviđena sa apsolutnom sigurnošću ako je poznata početna veličina populacije a i stopa nataliteta b . Na ovaj način se formulisao stohastički model. U ovom slučaju veličina populacije će biti predstavljena kroz vjerovatnoću, veličina populacije je n u trenutku t .

Pretpostavlja se da je veličina populacije diskretna promjenljiva sa neprekidnim vremenom. Pošto je prostor stanja diskretan, a vrijeme neprekidno, stohastički proces zadovoljava $X_t \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$, $t \in [0, \infty)$, gdje je X_t diskretna slučajna promjenljiva koja predstavlja veličinu populacije u trenutku t . Neka je vjerovatnoća funkcije gustine slučajne promjenljive X_t označena sa $\{p_n(t)\}_{n=0}^{\infty}$, gdje je

$$p_n(t) = P\{X_t = n\}$$

Slučajna promjenljiva X_t u dovoljno malom periodu vremena Δt ima sledeće pretpostavke:

- 1) Vjerovatnoća da će doći do rođenja je približna $b\Delta t$.
- 2) Vjerovatnoća da će doći do više od jednog rođenja u trenutku Δt je zanemarljiva.
- 3) Za $t = 0$, $P\{X_0 = a\} = 1$.

Kada kažemo da je vjerovatnoća zanemarljiva odnosi se na to da je reda Δt ili $o(\Delta t)$, tako da je $\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{o(\Delta t)}{\Delta t} = 0$, pri čemu $o(\Delta t)$ dostiže 0 brže od Δt , na osnovu knjige [1].

Na osnovu pretpostavki 1 i 2, da bi populacija bila veličine n u trenutku $t + \Delta t$, može biti ili veličine n u trenutku t i ne dešava se rođenje u $(t, t + \Delta t)$ ili veličine $n - 1$ u trenutku t i desi se jedno rođenje u $(t, t + \Delta t)$. Vjerovatnoća da će se populacija veličine n povećati na $n + 1$ u trenutku $(t, t + \Delta t)$ jednaka je $bn\Delta t$, a vjerovatnoća da populacija neće uspjeti da se poveća u trenutku $(t, t + \Delta t)$ jednaka je $1 - bn\Delta t$, detaljnije objašnjeno u radu [8].

Vjerovatnoća da je stanje jednako n u trenutku $t + \Delta t$ zavisi od toga da li je u trenutku t veličina populacije bila $n - 1$ i da se desilo rođenja ili da je veličina populacije n i nije se desilo rođenja. Tada je

$$p_n(t + \Delta t) = p_{n-1}(t)b(n-1)\Delta t + p_n(t)(1 - bn\Delta t). \quad (13)$$

Stanje procesa u trenutku $t + \Delta t$ zavisi samo od stanja u trenutku t , a ne od vremena prije t (poznato svojstvo Markova). Kada od obje strane jednačine (13) oduzmemo $p_n(t)$, podijelimo sa Δt i puštimo da $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, dobije se sistem diferencijalnih jednačina poznate kao Kolmogorove diferencijalne jednačine:

$$\frac{dp_n(t)}{dt} = b(n-1)p_{n-1}(t) - bnp_n(t), \text{ gdje je } n = 1, 2, \dots$$

Na primjer,

$$\frac{dp_1(t)}{dt} = -bp_1(t) \quad \text{i} \quad \frac{dp_2(t)}{dt} = bp_1(t) - 2bp_2(t).$$

Ako je na početku obim populacije 0, tada ne može da se desi rođenje i u svakom trenutku $p_0(t) = 1$. Kolmogorov jednačine se mogu riješiti iterativno ili koristeći tehnike generatrisne momenta. Rešenje $p_n(t)$ ima oblik negativne binomne raspodjele za fiksirano t :

$$p_n(t) = \binom{n-1}{\alpha-1} e^{-\alpha bt} (1 - e^{-bt})^{n-\alpha}, \quad n = \alpha, \alpha + 1, \alpha + 2, \dots$$

Detaljne informacije se mogu pronaći u knjizi [1].

S obzirom da je rađanje jedini događaj koji se razmatra, varijansa i matematičko očekivanje se mogu dobiti direktno iz negativne binomne raspodjele,

$$\mu_t = ae^{bt} \quad i \quad \sigma_t^2 = ae^{bt}(e^{bt} - 1). \quad (14)$$

U ovom primjeru matematičko očekivanje jednako je rešenju determinističkog modela, dok varijansa raste uporedo s vremenom. Vrijednosti matematičkog očekivanja i varijanse, dobijene pomoću formule (14), u slučaju kada je $a = 1$ i $b = 1$ date su u tabeli I:

Tabela I
TABELA VRIJEDNOSTI

t	μ_t	σ_t^2	σ_t	$n(t)$
0	1	0	0	1
1	2.72	4.67	2.16	2.72
2	7.39	47.21	6.87	7.39
3	20.09	383.34	19.58	20.09

U tabeli I μ_t je matematičko očekivanje, σ_t^2 varijansa, σ_t standardna devijacija i $n(t)$ je rešenje diferencijalnih jednačina za proces rađanja za $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$ kada su $a = 1$, $b = 1$, po ugledu na rad [5].

Slika 1. Tri stohastičke realizacije procesa rađanja

Slika napravljena na osnovu rada [1]. Na slici 1 su tri stohastičke realizacije procesa rađanja kada je $a = 1$, $b = 1$ i $X_0 = 1$. Isprekidanom linijom je prikazana eksponencijalna kriva rasta $n(t) = e^t$, na osnovu rada [1] i [5].

B. Proces umiranja

Proces smrti započinje u populaciji veličine n , koja je definisana na sledeći način:

$$p_i(0) = \begin{cases} 1, & j = n \\ 0, & i \neq n \end{cases}$$

Sve jedinke populacije imaju istu vjerovatnoću smrtnosti, definisanu pomoću sledećeg zapisa

$$p_i(t) = \begin{cases} \lambda_i = 0, & i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n \\ \mu_i = i\mu, & i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

pri čemu je $\mu > 0$.

Stanje nula je apsorbujuće stanje, a sva druga stanja su prelazna, grafički prikazano na slici 2, koja je preuzeta iz rada [10]. Detaljno se može pročitati u radu [10].

Slika 2. Stanje nula apsorbujuće, a sva druga stanja su prelazna

Matematički zapis (15) tumači se na sledeći način. Ako je natalitet λ_i jednako 0 tada je mortalitet μ_i proporcionalno veličini populacije, za $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$. Na ovaj način se dobija linearni proces umiranja. Kako nema rađanja interesuje samo matrica prelaza od 0 do n , koja ima sledeću formu

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \mu & -\mu & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2\mu & -2\mu & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & n\mu & -n\mu \end{pmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

gdje veličina $\mu > 0$.

Na osnovu matrice (16) dobija se sistem diferencijalnih jednačina Kolmogorov:

$$\begin{aligned} p'_0(t) &= \mu p_1(t), & p_0(0) &= 0 \\ p'_1(t) &= 2\mu p_2(t) - \mu p_1(t), & p_1(0) &= 0 \\ & \dots \\ p'_{n-1}(t) &= n\mu p_n(t) - (n-1)\mu p_{n-1}(t), & p_{n-1}(0) &= 0 \\ p'_n(t) &= -n\mu p_n(t), & p_n(0) &= 1. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Sistem se rešava od poslednje jednačine. Kako je u pitanju diferencijalna jednačina koja razdvaja promjenljive, njeno rešenje je $p_n(t) = ce^{-n\mu t}$. Početni uslov za $t = 0$ daje $c = 1$, pa je $p_n(t) = e^{-n\mu t}$. Dobijeno rešenje se ubacuje u pretposlednju jednačinu (17), pa se dobija obična diferencijalna jednačina

$$p'_{n-1}(t) + (n-1)\mu p_{n-1}(t) = n\mu e^{-n\mu t}. \quad (18)$$

Jednačina (18) je diferencijalna jednačina sa konstantnim koeficijentima i njenim rešavanjem dobije se homogeno rešenje $y_h = ce^{-(n-1)\mu t}$ i partikularno rešenje $y_p = Ae^{-n\mu t}$. Da bi se izračunala vrijednost od A uvrstimo partikularno rešenje y_p u diferencijalnu jednačinu (18) i dobije se:

$$-n\mu Ae^{-n\mu t} + (n-1)\mu Ae^{-n\mu t} = n\mu e^{-n\mu t},$$

odakle se dobija da je $A = -n$.

Opšte rešenje jednačine je:

$$p_{n-1}(t) = y_h + y_p = ce^{-(n-1)\mu t} - ne^{-n\mu t},$$

sa početnim uslovom $t = 0$ dobija se $c = n$.

Dakle, dobija se

$$p_{n-1}(t) = n(1 - e^{-\mu t})e^{-(n-1)\mu t}.$$

Nastavljanjem postupka, dalje rešavanje daje

$$p_i(t) = \binom{n}{i} (1 - e^{-\mu t})^{n-i} (e^{-\mu t})^i.$$

Dakle, slučajna promjenljiva $X(t)$ ima binomnu raspodjelu $B(n, e^{-\mu t})$. Veličina populacije u momentu t je $E(X(t)) = ne^{-\mu t}$. Za dodatne informacije pogledati rad [7].

C. Malthusov model rasta populacije

Engleski demograf Thomas Malthus je 1798. godine u svom radu *An Essay of the Principle of Population* modelirao rast populacije bez migracija. Tada je predvidio pojavu globalne gladi ukoliko vlade zemalja ne budu uticale na regulaciju veličine porodice. Izvodi se Malthus-ov model rasta populacije na sledeći način.

Neka je $N(t)$ veličina populacije, odnosno broj jedinki u trenutku t . Označimo sa b prosječnu stopu rađanja, a d prosječnu stopu umiranja po glavi stanovnika. Osnovna pretpostavka Malthusovog modela jeste da u vremenskom intervalu Δt broj rođenih iznosi $b\Delta t N(t)$, a broj umrlih $d\Delta t N(t)$.

Veličina populacije u trenutku $t + \Delta t$ nalazi tako što se veličini populacije u trenutku t doda broj rođenih u trenutku Δt , a zatim oduzme broj umrlih u trenutku Δt . Na osnovu prethodnog važi

$$N(t + \Delta t) = N(t) + b\Delta t N(t) - d\Delta t N(t). \quad (19)$$

Iz (19) slijedi

$$\frac{N(t + \Delta t) - N(t)}{\Delta t} = (b - d)N(t). \quad (20)$$

Za $\lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0}$ iz (20) dobija se diferencijalna jednačina

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = (b - d)N.$$

Označimo sa $N_0 = N(0)$ početnu veličinu populacije i neka je $r = b - d > 0$ stopa rasta populacije. Tada je veličina populacije u trenutku t data kao rešenje Cauchyjev-og početnog zadatka:

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = rN, N_0 = N(0) \quad (21)$$

Jednačina modela je diferencijalna jednačina prvog reda koja se rešava metodom razdvajanje promjenljivih:

$$\frac{dN}{N} = r dt \iff \ln N = rt + \ln c, c > 0 \iff N = ce^{rt}, c > 0$$

Iz uslova $N_0 = N(0)$ slijedi $c = N_0$, pa je rešenje Cauchyjev-og početnog zadatka (21) dato sa

$$N(t) = N_0 e^{rt}. \quad (22)$$

Dakle u Malthusov-om matematičkom modelu sa početnom veličinom populacije N_0 i rastom populacije $r = b - d$, rast populacije je opisan eksponencijalnom funkcijom u (22). Nedostatak modela jeste što pretpostavlja da su b i d konstante, pa slijedi i da je rast populacije r konstantan, a to bi značilo da je rast populacije neograničen, dodatne informacije u radu [3].

V. ZAKLJUČAK

Sam početak rada podsjeća na osnovne pojmove teorije vjerovatnoće zbog njene primjene u definisanju opšteg procesa rađanja i umiranja, procesa rađanja i procesa umiranja. Zatim govori o razvoju stohastičkih procesa, njihovoj definiciji i primjeni. Opšti proces rađanja i umiranja je Markov lanac koji je definisan kao slučajan proces u diskretnom skupu vrijeme, pa rad definiše Markov lanac, matricu prelaza. Kako se za objašnjenje procesa koriste Kolmogorov diferencijalne jednačine, izvedene su i definisane.

Prikazuje da opšti proces rađanja i umiranja, proces rađanja, proces umiranja i rast populacije zavise od *obima populacije*. Takođe se može primijetiti da je raspodjela vjerovatnoće za proces rađanja negativna binomna raspodjela, a za proces umiranja binomna raspodjela. Rast populacije prikazan je Malthusovim modelom koji pokazuje da je rast populacije neograničen.

Kod opšteg procesa rađanja i umiranja ukoliko je konačan Markov lanac dolazi do izumiranja populacije. Proces rađanja je definisan na osnovu tri pretpostavke: nema pojedinaca koji umiru, ne postoje interakcije među ljudima i stopa nataliteta je ista za sve pojedince. Kako je u tom procesu definisano samo rađanje kao događaj čije rešenje je prikazano kao negativna binomna raspodjela, dobijaju se iz nje direktno matematičko očekivanje i varijansa.

Pomoću postavljenih parametara $b = 1$ gdje je b stopa nataliteta i $a = 1$ obim populacije i vremena $t = 0, 1, 2, 3$ izračunate su: matematičko očekivanje, varijansa, standardna devijacija. Na taj način dobijeni su podaci koji predstavljaju rešenje diferencijalnih jednačina za proces rađanja. Na osnovu tih podataka prikazane su tri stohastičke realizacije u obliku grafika.

Kod procesa umiranja sve jedinice imaju istu vjerovatnoću smrtnosti. Prikazuje rešavanje sistema Kolmogorov diferencijalnih jednačina sa određenim uslovima. Rešenje dobija u obliku binomne raspodjele, a veličina populacije je izražena preko matematičkog očekivanja. Zatim se osvrće na Malthus-ov model rasta populacije koji predstavlja osnovu za sve ostale populacijske modele. Model rasta koji je opisan eksponencijalnom funkcijom.

Malthus-ov model rasta populacije zaključuje da je rast populacije neograničen, što je nemoguće u prirodi. Postoje određena ograničenja koja utiču na stopu rasta populacije. Među tim ograničenjima spadaju *ograničeni resursi staništa*: hrana, voda, prostora i tako dalje. Takođe kada populacija postane dovoljno velika neizbježno je da dođe i do takmičenja-kompetencije za resurse, zbog čega stopa rađanja s vremenom opada, a stopa smrtnosti raste. Pri izvođenju složenijih modela populacije, poput Logistički model rasta populacije (Verhustov) ili model grabljivac - plijen (Lotka - Volterra) uzeti su u obzir i druga ograničenja, na osnovu rada [3].

Proces rađanja i umiranja je koristan zbog činjenice da se pojam *jedinka* može odnositi na broj objekata kod bilo kojeg diskretnog, potencijalno interakcijskog sistema. Izučavanje ovih procesa se smatra bitnim jer svoju primjenu pronalaze u

evolutivnoj biologiji, populacionoj biologiji, genetici i ekologiji. Koristi u proučavanju dinamike zaraznih bolesti, gdje broj zaraženih jedinki predstavlja populaciju od interesa. Koriste za modelovanje populacije organizama koje žive u okruženjima sa ograničenim resursima.

U molekularnoj evoluciji mogu modelovati umetnute i izbrisane nukleotide u DNK ili RNK sekvenci, kao metode vjerovatnoće poravnanja, transportne genetske elemente, porodice gena ili čitave hromosome, na osnovu rada [4]. Međutim proces rađanja i umiranja pronalazi primjenu i u teoriji redova, odnosno teoriji čekanja u redu, gdje je stanje sistema broj jedinki u redu. Takođe se kao primjer pravljenja modela na osnovu procesa rađanja i umiranja navodi broj dolazaka i odlazak u sistemu, na osnovu rada [1].

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Bajesova verovatnoća u vremenskoj prognozi

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Sažetak—Ovaj rad istražuje primenu Bajesove verovatnoće u vremenskim prognozama, sa posebnim naglaskom na njen značaj za preciznost prognoza, posebno u kontekstu predviđanja padavina. U prvom delu rada, definisana je osnovna teorija verovatnoće, uključujući koncepte verovatnoće i Bajesove verovatnoće, kao i njihovu primenu u svakodnevnom životu. Drugi deo se fokusira na Bajesovu verovatnoću u vremenskim prognozama, gde su analizirani apriorni podaci i uslovne verovatnoće koje se koriste za predviđanje vremenskih događaja. Posebno je istraženo kako se Bajesova metoda koristi za procenu verovatnoće padavina na osnovu dostupnih podataka, kao što su temperatura, vlažnost i oblačnost. Takođe, rad istražuje prednosti koje Bajesova verovatnoća donosi u smislu tačnosti i fleksibilnosti vremenskih prognoza. Na kraju, rad razmatra dalja moguća proširenja primene Bajesove verovatnoće, uključujući njen uticaj na različite aspekte vremenskih modela i prognoza. Cilj rada je da se pokaže kako statističke metode, kao što je Bajesova verovatnoća, mogu značajno unaprediti tačnost i pouzdanost vremenskih prognoza.

Ključne riječi: Bajes, Prognoza, Verovatnoća

I. UVOD

U savremenom svetu, suočavamo se s nesigurnostima koje proističu iz složenosti prirodnih fenomena, kao što je vremenska prognoza. Verovatnoća kao grana matematike koja se bavi analizom i merenjem nesigurnosti, postaje ključan alat u predikciji događaja i donošenju informisanih odluka. U ovom radu istražujemo koncept verovatnoće, sa posebnim osvrtom na Bajesovu verovatnoću, koja omogućava prilagođavanje i ažuriranje naših procena na osnovu novih informacija.

Bajesova verovatnoća, zasnovana je na Bajesovoj teoremi, predstavlja revolucionarni pristup koji se koristi u različitim oblastima od statistike do veštačke inteligencije. U meteorologiji Bajesova verovatnoća ima značajnu primenu omogućavajući meteorolozima da kombinuju apriorne podatke s novim informacijama kako bi unapredili tačnost vremenskih prognoza. U ovom radu analiziraćemo kako meteorolozi koriste apriorne podatke i uslovne verovatnoće za predviđanje vremenskih obrazca, kao i kako se Bajesova verovatnoća koristi za procenu verovatnoće kiše.

S obzirom na sve veći značaj preciznog prognoziranja vremena u svakodnevnom životu i razvoju strategija za upravljanje rizicima, razumjevanje Bajesove verovatnoće postaje od vitalnog značaja. Ovaj rad će istražiti prednosti koje ova metoda nudi, kao i njene dalje primene, čime će doprineti boljem razumevanju njenog uticaja na savremenu meteorologiju.

Vremenska prognoza predstavlja proces predviđanja atmosferskih uslova na određenom području u budućnosti, oslanjajući se na prikupljenje podataka kao što su temperatura, vazdušni pritisak, vlažnost, vetrovi i padavine. Tačnost prognoze zavisi od kvaliteta i obima ovih podataka ali i od sposobnosti modela da predvide neočekivane promene u atmosferi. Upravo zbog složenosti i neizvesnosti u atmosferi meteorolozi sve češće koriste Bajesovu verovatnoću, koja omogućava prilagođavanje prognoza na osnovu novih informacija. Bajesov pristup kombinuje apriorne podatke sa novim opažanjima čime se poboljšava tačnost predikcija jer omogućava stalno ažuriranje verovatnoća i smanjenje nesigurnosti. Na taj način vremenske prognoze postaju preciznije i fleksibilnije uzimajući u obzir dinamičke promene u atmosferi.

Cilj ovog rada mi je da istražim kako primena Bajesove verovatnoće u meteorologiji može unaprediti preciznost vremenskih prognoza, pružajući dublje razumjevanje načina na koji kombinacija apriornih podataka i novih informacija smanjuje neizvesnost u predikcijama. Rad ima za cilj da istakne prednosti ovog probabilističkog pristupa u odnosu na klasične metode prognoziranja, kao i da istraži šire primene Bajesove verovatnoće na druge oblasti koje zahtijevaju donošenje odluka pod nesigurnim uslovima.

II. TEORIJA VEROVATNOĆE

A. Definicija verovatnoće

U svakodnevnom životu često se srećemo sa izjavama koje u sebi sadrže riječ **verovatnoća**. Umesto riječi verovatnoća koriste se i riječi mogućnost ili šansa. Primjeri koji su preuzeti iz [2] nam pokazuju da koristimo verovatnoću i njenu definiciju:

- Prognošičar vremena kaže u izvještaju na TV da je verovatnoća da sutra padne kiša 80%.
- Reporter koji izveštava o zdravlju građana kaže da pušaci imaju veću verovatnoću da dobiju rak nego nepušaci.
- Zaposleni se pitaju kolika je verovatnoća da će se plate povećati u narednoj godini.

Verovatnoća kao nauka, bavi se procenama, prognozama, mogućnostima u situaciji kada nemamo sve potrebne podatke za rešavanje nekog problema. U tom smislu verovatnoća:

- meri mogućnost da li će se neki događaj realizovati ili ne
- koristi se da donosimo odluke u uslovima nepotpunih informacija
- predstavlja osnovu statističkog zaključivanja

Teorija verovatnoće je matematička disciplina koja izučava zakonitosti pojava čiji su ishodi slučajni [2]. Teorija verovatnoće za svoja istraživanja koristi idealne eksperimente koji imaju sledeće osobine:

- Ponavljaju se proizvoljan broj puta pod istim uslovima,
- Svi njihovi ishodi su unapred definisani,
- Ishod pojedinačnog eksperimenta nije unapred poznat.

Slučajni eksperimenti nazivaju se još **statistički** ili **stohastički eksperimenti**.

Ishod slučajnog eksperimenta je **slučajan događaj**. Slučajni događaji mogu biti **elementarni**, odnosno da se ne mogu redukovati na jednostavnije događaje i **složeni**, koji mogu da se dalje razlože na elementarne događaje.

Kako je rečeno u knjizi [2] prvi problemi za čije je rešavanje korišćena verovatnoća potiču iz 10 i 11 vijeka i odnose se na rezultate prilikom bacanja kocke i hazardnih igara. Rađanje teorije verovatnoće vezano je za imena: Blez Paskal, Pjer Ferma i Kristina Hajgensa.

Definicija

Neka skup Ω sadrži n elementarnih događaja koji su disjunktni i jednako mogući. Ako je $m(0 \leq m \leq n)$, broj svih povoljnih ishoda događaja A , onda je verovatnoća $P(A)$ jednaka $P(A) = \frac{m}{n}$ [2].

B. Bajesova verovatnoća

Verovatnoća događaja A znajući da se događaj B već realizovao ili pretpostavljajući da će se realizovati naziva se **uslovna verovatnoća** [8].

Definicija

Verovatnoća $P(A|B)$ zove se uslovna verovatnoća događaja A pod uslovom B i definiše se sa $P(A|B) = \frac{P(A \cdot B)}{P(B)}$ za $P(B) > 0$ [8].

Koristeći definiciju uslovne verovatnoće moguće je definisati zavisnost i nezavisnost događaja. Neka je dat skup Ω i $A, B \subset \Omega$. Događaj A je **zavisan** od događaja B , ako ostvarivanje događaja B utiče na realizaciju događaja A . U suprotnom su nezavisni.

Definicija

Ako su događaji A i B međusobno zavisni, tada je proizvod događaja A i B : $P(AB) = P(B) \cdot P(A|B) = P(A) \cdot P(B \cdot A)$ [8].

Definicija

Događaji A i B su međusobno nezavisni ako je

$$P(A|B) = P(A), P(B|A) = P(B) \text{ [8],}$$

a proizvod događaja A i B je

$$P(AB) = P(A)P(B) \text{ [8].}$$

Neka nezavisni slučajni događaji H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n čine jedno **razlaganje** skupa Ω . Oni čine **potpuni sistem hipoteza**, odnosno $\sum_{k=1}^n H_k = \Omega$, gde su verovatnoće $P(H_k)$ realizacije pojedinih hipoteza koje su dovele do ostvarivanja događaja A .

Teorema 1. Formula totalne verovatnoće: Ako događaji H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n čine **potpuni sistem hipoteza** u odnosu na događaj A , tada je

$$P(A) = \sum_{k=1}^n P(H_k)P(A|H_k) \text{ [8].}$$

Definicija

Bajesova formula

Ako događaji H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n čine **potpuni sistem hipoteza** u odnosu na događaj A i $P(A) > 0$, tada je

$$P(H_i|A) = \frac{P(H_i)P(A|H_i)}{P(A)} = \frac{P(H_i)P(A|H_i)}{\sum_{k=1}^n P(H_k)P(A|H_k)} \text{ [8].}$$

Bajesova formula zove se i **formula verovatnoća hipoteza (uzorka)**, jer na događaje H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n može se gledati kao na različite uzorke koji mogu dovesti do realizacije događaja A .

III. BAJESOVA VEROVATNOĆA U VREMENSKOJ PROGNOZI

Bajesova verovatnoća, koja se zasniva na Bajesovu teoremu, predstavlja moćan alat u oblasti vremenskih prognoza jer omogućava ažuriranje verovatnoće na osnovu novih informacija.

Bajesova teorema omogućava ažuriranje događaja na primer vremenskih pojava na osnovu novih podataka. Formula za Bajesovu teoremu koja je preuzeta iz [5] je sledeća:

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A) \cdot P(A)}{P(B)} \text{ gdje:}$$

- $P(A|B)$: Aposteriorna verovatnoća to jeste verovatnoća događaja A nakon što su dostupni podaci B ,
- $P(A)$: Apriorna verovatnoća to jeste verovatnoća događaja pre novih podataka,
- $P(B|A)$: Verovatnoća podataka pod uslovom da se dogodilo događaj A .
- $P(B)$: Marginalna verovatnoća podataka.

A. Apriorne podatke i uslovne verovatnoće za predviđanje

Meteorolozi koriste apriorne podatke i uslovne verovatnoće kako bi poboljšali tačnost vremenskih prognoza. Kako je rečeno u knjizi [7] ova kombinacija informacija omogućava im da donesu bolje odluke u situacijama sa nesigurnostima i složenim vremenskim obrascima.

Aprioroni podaci predstavljaju informacije koje su poznate pre nego što se izvrši novo posmatranje ili eksperiment. U meteorologiji to uključuje:

- Istorijske podatke: ovo su podaci o vremenskim uslovima iz prošlih godina koji se koriste za identifikaciju obrazca ili trendova. Na primjer ako istorijski podaci pokazuju da u određenom mesecu uvek pada određena količina kiše, ti podaci se koriste kao osnova za buduće prognoze.

- Geografski i sezonski obrasci: Razumjevanje kako geografski faktori, kao što su visina ili blizina mora utiču na vremenske obrasce takođe predstavlja apriorne podatke.

Uslovne verovatnoće se koriste za izračunavanje verovatnosti određenog događaja uzimajući u obzir druge poznate događaje. U meteorologiji se često koristi kako bi se modelovali različiti scenariji:

- Modeliranje klimatskih varijabli: Na primjer uslovna verovatnoća se koristi za izračunavanje verovatnoće padavina ako je poznato da su temperature veće od određenog praga. Ova vrsta analiza pomaže meteorolozima da razumiju složenije međuzavisnosti između različitih meteoroloških faktora.
- Bajesov pristup: Korišćenje Bajesove teoreme omogućava meteorolozima da ažuriraju svoje verovatnoće u svetlu novih podataka. Na primjer ako nova meteorološka posmatranja pokazuju da su se uslovi promijenili, uslovne verovatnoće se revidiraju na osnovu tih informacija.

Slika 1. Verovatnoća kiše [1]

Redom su date tabele sa odgovarajućim verovatnoćama. Na tabeli I su date verovatnoće za vlažnost (humidity), na tabeli II su date verovatnoće za padavine (rainfall) i na tabeli III su date verovatnoće za temperaturu (temperature):

	Low	Medium	High
Yes	0.1	0.3	0.6
No	0.9	0.7	0.4

Tabela I
VLAŽNOST (HUMIDITY)

	Low	Medium	High
Yes	0.1	0.2	0.7
No	0.9	0.8	0.3

Tabela II
PADAVINE(RAINFALL)

	Low	Medium	High
Yes	0.1	0.2	0.7
No	0.9	0.8	0.3

Tabela III
TEMPERATURA(TEMPERATURE)

B. Kako se koristi Bajes za procenu verovatnoće kiše

Bajesovska mreža predstavlja moćan alat za procenu verovatnoće različitih događaja u sistemima s više varijabli. U kontekstu meteoroloških prognoza, Bajesovske mreže mogu se koristiti za procenu verovatnoće padavina na osnovu nekoliko ključnih vremenskih parametara poput vlažnosti, temperature i prethodnih padavina. Ovaj pristup omogućava kombinovanje postojećih informacija i trenutnim vremenskim uslovima kako bi se izračunala verovatnoća da će padati kiša.

Bajesovska mreža funkcioniše tako što modelira međusobno zavisnost varijabli koje utiču na prognozu kiše. Varijable kao što su vlažnost, temperatura i padavine su direktno povezane s verovatnoćom padavina, a Bajesova teorema omogućava korišćenje ovih veza kako bi se napravile tačnije prognoze. Na primjer visoka vlažnost i niska temperatura mogu značajno povećati verovatnoću padavina, dok su suprotni indikatori suhog vremena. U nastavku slijedi jedan konkretan primjer koji je preuzet iz članka [1], koji nam pokazuje detaljno kako se koristi Bajes za procenu verovatnoće kiše.

Na slici 1 je prikazano Bajesovska mreža za predviđanje šanse za kišu. Postoje tri nezavisne varijable, vlažnost (humidity), temperatura (temperature) i padavine (rainfall) koje su direktno pod uticajem kiše (rain). Prikazane su odgovarajuće uslovne tabele verovatnoća za svaku varijablu. Simboli yes i no označavaju da ima kiše i da nema kiše. Vrijednosti za vlažnost, temperaturu i padavine su u tri klase: niska(low), srednja(medium) i visoka(high).

Budući da su izlazni podaci neuronske mreže podaci prognoze potrebno je navesti nivo pouzdanosti s kojim će se ti podaci zapravo dogoditi. Da bismo izvršili ovaj zadatak koristimo Bajesovsku mrežu. Bajesovska mreža je struktura podataka koja predstavlja zavisnost između varijabli s konciznom specifikacijom bilo koje potpune zajedničke verovatnoće distribucije.

Topologija Bajesovske mreže za izračunavanje šanse za kišu prikazana je na slici 1. Tri varijable vlažnost, temperatura i padavine su uslovno nezavisne jedna od druge pod pretpostavkom da je padala kiša. Promjene u vrijednostima vlažnosti, temperature i padavina direktno su pod uticajem kiše, dok među njima ne postoji direktna uzoročno-posljedična veza.

Potpuna zajednička verovatnoćna distribucija Bajesove mreže data je formulom: $P(x_1, \dots, x_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(x_i | \text{roditelji}(x_i))$

gde roditelji (x_i) označavaju specifične vrijednosti varijabli koje direktno utiču na x_i u ovom slučaju to su temperatura,

vlažnost i padavine. Dakle za Bajesovsku mrežu prikazanu ne slici 1 zajednička distribucija je data kao :

$$P(R, H, T, RF) = P(H | R)P(T | R)P(RF | R)P(R)$$

gde je R kiša, H je vlažnost, T je temperatura i RF su padavine.

Ulazne vrijednosti za instancu vlažnost i temperatura kreću se od 0 do 100. Vrijenost vlažnosti i temperature kategorizirane su kao niske, srednje i visoke. Procentualna vrijednost vlažnosti dobija se iz izlaznih podataka neuronske mreže. Procentualna vrijednost za temperaturu izračunava se korišćenjem omjera mokrog i suhog termometra (Mokri termometar/Suhi termometar) $\times 100$ koristi se za temperaturu u instanci Bajesovske mreže. Kada su sve vrijednosti poznate, možemo izračunati verovatnoću kiše ako je vlažnost niska, temperatura visoka, a padavine niske. Izračun je sledeći:

$$\begin{aligned} P(R=DA, H=Niska, T=Visoka, RF=Niske) &= \\ P(H=Niska | R=DA)P(T=Visoka | R=DA) &= \\ P(RF=Niska | R=Da)P(R=Da) &= \\ (0.1)(0.7)(0.1)(1.45) &= 0.00315 \end{aligned}$$

dakle verovatnoća da će padati kiša kada je vlažnost niska, temperatura visoka, a padavine niske iznosi 0.315%.

Egzaktna inferencija može se izvršiti kada nisu svi podaci o varijablama dostupni. U ovom slučaju imamo tri tipa varijabli naime upitne varijable, dokazne varijable i skrivene varijable. Ako želimo odrediti verovatnoću kiše znajući da je vlažnost srednja, a temperatura visoka, tada je upitna varijabla kiša, dokazane varijable su vlažnost i temperatura, dok su skrivene varijable padavine. Formula koju ćemo koristiti za izračunavanje ove vjerovatnoće je:

$$\begin{aligned} P(R=DA | H=Srednja, T=Visoka) &= \\ \alpha P(R=DA) \sum_{RF} P(H=Srednja | R=Da)P(T=Visoka &= \\ | R=Da)P(RF | R=Da) \end{aligned}$$

gdje je α recipročna vrijednost od

$$P(R=Da | H=Srednja, T=Visoka) + P(R=Ne | H=Srednja, T=Visoka) \cdot \sum_{RF} P(H=srednja | R=Da)P(T=Visoka | R=da)P(RF | R=Da)$$

znači da ćemo sabrati ovaj proizvod kada su RF niske, RF srednje i RF visoke. Dakle:

$$P(R=Da | H=Srednje, T=Visoka) = \alpha(0.45)(0.3)(0.7)(0.1+0.2+0.7) = 0.0945\alpha$$

$$P(R=Ne | H=Srednje, T=Visoka) = \alpha(0.55)(0.7)(0.3)(0.9+0.8+0.3) = 0.231\alpha$$

Dakle,

$$P(R=Da | H=Srednje, T=Visoko) = (0.0945)(3.072197) = 0.290323$$

ili 29% šanse da ima kiše.

$$P(R=Ne | H=Srednje, T=Visoko) = (0.231)(3.072197) = 0.709078$$

ili 78% šanse da nema kiše.

C. Prednosti koje daje Bajesova verovatnoća u vremenskoj prognozi

Bajesova verovatnoća pruža ključne prednosti u vremenskoj prognozi jer koristi nove podatke za stalno poboljšavanje. Iz knjige [7] možemo izvući koje su dobre strane Bajesove verovatnoće u vremenskoj prognozi. Njene prednosti su sledeće:

- **Ažuriranje na osnovu novih informacija:** Bajesovske metode omogućavaju da se meterološki modeli stalno ažuriraju sa novim informacijama, što je važno jer se

vremenske prilike brzo mijenjaju. Svaki novi podatak o temperaturi, pritisku, vlažnosti utiče na verovatnoću događaja, tako da Bajesovi modeli mogu precizno prilagoditi prognozi u stvarnom vremenu. Ova sposobnost osigurava tačnije prognoze u promenljivim vremenskim uslovima.

- **Integrišu istorijske podatke i trenutna merenja:** Bajesova verovatnoća koristi prethodne podatke zajedno sa novim opažanjima, što je posebno korisno u klimatskim modelima, gde istorijski obrasci igraju važnu ulogu. Takođe Bajesovi modeli omogućavaju korišćenje informacija iz različitih izvora uključujući satelitske podatke i podatke sa meteroloških stanica.
- **Predviđanje sa ocjenom neizvesnošću:** Bajesova verovatnoća u vremenskoj prognozi ne pruža samo najverovatniji ishod, već i interval neizvesnosti. To znači da se prognoza može dati u formatu "š verovatnoćom od 70% očekuje se kiša", što meterolozima i javnosti daje realniji prikaz potencijalnih ishoda.
- **Prilagodljivost složenim vremenskim promenama:** Bajesovski pristup je prilagodljiv modelima vremenskih seriji, što znači da može reagovati na ekstremne vremenske događaje kao što su cikloni i talasi vrućine. Takva fleksibilnost čini Bajesovske modele korisnim u područjima gde su vremenske prilike vrlo promenljive, kao što su tropska ili polarna područja.
- **Smanjenje grešaka u prognozama:** Upotrebom Bayesian Model Avering tehnika, Bajesovska verovatnoća pomaže u kombinovanju rezultata iz više meteroloških modela, čime se smanjuje ukupna greška. Tako kombinovana prognoza smanjuje šanse za velike greške u proceni padavina, temperature i drugih vremenskih uslova.

IV. DALJE PRIMJENE BAJESOVE VEROVATNOĆE

Iz rada [4] možemo vidjeti da primjena Bajesove verovatnoće obuhvata razne oblasti, što demonstrira njenu široku primenu u realnim situacijama. Bajesova verovatnoća predstavlja temeljni koncept u statistici i matematici, omogućavajući donošenje zaključaka na osnovu verovatnoća koje se ažuriraju u svetlu novih podataka. Njena praktična primena prevaizlazi teoretske granice i nalazi značajnu upotrebu u različitim naučnim, tehnološkim i industrijskim oblastima.

Primjena Bajesove verovatnoće u različitim oblastima:

• Medicina

U medicinskoj dijagnostici Bajesova verovatnoća se koristi za procjenu vjerovatnoće da pacijent ima određenu bolest na osnovu simptoma i rezultata testova. Primjer bi bio utvrđivanje verovatnoće prisustva bolesti nakon pozitivnog testa, uzimajući u obzir prethodnu učestalost bolesti i tačnost dijagnostičkog testa.

• Finansije i ekonomija

U ekonomiji i finansijama, koristi se sa donošenje odluka u uslovima nesigurnosti. Na primjer, investitori koriste Bjesov pristup za procjenu rizika ulaganja na osnovu prethodnih tržišnih trendova i trenutnih informacija.

- **Pravo**

Bajesova verovatnoća može pomoći u procjeni verovatnoće krivice osumnjičenog na osnovu dokaza. Na primjer, ako se pronađe DNK osumnjičenog na mjestu zločina, može se izračunati verovatnoća da je osumnjičeni stvarno počinio zločin, uimajući u obzir verovatnoće slučajne podudarnosti DNK.

- **Svakodnevne situacije**

Bajesova formula se primjenjuje u donošenju odluka u svakodnevnim životnim situacijama, poput procjene verovatnoće kašnjenja autobusa na osnovu vremenskih uslova ili procjene verovatnoće uspjeha na određenim aktivnostima na osnovu prethodnih iskustva.

- **Sport**

U članku [6] možemo čitati da se Bajesova verovatnoća u sportu koristi za analizu performansi timova i igrača, kao i za predviđanje ishoda utakmica. Analitičari koriste ovaj pristup kako bi procenili verovatnoću pobjede određenog tima. Takođe Bajesova verovatnoća omogućava trenerima da donesu informisane odluke tokom utakmice, kao što su zamene igrača ili promene taktike, na osnovu trenutnog stanja igre, pa se na taj način pomaže u optimizaciji strategije i donošenju odluka koje mogu značajno uticati na ishod utakmice.

- **Astronomija**

Na osnovu informacija iz članka [3] Bajesova verovatnoća se u astronomiji koristi za tumačenje i analizu podataka koje dolaze iz različitih izvora, kao što su teleskopi i sateliti. Astronomi koriste ovaj pristup kako bi procenili verovatnoću određenih kosmičkih fenomena. Takođe Bajesova verovatnoća pomaže i u merenju kosmoloških parametara, kao što su starost svemira i količina tamne materije, na osnovu podataka sa teleskopa. Ovaj pristup omogućava astronomima da stalno ažuriraju svoje teorije u skladu sa novim podacima, čime se unapređuju naša znanja o svemiru.

V. ZAKLJUČAK

Bajesova verovatnoća predstavlja izuzetan moćan alat u analizi podataka, donošenju odluka i predviđanjima u raznim oblastima ljudske delatnosti. U ovom radu, detaljno smo se osvrnuli na njene osnove, primenu u vremenskoj prognozi, i šire mogućnosti koje pruži u drugim domenima. Analiza je pokazala da Bajesov pristup ima ključnu prednost u integraciji apriornih informacija sa novim podacima, omogućavajući preciznije procene u situacijama gde su podaci ograničeni, neizvesni ili podloženi promenama.

U kontekstu vremenske prognoze, Bajesova verovatnoća je osvetila nove mogućnosti u korišćenju apriornih podataka i uslovnih verovatnoća za predviđanje vremenskih pojava. Uvođenjem ovog pristupa u meteorološke modele, omogućeno je kombinovanje istorijskih obrazaca i aktuelnih podataka na način koji povećava tačnost prognoza. Na primer, procena verovatnoće kiše putem Bajesa jasno demonstrira kako se uzimaju u obzir prethodna iskustva (kao što su sezonski trendovi) i trenutni faktori (kao što su promene temperature,

vlažnost i padavine) kako bi se došlo do stabilnijeg rezultata.

Jedan od ključnih uvida rada jeste da Bajesova verovatnoća omogućava prilagodljivost i sposobnost učenja novih informacija. Ova dinamičnost je naročito korisna u vremenskim prognozama, gde se uslovi često menjaju, a pouzdanost modela zavisi od njegove sposobnosti da se prilagodi na osnovu ažuriranih podataka. Pored toga, uvođenje Bajesa u meteorologiji pruža dodatne prednosti, kao što su smanjenje neizvesnosti u procenama i mogućnost obuhvatanja složenih međuzavisnosti među različitim meteorološkim parametrima.

Van vremenske prognoze, Bajesova verovatnoća nalazi široku primenu u oblastima poput medicine, ekonomije. Njena univerzalnost potiče iz fleksibilnosti u radu sa različitim vrstama podataka i sposobnosti da pruži uvid u složene sisteme.

Zaključno, Bajesova verovatnoća pruža neprocenjivu vrednost u savremenom svetu, koji je preplavljen informacijama i izazovima u njihovoj interpretaciji. Njen doprinos nije samo u poboljšanju preciznosti prognoza i odluka, već i u transformaciji načina na koji razmišljamo o verovatnoći, neizvesnosti i učenje iz podataka. Kao takva, ona ostaje osnova za inovacije u raznim naučnim i praktičnim disciplinama, podsećajući nas na značaj i kombinovanja teorijskog znanja i praktičnih alata za rešavanje problema u svakodnevnom životu. Rad na ovu temu pokazao je ne samo važnost Bajesa u vremenskoj prognozi, već i njegov potencijal za dalju primenu u različitim sferama, čime se otvara prostor za nove mogućnosti istraživanja i razvoja.

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Markovljevi lanci u finansijama

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Sažetak—Markovljevi lanci su stohastički procesi koji se često primjenjuju u različitim oblastima, a naročito u finansijama, zbog svoje sposobnosti da modeluju promjenljive tržišne uslove i predviđaju kretanje cijena ili drugih ekonomskih vrijednosti. Ovaj rad istražuje osnovne principe Markovljevih lanaca, sa naglaskom na njihovu podjelu na diskretne i neprekidne tipove. Diskretni Markovljevi lanci, koji modeluju promjene u vremenskim intervalima, često se koriste za modelovanje tržišta akcija ili kamatnih stopa, dok neprekidni Markovljevi procesi omogućavaju precizniju analizu promjena neprekidnosti, kao što je kretanje cijena u realnom vremenu. Kroz razmatranje Monte Carlo metode, koja je popularna tehnika za simulaciju i procjenu vjerovatnoća u ovim procesima, rad pokazuje kako se Markovljevi lanci primjenjuju za rješavanje problema u finansijama, kao što su procjena rizika, volatilnosti i optimizacija portfolija. Takođe, razmatramo prednosti i ograničenja Markovljevih lanaca u kontekstu finansijskih modela, uključujući jednostavnost modelovanja, ali i izazove povezane sa njihovim pretpostavkama i ograničenjima u dinamičnim tržišnim uslovima. Takođe, razmatrane su i mogućnosti kombinovanja Markovljevih lanaca sa drugim metodama, poput Monte Carlo simulacija, radi unaprijeđenja tačnosti prognoza. Na kraju, rad pruža osnovne smjernice za dalja istraživanja u primjeni Markovljevih lanaca u finansijskim analizama i donošenju odluka.

Ključne riječi—stohastički procesi, Markovljevi lanci, Monte Carlo metoda, finansije.

I. UVOD

U svijetu finansija, donošenje odluka često zavisi od predviđanja kretanja tržišta, koje je, zbog svoje složenosti i nesigurnosti, veoma izazovno. Da bi se efikasno oblikovala ova neizvjesnost, koriste se različiti matematički alati, među kojima se stohastički procesi izdvajaju kao ključni. Ovi procesi omogućavaju analizu slučajnih promjena koje se dešavaju tokom vremena, a među najpoznatijima su Markovljevi lanci. Temelje se na principu „memorije bez prošlosti“. Markovljevi lanci omogućavaju oblikovanje sistema čije stanje u budućnosti zavisi samo od trenutnog stanja, a ne od prethodnih događaja.

U prvom dijelu rada istražuju se osnovni principi stohastičkih procesa, zatim su detaljnije analizirani Markovljevi lanci i njihova primjena u finansijskim modelima, kao i prednosti i ograničenja ovog pristupa. Kroz ovu analizu, cilj je prikazati kako Markovljevi lanci mogu unaprijediti strategije u finansijama, ali i ukazati na izazove s kojima se suočavaju u ovom kontekstu. S obzirom na sve veću kompleksnost finansijskih tržišta, upotreba sofisticiranih modela kao što su Markovljevi lanci može doprinjeti efikasnijem donošenju odluka i upravljanju rizikom. Razumijevanje kako ovi modeli

funkcionišu i kako se mogu primijeniti u praksi može imati značajan uticaj na strategije investiranja i analizu tržišta.

U finansijama, Markovljevi lanci se koriste za oblikovanje promjena cijena akcija, kamatnih stopa, kao i rizika u portfolijima. Kroz ovaj pristup, investitori i analitičari mogu bolje razumjeti dinamiku tržišta i optimizovati svoje odluke u situacijama sa visokim stepenom nesigurnosti.

Markovljevi lanci u finansijama nude jednostavnu i efikasnu analizu tržišta, omogućavajući oblikovanje rizika i simulaciju scenarija. Međutim, njihova ograničenja uključuju pretpostavku da zavise samo od trenutnog stanja, zanemarujući istorijske podatke, kao i stacionarnost, koja nije realna u dinamičnom tržištu. Takođe, ne uzimaju u obzir kompleksne spoljne faktore koji utiču na tržište.

U naučnoj literaturi, novijeg datuma, gotovo da nije moguće ne susresti se sa nekim oblikom naglaska na rizik, kao ključnim za savremene tržišne uslove [1]. Što ukazuje na veću upotrebu finansijskih i ostalih analiza. Jednostavno rečeno, za promjenljivu, čija se vrijednost mijenja tokom vremena na način koji ne prati neki predvidljiv (deterministički) šablon, kažemo da prati stohastički proces. U okviru tog procesa, razlikujemo diskretno i neprekidno vrijeme, u zavisnosti od toga da li se promjene dešavaju u određenim, fiksno definisanim momentima, ili se dešavaju neprekidno. Stohastički procesi mogu obuhvatati diskretne ili neprekidne promjenljive, pri čemu posmatrane promjenljive mogu mijenjati vrijednost samo u izvjesnim diskretnim iznosima. Na slici 1 prikazani su mogući oblici slučajnih procesa kao familije slučajnih promjenljivih.

Cijene akcija, primjera radi, mogu mijenjati vrijednost samo u unaprijed određenom iznosu. Uprkos tome, ovaj pristup se primjenjuje u finansijskom oblikovanju. To su Markovljev, Vinerov i Itoov proces [1].

S \ T	Diskretan	Neprekidan
Diskretan	Slučajni niz	Slučajan proces
Neprekidan	Slučajni niz	Slučajan proces

Slika 1. Grafikon

II. STOHAŠTIČKI PROCES

Neka je $X(t)$ slučajna promjenljiva, za $t \in I$. Što znači da na skup svih slučajnih promjenljivih $X(t)$, $t \in I$ možemo gledati kao na slučajnu veličinu koja se mijenja u vremenu, odnosno slučajnu funkciju vremena. Tada je za nas $X(t)$ jedan slučajni ili stohastički proces.

Neka I označava proizvoljan neprazan skup i neka je (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) prostor vjerovatnoće [1].

Definicija 1. Familija

$$\{X_t : t \in I\} \text{ Rd}$$

vrijednosnih slučajnih promjenljivih se zove **stohastički (slučajan) proces** sa parametarskim (indeksnim) skupom I i prostorom stanja Rd . Ako je parametarski skup konačan tada jednostavno imamo konačno mnogo slučajnih promjenljivih. Ako je taj skup prebrojiv govorimo o nizu slučajnih promjenljivih. Izraz „proces“ najčešće koristimo u slučaju kada parametarski skup nije prebrojiv [1].

Definicija 2. Neka je

$$\{X_t : t \in [t_0, T]\}$$

slučajan proces. Tada je $X_t(\cdot) \text{ Rd}$ - vrijednosna slučajna promjenljiva za svako fiksirano $t \in [t_0, T]$. Tu slučajnu promjenljivu nazivamo zasijek ili siječenje stohastičkog procesa [1].

Definicija 3. Neka je

$$\{X_t : t \in [t_0, T]\}$$

slučajan proces. Tada je za svako fiksirano $\omega \in \Omega$, $X(\omega) \text{ Rd}$ vrijednosna funkcija na $[t_0, T]$ i zove se staza (trajektorija) slučajnog procesa [1].

A. Markovljevi lanci

Markovljevi lanci su matematički modeli koji opisuju niz mogućih događaja u kojem vjerovatnoća svakog događaja zavisi samo od stanja postignutog u prethodnom događaju. Drugim riječima, to su stohastički procesi koji prolaze kroz prelaze iz jednog stanja u drugo u nizu diskretnih vremenskih koraka.

Markovljev lanac, nazvan po Andreyu Markovu, predstavlja niz stanja [2]. U svakom trenutku stanje može preći u neko novo stanje ili može ostati u istom stanju. Promjene stanja nazivaju se tranzicije. Niz diskretnih slučajnih promjenljivih (x_0, x_1, x_2, \dots) predstavlja stohastički lanac.

Slučajne promjenjive uzimaju vrijednosti u konačnom skupu $S = S_0, S_1, \dots, S_n$. Lanac X_0, X_1, \dots je Markovljev lanac prvog reda, ako za sve izbore stanja

$$S_0, S_1, \dots, S_n \in S$$

vrijedi

$$P(X_n = s_n | X_{n-1} = s_{n-1}, \dots, X_0 = s_0).$$

Ovdje trenutak n predstavlja sadašnjost, a $0, \dots, n-1$ prošlost. Sadašnje stanje s_n zavisi samo o prethodnom s_{n-1} stanju, ali ne i o načinu na koji je proces dospio u prethodno stanje to

jest vrijednostima procesa u ranijim trenucima.

Markovljev lanac drugog reda zavisi o 2 prethodna stanja s_{n-1}, s_{n-2} te vrijedi:

$$\begin{aligned} P(X_n = s_n | X_{n-1} = s_{n-1}, \dots, X_0 = s_0) &= \\ &= P(X_n = s_n | X_{n-1} = s_{n-1}, X_{n-2} = s_{n-2}) \end{aligned}$$

Skladno tome, Markovljev lanac k -tog reda zavisi o k prethodnih stanja $s_{n-1}, s_{n-2}, \dots, s_{n-k}$. Viši redovi lanaca „pamte“ dalje u prošlost, daju više informacija o procesu [3]. Prelazi između stanja upravljaju vjerovatnoćama, obično predstavljenim matricom prelaza. Markovljevi lanci se široko koriste u različitim oblastima kao što su teorija vjerovatnoće, statistika, fizika, računarstvo, ekonomija i biologija kako bi modelovali slučajne procese i analizirali njihovo ponašanje tokom vremena.

B. Definicije Markovljevih lanaca

Definicija 4. Neka je (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) prostor vjerovatnoće. Funkciju $X : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$ za koju je skup $\{\omega \in \Omega : X(\omega) \in B\}$ događaj u \mathcal{F} tj. $X^{-1}(B) \in \mathcal{F}$, za svaki $B \in B^n(\mathbb{R})$, zovemo n -dimenzionalan slučajni vektor (ili, kraće, slučajni vektor) [3].

Definicija 5. Neka je S diskretni skup stanja. Slučajni proces $X = (X_n, n \in \mathbb{N}_0)$ na vjerovatnosnom prostoru (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) s vrijednostima u skupu stanja S zovemo Markovljev lanac ako vrijedi:

$$\begin{aligned} P(X_{n+1} = j | X_n = i, X_{n-1} = i_{n-1}, \dots, X_0 = i_0) &= \\ &= P(X_{n+1} = j | X_n = i), \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}_0 \end{aligned}$$

iz za svaki izbor stanja $i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{n-1}, i, j \in S$, za koje su gornje vjerovatnoće dobro definisane.

Definicija 6. Stohastičke procese koji imaju takozvano odsustvo memorije nazivamo **Markovljevim lancima**.

U matematičkom smislu definicija se može izraziti na sledeći način. Slučajni proces $X = X_n, n \in \mathbb{N}$ u prebrojivom prostoru S je Markov lanac sa diskretnim vremenom ako:

$$\forall n \geq 0, X_n \in S$$

$$\forall n \geq 1, \forall i_0, i_1, \dots, i_{n-1}, n \in S$$

C. Osnovna svojstva Markovljevih lanaca

- Markovljevo svojstvo kaže da buduće ponašanje stohastičkog procesa zavisi samo od njegovog trenutnog stanja i nezavisno je od njegove prošlosti, uzimajući u obzir trenutno stanje.
- Diskretni vremenski domen odnosi se na sistem ili proces u kojem je vrijeme podijeljeno na odvojene, različite intervale ili korake. U ovom kontekstu, vrijeme napreduje u nizu diskretnih jedinica, pri čemu svaka jedinica predstavlja fiksni period vremena. Ovi intervali obično su uniformni, što znači da imaju istu dužinu.
- Diskretni prostor stanja se odnosi na skup mogućih stanja u kojima se sistem može nalaziti, pri čemu su ta stanja odvojena i jasno definisana. Ovaj koncept se koristi kada

sistem može zauzeti samo određeni broj diskretnih vrijednosti, umjesto neprekidnog spektra vrijednosti. Diskretni prostor stanja može biti konačan ili beskonačan.

- Vjerovatnoće prelaza se odnose na vjerovatnoće da sistem pređe iz jednog stanja u drugo u narednom koraku vremena. Svaka od ovih vjerovatnoća odgovara prelasku iz određenog početnog stanja u određeno ciljno stanje i obično su predstavljene matricom prelaza
- Ergodičnost kaže da će se nakon dovoljno dugog vremena, lanac stabilizovati i vjerovatnoća prelaska između stanja konvergirati ka određenim vrijednostima, nezavisno od početnog stanja

III. VJEROVATNOĆE PRELAZA I MATRICE PRELAZA

U Markovljevim lancima, vjerovatnoće prelaza i matrice prelaza predstavljaju ključne komponente za oblikovanje i analizu procesa. Da bi bili razumljivi, prvo će biti definisani osnovni pojmovi, a zatim pružiti konkretne primjere kako se koriste u praksi [4].

- Markovljev lanac

Markovljev lanac je niz slučajnih promenljivih X_0, X_1, X_2, \dots koje imaju Markovljevo svojstvo, što znači da je vjerovatnoća prelaza u buduće stanje zavisna samo od trenutnog stanja, a ne od prethodnih stanja. Ovo svojstvo se može izraziti kao:

$$P(X_{n+1} = j \mid X_n = i, X_{n-1} = i_{n-1}, \dots, X_0 = i_0) = P(X_{n+1} = j \mid X_n = i)$$

- Vjerovatnoća prelaza

Vjerovatnoća prelaza predstavlja vjerovatnoću da će sistem preći iz jednog stanja i u drugo stanje j u jednom koraku (ili vremenskom periodu). Ova vjerovatnoća se obično zapisuje kao:

$$P(X_{n+1} = j \mid X_n = i) = p_{ij}$$

Gdje p_{ij} označava vjerovatnoću da će proces preći iz stanja i stanje j .

- Matrica prelaza

Matrica prelaza je kvadratna matrica koja sadrži sve vjerovatnoće prelaza između stanja u Markovljevom lancu. Ako imamo n stanja, matrica prelaza P je nn matrica, gdje je element p_{ij} vjerovatnoća da će lanac preći iz stanja i u stanje j . Matrica prelaza se obično zapisuje kao:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} & \dots & p_{1n} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} & \dots & p_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ p_{n1} & p_{n2} & \dots & p_{nn} \end{bmatrix}$$

Vjerovatnoće prelaza i matrice prelaza su ključni alati u analizi Markovljevih lanaca. Korišćenjem matrica prelaza mogu se lako analizirati i predvidjeti ponašanje sistema u budućnosti. Matrica prelaza može se koristiti za analizu vjerovatnoća u različitim vremenskim intervalima, kao i za računanje stabilnih distribucija i predikciju dugoročnih ponašanja sistema.

IV. MONTE CARLO METODA

Monte Carlo metoda, poznata i kao Monte Carlo simulacije, koristi se uglavnom u tri klase problema: optimizacija, numerička integracija i generiranje uzorka iz distribucije vjerovatnoće. Riječ je o metodi koja pomoću slučajno generisanih vrijednosti i velikog broja ponavljanja opisuje ponašanje složenih sistema. Svoje ime duguje poznatom kazinu smještenom u Kneževini Monako, a uveli su ga Stanislaw Ulam, John von Neumann i Nicholas Metropolis 1946. godine. Iste godine, pojavom prvog elektroničkog računala ENIAC, dolazi do detaljnog proučavanja metode. Ima široku lepezu primjena u područjima u kojima je jasna i očita prisutnost teško mjerljivih slučajnih uticaja, posebno u poslovanju i ulaganju. Koristi se za procjenu vjerovatnoće prekoračenja troškova u velikim projektima i vjerovatnoće da će se cijena imovine promijeniti na određeni način.

Monte Carlo simulacije u osnovi imaju četiri jednostavna koraka:

- 1) Određivanje jednačine prenosa

Za izradu Monte Carlo simulacije potreban nam je model problema kojeg želimo analizirati. Matematički izraz za model naziva se „jednačina prenosa”.

- 2) Definisanje ulaznih parametara

Za svaki faktor u jednačini prenosa trebamo odrediti iz koje distribucije dolazi.

- 3) Simulacija

Potrebno je generisati veliki skup slučajno odabranih vrijednosti.

- 4) Analiza izlaznih podataka

Simulirane podatke uvrstiti u jednačinu prenosa.

Monte Carlo metoda je tehnika koja koristi slučajan uzorak kako bi riješila matematičke probleme koji se ne mogu lako riješiti analitički. Kada se primjeni u kontekstu Markovljevih lanaca, Monte Carlo metoda može biti izuzetno korisna za procjenu i simulaciju različitih procesa i vjerovatnoća koji su vezani za stanje sistema koji se razvija kroz niz diskretnih vremena ili stanja. Markovljevi lanci su matematički modeli za sisteme koji se razvijaju kroz niz stanja, gdje je vjerovatnoća prelaska u sledeće stanje zavisna samo od trenutnog stanja, a ne od prethodnih stanja. Ovaj princip je poznat kao **Markovljevo svojstvo**. Monte Carlo metoda koristi simulaciju kako bi generisala niz stanja koja slijede jedno drugo prema pravilima Markovljevog lanca. Da bi ovo postigla, metoda koristi slučajne uzorke da bi napravila prelaz između stanja prema vjerovatnoćama koje su definisane u matrici prelaza Markovljevog lanca.

Korišćenjem Monte Carlo simulacije, može se procjeniti vjerovatnoća da će Markovljev lanac biti u određenom stanju nakon određenog broja koraka. To se postiže simulacijom velikog broja „lanaca” i izračunavanjem prosječnih vrijednosti ili frekvencija stanja tokom tih simulacija. Monte Carlo metoda može biti korisna za procjenu stacionarnih distribucija Markovljevih lanaca, posebno kada je analitičko rješavanje problema složeno ili neizvodljivo.

Stacionarna distribucija predstavlja stanje sistema kada se ne

mijenja vremenom, to jest kada prelazi između stanja postanu nezavisni od vremena. Monte Carlo metoda se koristi za simulaciju dugačkih sekvenci stanja, posebno u složenim sistemima gdje nije moguće direktno riješiti stacionarne distribucije ili gde su vjerovatnoće prelaza između stanja složene.

Prednosti:

- **Fleksibilnost:** Monte Carlo metoda je jednostavna za implementaciju i može da se koristi za širok spektar problema, uključujući i složene Markovljeve lance sa velikim brojem stanja.
Približna rešenja: Omogućava dobijanje približnih riješenja za probleme gdje analitičko riješenje nije moguće ili je veoma teško izvodljivo.

Izazovi:

- **Potrebno je mnogo simulacija:**
Da bi se dobile tačne procjene, potrebno je da se uradi veliki broj simulacija, što može biti računski zahtjevno, posebno za kompleksne Markovljeve lance.
- **Zavisnost od početnih uslova:**
U nekim slučajevima, početni uslovi mogu značajno uticati na rezultate, a to može biti izazov u dinamičkim okruženjima.

Monte Carlo metoda u kontekstu Markovljevih lanaca je moćan alat za procjenu ponašanja složenih stohastičkih sistema. Omogućava rješavanje problema u situacijama gdje su analitička rješenja teška za primjenu, ili kada su matematički modeli previše složeni da bi ih rješavali tradicionalnim metodama. Kroz simulaciju velikog broja scenarija, Monte Carlo pristup može pružiti približna rješenja za stacionarne distribucije, procjene vremena do apsorpcije i mnoge druge aspekte Markovljevih lanaca.

V. PRIMJENE MARKOVLJEVIH LANACA U FINANSIJAMA

Markovljev lanac je matematički model koji se koristi za analizu sistema koji prelazi iz jednog stanja u drugo, gdje vjerovatnoća prelaska zavisi samo od trenutnog stanja, a ne od prethodnih stanja. Ovaj princip je poznat kao Markovljeva svojstva ili bezmemorijski princip. U finansijama, Markovljevi lanci se koriste za modeliranje različitih aspekata tržišta, jer omogućavaju analizu ponašanja tržišta kroz diskretne, ili neprekidne, prelaze između različitih stanja [4].

A. Oblikovanje cijena imovine

Markovljevi lanci se koriste za oblikovanje promjena cijena imovine (kao što su akcije, obveznice ili valute) koje prelaze između različitih stanja (na primjer „rast“, „pad“, „neutralno“) u zavisnosti od trenutnog stanja tržišta. Pretpostavka je da tržište „ne pamti“ prethodne cikluse, pa se vjerovatnoće prelaza iz jednog stanja u drugo zasnivaju samo na trenutnom stanju. Primjer:

Cijena akcije može biti u jednom od tri stanja: rastuća cijena, opadajuća cijena, i stabilna cijena. Na osnovu istorijskih podataka, Markovljev lanac može izračunati vjerovatnoće prelaza između tih stanja i pomoći u predviđanju budućih cijena akcija.

B. Oblikovanje kreditnih rizika

Markovljevi lanci se koriste u modeliranju kreditnih rejtinga. Rejting preduzeća može prelaziti između različitih stanja, kao što su „AAA“, „AA“, „A“, „B“, i tako dalje. Svaka od ovih kategorija označava različiti nivo kreditnog rizika. Markovljev lanac može da modeluje vjerovatnoće prelaza između tih rejtinga, čime se pomaže u ocjeni vjerovatnoće da će kompanija preći u niži rejting ili čak doći do defaulta (neizmirivanja obaveza).

Primjer:

Kompanija sa kreditnim rejtingom „A“ može imati određene vjerovatnoće za prelaz u niži rejting („BBB“) ili čak u stanje neizmirivanja obaveza („default“).

C. Optimizacija portfolija

U kontekstu portfolija, Markovljevi lanci mogu se koristiti za oblikovanje vjerovatnoća da će portfolijo preći iz jednog stanja (npr. visok rizik) u drugo stanje (npr. nizak rizik). Ovo može biti korisno za optimizaciju portfolija, jer investitori žele da izbjegnju velike gubitke i maksimalizuju profit u različitim tržišnim uslovima.

Primjer:

Investitor može koristiti Markovljev lanac za analizu vjerovatnoće da će njegov portfolijo, koji je trenutno u fazi visokog rizika, preći u fazu niskog rizika, što može značiti promjenu strategije ulaganja.

D. Predviđanje tržišta i ekonomske cikluse

Markovljevi lanci su korisni u analizi ekonomske aktivnosti, jer tržišta i ekonomije prolaze kroz različite faze ciklusa, poput recesije, rasta i stagnacije. Na osnovu istorijskih podataka o tržištu, Markovljev lanac može pomoći u predviđanju kada bi moglo doći do prelaza iz jedne faze u drugu, čime se omogućavaju bolje odluke u investiranju i upravljanju rizikom. Primjer:

Ako ekonomski ciklus prolazi kroz faze recesije, rasta i stagnacije, Markovljev lanac može odrediti vjerovatnoće za prelazak iz recesije u fazu rasta ili stagnacije, što može pomoći u planiranju strategije investicija.

E. Optimizacija strategija trgovanja

U trgovanju na finansijskim tržištima, Markovljevi lanci se koriste za razvoj automatizovanih trgovinskih sistema. Na osnovu analize tržišnih uslova i istorijskih podataka, trgovinski algoritmi mogu koristiti Markovljev lanac za donošenje odluka o tome kada da kupuju ili prodaju imovinu na osnovu vjerovatnoće da će tržište preći u povoljnije stanje.

Primjer:

Trgovci mogu koristiti Markovljev lanac za odlučivanje kada da otvore ili zatvore pozicije na osnovu vjerovatnoće prelaza između stanja tržišta (na primjer stabilno, raste, opada).

VI. PREDNOSTI I OGRANIČENJA MARKOVLJEVIH LANACA U FINANSIJAMA

A. Prednosti primjene Markovljevih lanaca u finansijama

- **Jednostavnost modela:**
Markovljev lanac je relativno jednostavan za implementa-

ciju u finansijskim modelima jer zahtjeva samo informacije o trenutnom stanju, bez potrebe za komplikovanim istorijskim podacima.

- Prilagodljivost:
Markovljevi lanci se mogu koristiti u različitim aspektima finansijskog modelovanja, od predviđanja cijena do analize kreditnog rizika.
- Učinkovitost u predviđanjima:
Korišćenje Markovljevih lanaca može poboljšati tačnost predviđanja kada tržišta prelaze iz jednog stanja u drugo, što je korisno za optimizaciju portfolija i strategija trgovanja.

B. Ograničenja primjene Markovljevih lanaca u finansijama

- Pretpostavka bezmemorijskog svojstva:
Markovljev lanac pretpostavlja da je vjerovatnoća prelaza samo funkcija trenutnog stanja, što može biti nerealno za složene ekonomske ili tržišne sisteme koji zavise od šireg konteksta.
- Nedostatak preciznosti u ekstremnim slučajevima:
U slučajevima tržišnih šokova ili neregularnih promjena, Markovljev lanac može biti manje efikasan jer ne uzima u obzir izuzetke koji ne slijede tipične tranzicije između stanja.

VII. ZAKLJUČAK

Markovljevi lanci predstavljaju snažan alat u oblikovanju i analizi finansijskih sistema, omogućujući predviđanje kretanja tržišta i ekonomskih parametara u uslovima nesigurnosti. Primjena Markovljevih lanaca u finansijama omogućava analizu stanja, oblikovanje cijena, procjenu rizika, kao i optimizaciju investicija. Ovi matematički modeli se koriste za simulaciju različitih ekonomskih scenarija, predviđanje promjena u cijena akcija, analizu kamatnih stopa, kao i za izradu portfolija i strategija upravljanja rizikom.

Iako su Markovljevi lanci vrlo korisni, važno je naglasiti da oni zasnivaju svoje predikcije na pretpostavci da su tržišni uslovi u budućnosti samo zavisni od trenutnog stanja, a ne i od prethodnih događaja. Ova pojednostavljena mogu u nekim situacijama biti ograničavajuća, jer stvarni finansijski sistem često zavisi od mnogo kompleksnijih i dugoročnijih faktora. Takođe, u praksi se često koristi varijacija modela, kao što su hidden Markov models (HMM), koji omogućavaju dodatnu fleksibilnost i preciznost u analizi.

Iako Markovljevi lanci imaju određene limitacije, njihova primjena u finansijama ostaje ključna za donošenje odluka zasnovanih na podacima, kao i za razvijanje strategija koje mogu smanjiti rizik i maksimizirati dobit u dinamičnom i neizvesnom okruženju finansijskih tržišta.

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